

H2020 DAEMON Project
Grant Agreement No. 101017109

D2.1 Initial report on requirements analysis and state-of-the-art frameworks and toolsets

Abstract

The work presented in this deliverable has been carried out by WP2 partners, during the first six months of the project, and it tackles both engineering and research aspects that need to be addressed in the DAEMON project and its vision for a network intelligence (NI) framework. This document presents a detailed specification of the eight network intelligence use cases, namely reconfigurable intelligent surface control (RISC), multi-scale edge resource management (MTERM), in-backhaul support for service intelligence (IBSSI), compute-aware radio scheduling (CAWRS), energy-aware VNF control and orchestration (EAWVNF), self-learning management and orchestration (SLMANO), capacity forecasting (CFORE), and automated anomaly response (AARES). All four tasks (T2.1, T2.2, T2.3, and T2.4) have produced various results, starting with the state-of-the-art analysis of architectural frameworks and toolsets for network management. D2.1 presents initial guidelines on the i) selection, ii) configuration, and iii) orchestration of all NI instances deployed in the network. All three aspects are driven by the time constraints in NI functions execution, considering time as one of the most influential factors when making decisions on selection, configuration, and orchestration, of NI functions and algorithms.

Document properties

Document number	D2.1
Document title	Report on initial requirements analysis and state of art frameworks and toolsets
Document responsible	ADLINK (ADL)
Document editor	Ivan Paez (ADL) Luca Cominardi (ADL)
Document Contributors	Miguel Camelo (IMEC) Paola Soto-Arenas (IMEC) Nina Slamnik-Krijestorac (IMEC) Marco Fiore (IMDEA) Marco Gramaglia (UC3M) Albert Banchs (UC3M) Maria Molina (UC3M) Ana Hernandez (UC3M) Danny de Vleeschauwer (NBL) Chia-Yu Chang (NBL) Andres Garcia-Saavedra (NEC) Andra Lutu (TID) Lidia Fuentes (UMA) Joaquín Ballesteros (UMA) Aspa Skalidi (WINGS) Alexandros Kostopoulos (OTE)
Target dissemination level	Public
Status of the document	Final
Version	1.0

Production properties

Reviewers	Georgios Iosifidis (TUD), Marco Fiore (IMDEA), Andres Garcia (NEC)
------------------	--

Document history

Revision	Date	Issued by	Description
D2.1 Final version	30/06/2021	WP2 participants	Final version for delivery
D2.1 First draft version	30/05/2021	WP2 participants	Initial version by the editors

Disclaimer

This document has been produced in the context of the DAEMON Project. The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no.101017109.

All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors view.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	9
1 Introduction	10
1.1 Objectives, methodology and status of WP2	10
1.2 Relationship to the other deliverables of DAEMON	11
1.3 Structure of the document	11
2 A Vision for a Network Intelligence Framework	12
3 Network Intelligence Use Cases	16
3.1 Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces control.....	17
3.2 Multi-timescale edge resource management	17
3.3 In-backhaul support for service intelligence.....	18
3.4 Compute-aware radio scheduling.....	18
3.5 Energy-aware VNF control & orchestration.....	18
3.6 Self-learning MANO	19
3.7 Capacity forecasting.....	19
3.8 Automated anomaly response	20
4 Network Intelligence Functional Requirements	21
4.1 Methodology	21
4.2 Main requirements and analysis.....	22
4.3 Verification.....	25
5 Network Intelligence Analysis.....	26
5.1 Limits of existing frameworks and architectures	26
5.2 Data management	27
5.3 Control.....	28
5.4 Machine learning workflows	30
5.5 Taxonomies of deep learning applications in wireless networks	32
5.5.1 Traffic Prediction	33
5.5.2 Traffic Classification.....	33
5.5.3 Link Evaluation.....	34
5.5.4 Fault management	34
5.5.5 Congestion control	34
5.5.6 Resource management for Network Resilience.....	34
5.5.7 QoS and QoE management	35
5.5.8 Intrusion and anomaly detection	35
5.5.9 Spectrum allocation	35
5.5.10 Modulation Classification	35
5.5.11 Technology Recognition.....	36
5.5.12 Traffic Routing.....	36
5.5.13 VNF placement	36
5.6 Key Innovations, Gap Analysis.....	36
6 DAEMON initial guidelines	38
6.1 Network-driven specifications of AI for NI.....	38
6.2 Service-driven specifications of AI for NI.....	40
6.2.1 Use cases with service-driven specifications	40
6.2.2 Customized and adaptable AI for NI	41
7 Conclusions & Future Work.....	43
8 References	45
9 Appendix A: NI Use Cases Functional Requirements	50
9.1 RIS control	51

9.2	Multi-timescale edge resource management	53
9.3	In-backhaul support for service intelligence.....	67
9.4	Compute-aware radio scheduling.....	69
9.5	Energy-aware VNF placement.....	71
9.6	Self-learning MANO	76
9.7	Capacity forecasting.....	80
9.8	Automated anomaly response	82
9.9	Non-functional requirements	84
9.10	Verification.....	90
9.10.1	Functional requirements: RIS control.....	90
9.10.2	Functional requirements: Multi-timescale Edge resource management.....	90
9.10.3	Functional requirements: In-backhaul support for service intelligence.....	91
9.10.4	Functional requirements: Compute-aware radio scheduling.....	91
9.10.5	Functional requirements: Energy-aware VNF placement	91
9.10.6	Functional requirements: Self-learning MANO	92
9.10.7	Functional requirements: Capacity forecasting.....	92
9.10.8	Functional requirements: Automated anomaly response	92
9.10.9	Non-functional requirements.....	92
10	Appendix B: Analysis of Existing Frameworks and Architectures	94
10.1	ETSI MEC.....	94
10.1.1	MEC platform functions.....	94
10.1.2	Gaps	95
10.2	ETSI NFV	95
10.3	ETSI ENI.....	99
10.4	ORAN.....	100
10.5	OSM	102
10.6	3GPP.....	103
10.7	ONAP.....	105
11	Appendix C: MLOps.....	108

List of Figures

Figure 2-1. Concept of the DAEMON NI-native architecture.	13
Figure 4-1. NI use cases functional requirements.	23
Figure 4-2. Percentage of requirements that address each KPI.	24
Figure 4-3. Risk level percentages.	25
Figure 4-4. Risk level percentages per cluster.	25
Figure 5-1. NI-assisted hierarchical multi-timescale management and orchestration of services and resources.	26
Figure 5-2. Simplified machine learning workflow.	30
Figure 5-3. DAEMON ML workflows.	31
Figure 6-1. Network Intelligence degrees of freedom, input-output relationship, and real-time constraints subject to infrastructure observability and controllability.	38
Figure 9-1. NI use cases functional requirements.	50
Figure 9-2. RIS control requirements.	51
Figure 9-3. Multi-timescale edge resource management requirements – Part 1.	53
Figure 9-4. Multi-timescale edge resource management requirements – Part 2.	54
Figure 9-5. IBSSI functional requirements.	67
Figure 9-6. CAWRS non-functional requirements.	69
Figure 9-7. EAWVNF functional and non-functional requirements.	71
Figure 9-8. SLMANO functional and non-functional requirements.	76
Figure 9-9. CFORE functional and non-functional requirements.	80
Figure 9-10. AARES functional requirements.	82
Figure 10-1. Multi-access edge system reference architecture variant for MEC in NFV [28].	94
Figure 10-2. The ETSI NFV-MANO architectural framework with reference points.	95
Figure 10-3. High-level overview of steps in a closed loop.	97
Figure 10-4. High-Level Functional Architecture of ENI When an API Broker Is Used.	99
Figure 10-5. O-RAN architecture.	101
Figure 10-6. O-RAN Deployment Models.	101
Figure 10-7. OSM as a network service orchestrator for NaaS.	103
Figure 10-8. 5G System architecture.	104
Figure 10-9. Analytics for the 5G System [113].	104
Figure 10-10. Extended data analytics for the 5GS [114].	105
Figure 10-11. MDAF and MDAS [115].	105
Figure 10-12. Functional view of the ONAP architecture.	106
Figure 11-1. Example of MLOps workflow.	108

List of Tables

Table 3-1. Mapping of NI use-cases.....	16
Table 4-1. Identifiers, partners in charge, reviewers, and project tasks of NI-assisted functionalities.....	21
Table 5-1. Summary of NI control timescale characteristics.....	30
Table 5-2. Summary of NI training timescale characteristics.....	31
Table 5-3. AI/ML applications in networking.....	33
Table 9-1. FR-RIS-000 description.....	51
Table 9-2. FR-RIS-001 description.....	51
Table 9-3. FR-RIS-002 description.....	52
Table 9-4. FR-MTERM-000 description.....	55
Table 9-5. FR-MTERM-001 description.....	55
Table 9-6. FR-MTERM-002 description.....	55
Table 9-7. FR-MTERM-003 description.....	56
Table 9-8. FR-MTERM-003.00 description.....	57
Table 9-9. FR-MTERM-003.01 description.....	57
Table 9-10. FR-MTERM-003.02 description.....	57
Table 9-11. FR-MTERM-003.03 description.....	58
Table 9-12. FR-MTERM-004 description.....	58
Table 9-13. FR-MTERM-005 description.....	59
Table 9-14. FR-MTERM-006 description.....	59
Table 9-15. FR-MTERM-007 description.....	60
Table 9-16. FR-MTERM-007.00 description.....	60
Table 9-17. FR-MTERM-007.01 description.....	60
Table 9-18. FR-MTERM-008 description.....	61
Table 9-19. FR-MTERM-009 description.....	61
Table 9-20. FR-MTERM-010 description.....	61
Table 9-21. FR-MTERM-011 description.....	62
Table 9-22. FR-MTERM-012 description.....	62
Table 9-23. FR-MTERM-013 description.....	63
Table 9-24. FR-MTERM-014 description.....	63
Table 9-25. FR-MTERM-014.00 description.....	63
Table 9-26. FR-MTERM-015 description.....	64
Table 9-27. FR-MTERM-015.00 description.....	64
Table 9-28. FR-MTERM-015.01 description.....	65
Table 9-29. FR-MTERM-016 description.....	65
Table 9-30. FR-MTERM-017 description.....	65
Table 9-31. FR-MTERM-018 description.....	66
Table 9-32. FR-MTERM-019 description.....	66
Table 9-33. FR-IBSSI-000 description.....	67
Table 9-34. FR-IBSSI-001 description.....	67
Table 9-35. FR-IBSSI-002 description.....	68
Table 9-36. FR-CAWRS-000 description.....	69
Table 9-37. NFR-CAWRS-000 description.....	69
Table 9-38. NFR-CAWRS-001 description.....	70
Table 9-39. NFR-CAWRS-002 description.....	70
Table 9-40. FR-EAWVNF-000 description.....	72
Table 9-41. FR-EAWVNF-001 description.....	72
Table 9-42. FR-EAWVNF-001.00 description.....	72
Table 9-43. FR-EAWVNF-001.01 description.....	73
Table 9-44. FR-EAWVNF-002 description.....	73
Table 9-45. FR-EAWVNF-003 description.....	73
Table 9-46. FR-EAWVNF-003.00 description.....	74

Table 9-47. FR-EAWVNF-003.01 description.....	74
Table 9-48. FR-EAWVNF-004 description.....	75
Table 9-49. FR-EAWVNF-004.00 description.....	75
Table 9-50. FR-EAWVNF-004.01 description.....	75
Table 9-51. FR-SLMANO-000 description.....	76
Table 9-52. FR-SLMANO-001 description.....	77
Table 9-53. FR-SLMANO-002 description.....	77
Table 9-54. FR-SLMANO-003 description.....	77
Table 9-55. FR-SLMANO-004 description.....	78
Table 9-56. FR-SLMANO-005 description.....	78
Table 9-57. FR-SLMANO-006 description.....	79
Table 9-58. FR-CFORE-000 description.....	80
Table 9-59. FR-CFORE-001 description.....	80
Table 9-60. FR-CFORE-002 description.....	81
Table 9-61. FR-CFORE-003 description.....	81
Table 9-62. FR-AARES-000 description.....	82
Table 9-63. FR-AARES-001 description.....	82
Table 9-64. FR-AARES-002 description.....	83
Table 9-65. FR-AARES-003 description.....	83
Table 9-66. NFR-RIS-000 description.....	84
Table 9-67. NFR-RIS-001 description.....	84
Table 9-68. NFR-RIS-002 description.....	84
Table 9-69. NFR-EAWVNF-001 description.....	84
Table 9-70. NFR-EAWVNF-002 description.....	85
Table 9-71. NFR-EAWVNF-003 description.....	85
Table 9-72. NFR-CFORE-001 description.....	85
Table 9-73. NFR-CFORE-002 description.....	86
Table 9-74. NFR-MTERM-001 description.....	86
Table 9-75. NFR-MTERM-002 description.....	87
Table 9-76. NFR-MTERM-003 description.....	87
Table 9-77. NFR-MTERM-004 description.....	87
Table 9-78. NFR-SLMANO-001 description.....	88
Table 9-79. NFR-CAWRS-000 description.....	88
Table 9-80. NFR-CAWRS-001 description.....	89
Table 9-81. NFR-CAWRS-002 description.....	89
Table 10-1. ENI use cases.....	98

List of Acronyms

AARES - Automated Anomaly REsponse
AI - Artificial Intelligence
ARIMA - Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
B5G - Beyond 5G
CAWRS - Compute-aware radio scheduling
CFORE - Capacity FOREcasting
CNF - Cloud-native Network Function
CU - Centralized Unit
DL - Deep Learning
DNN - Deep Neural Networks
DRL - Deep Reinforcement Learning
DU - Distributed Unit
EAWVNF - Energy-aware VNF control & orchestration
GPU - Graphs Processor Unit
IBSSI - In-Backhaul Support for Service Intelligence
LP - Linear Programming
LSTM - Long-Short Memory
MANO - MANagement and Orchestration
MTERM - Multi-Timescale Edge Resource Management
ML - Machine Learning
NI - Network Intelligence
NSaaS -Network Slice as a Service
PNF - Physical Network Function
QoE - Quality of Experience
QoS - Quality of Service
RAN - Radio Access Network
RIS - Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
RISC - RIS Control
RL - Reinforcement Learning
RNN - Recurrent Neural Network
RU - Radio Unit
RTT - Round-Trip Time
SDN - Software Defined Network
SL - Supervised Learning
SLA - Service Level Agreement
SLMANO - Self-Learning MANO
SVR - Support Vector Regression
TC - Traffic classification
TCP - Transmission Control Protocol
TP - Traffic Prediction
VNF - Virtual Network Function
WLAN - Wireless Local Area Network

Executive Summary

This deliverable, the first outcome of WP2, includes the initial review of standard control, management and orchestration specifications and systems, and the initial review of the spectrum of learning and optimization tools, and of the emerging techniques in fundamental research on AI models that are relevant to concrete networking problems. This D2.1 deliverable lays the technical foundation of other work packages, in particular WP3 and WP4, as they are in charge of developing the NI-assisted functionalities for 5G problems, in the area of real-time control and network function intelligence (WP3), and in the area of service and resource management and orchestration (WP4).

In addition, D2.1 presents DAEMON's vision for a network intelligence framework with a more systematic and deeper integration of NI, thereby providing means to overcome the limits of current control plane-centric closed-loop approaches. This deliverable provides insights into the eight NI use cases/functionalities and a thorough analysis of their functional and non-functional requirements. Furthermore, it discusses the NI workflows, which are presented as a closed-loop that consists of data management, control, and training, thus, providing traditional network management and orchestration frameworks with automation capabilities enforced by optimized decision-making processes.

D2.1 also presents DAEMON's initial guidelines on the i) selection, ii) configuration, and iii) orchestration of all NI instances deployed in the network. All three aspects are driven by the time constraints in NI functions execution, considering time as one of the most influential factors when making decisions on selection, configuration, and orchestration, of NI functions and algorithms. The specifications of AI for NI that are provided in Section 6 are studied from the perspectives of the network, and the service, thus the specifications are separately presented as network-driven, and service-driven ones. For the network-driven specifications there are trade-offs that an NI native framework shall be able to tackle are discussed in terms of the infrastructure monitoring data, the timely decision and the enforcement of such a decision in the infrastructure. For the service-driven specifications, this document identified three use cases where the specifications of AI for NI depend on the application-level target.

The future work in WP2 is based on an iterative process that will incorporate the feedback provided by WP3/WP4 (algorithms) and WP5 (performance evaluation), so the DAEMON's NI framework and tools keep evolving and are aligned with the NI-assisted functionality designed and developed in WP3 and WP4. In addition, this deliverable D2.1 contains three appendixes, Appendix A presents the functional and non-functional requirements of the NI use cases and verification scenarios. Appendix B presents an analysis on existing frameworks and architectures, and finally Appendix C presents MLOps methodology that combines Machine Learning (ML) with software development operations (DevOps).

1 Introduction

This is the first public deliverable of the DAEMON project's Work Package 2 (WP2) that reports initial requirements analysis and state-of-the-art frameworks and toolsets. The role of this deliverable is i) to capture the progress of identification and definition of requirements, ii) to analyze the state-of-the-art Network Intelligence (NI) solutions, and iii) to provide a gap analysis, which all together set the baseline for directions in which the DAEMON project will evolve.

This deliverable includes the initial review of standard control, management and orchestration specifications and systems, and the initial review of the spectrum of learning and optimization tools and of the emerging techniques in fundamental research on AI models that are relevant to concrete networking problems. In addition, the innovative changes in architectures for B5G network infrastructure are presented, aiming to enable a more systematic and deeper integration of NI in such network architectures, thereby providing means to overcome the limits of current control plane-centric closed-loop approaches. This report provides insights into several NI use cases/functionalities and a thorough analysis of their functional and non-functional requirements. Furthermore, it discusses the NI workflows, which are presented as a closed-loop that consists of data management, control, and training, thus, providing traditional network management and orchestration frameworks with automation capabilities enforced by optimized decision-making processes.

1.1 Objectives, methodology and status of WP2

The D2.1 deliverable addresses the following milestone of the DAEMON project: MS1: *First analysis of requirements and revision of state of the art completed.*

As WP2 is devoted to the design and implementation of an architectural framework for NI-native B5G networks, it pursues the following objectives within the DAEMON project:

- **Objective 1.1:** To enable and drive the coordination and cross-compatibility across NI deployed in different network domains that are operating at different timescales,
- **Objective 1.2:** To enable NI deep into the network infrastructure,
- **Objective 3.1:** To adjust AI techniques to the specific needs of the network environment and operations, and to develop novel AI hybrid approaches,
- **Objective 3.2:** To introduce appropriate cost functions for the networking context in the AI techniques,
- **Objective 3.3:** To develop novel AI techniques that can adapt their requirements to the available network resources.

In recent years, network complexity has increased without precedents. Now, manual configuration of resources and virtual networks coping with diverse network optimization goals is almost impossible to achieve. Therefore, Artificial Intelligence (AI) or Machine Learning (ML) approaches are being proposed to replace or assist network operators in their diverse set of network management tasks. With the help of AI/ML, the network is no longer explicitly programmed by a human operator but can learn from the data it collects and from past experience. Furthermore, the state-of-the-art NI-assisted architectural frameworks usually follow an intrinsically control plane-centric closed-loop approach, which imposes a significant risk of increased latency in data transfer and decision-making processes due to the strongly centralized closed-loop models. Such risk makes the architectural frameworks unsuitable for numerous low-latency use cases promised by B5G architectures. Thus, to mitigate the challenges of insufficiently scalable NI architectures that solely depend on operations of individual NI instances, WP2 strives to build a standard-compliant architecture that will enable a systematic and deep integration of NI in the B5G infrastructure. The DAEMON NI-assisted architectural framework enables the penetration of intelligence into both the user and control planes, thereby creating a multi-time scale hierarchical NI architecture that consists of distributed NI instances for network management, which altogether collaborate to improve their individual learning and decision-making processes. Based on the timescale of their operations, the architecture distributes NI instances into three following levels, i.e., i) NI at Orchestrators in the Core Network (CN), ii) NI at Non-Real-Time Controllers, and iii) NI at Real-time Controllers.

Furthermore, to enable adjustments and improvements in such an architectural framework during the project's lifetime, WP2 defines the extensive list of non-functional and functional requirements that project needs to meet and verify. To this end, WP2 defines the verification procedure that needs to be applied to all identified requirements.

1.2 Relationship to the other deliverables of DAEMON

Since WP2 sets the foundations for the technical work in the project, thereby designing and implementing an architectural framework with an NI-based toolset to support WP3 and WP4, its deliverables will be organized in correspondence with other WPs as well.

The close collaboration between WP2 and other work packages is planned, in particular with WP3 and WP4, as they are in charge of developing the NI-assisted functionalities for B5G problems, in the area of real-time control and network function intelligence (WP3), and in the area of service and resource management and orchestration (WP4). The outcomes and deliverables of these two WPs (i.e., D3.1, D4.1) provide support to WP2 in the form of a qualitative feedback that will enforce and help to adjust the designed NI-native B5G architectural framework and tools. As the deliverable D2.1 sets the baseline for the DAEMON's framework, further updates and a complete design of the first version of the framework and its tools will be reported in D2.2 (M19). Finally, based on a thorough evaluation of the NI functionalities developed within WP3 and WP4, the feasibility of the NI architectural framework and tools designed and implemented in WP2 will be assessed, and the final version of the DAEMON's NI framework will be presented in D2.3 (M30).

1.3 Structure of the document

The main structure of this deliverable can be summarized as follow:

- Section 2 details on the vision of a Network Intelligence Framework,
- Section 3 presents eight NI use cases that tackle various aspects of the Network Intelligence Framework presented in Section 2. All these use cases are mapped to the three following categories: i) Network Planning, ii) Network Diagnosis and insights, and iii) Network Optimization and Control, which are the main B5G AI/ML use cases defined by 5GPPP [1].
- Section 4 defines and analyzes the functional and non-functional requirements of use cases identified and presented in Section 3, whereas the detailed description of these requirements is available in Section 9 Appendix A,
- Section 5 analyzes the Network Intelligence workflows, by providing insights into the existing multi-domain and multi-timescale frameworks and architectures, and by studying the closed-loop AI that consists of different NI aspects, such as data management, control, and training. This section also describes ML workflows, and presents taxonomies of deep learning, followed by the gap analysis that explains where the DAEMON architecture is bringing innovation comparing to the 5G PPP projects when it comes to complete automation of network operations,
- Section 6 provides DAEMON's initial guidelines, thereby separating and studying the specifications of AI for NI into two categories, i.e., network-driven, and service-driven specifications, and
- Section 7 presents the conclusions and the expected future work.

Complementary, this deliverable includes three Appendixes:

- Section 9, Appendix A presents the NI use cases functional and non-functional requirements, as well as the means for verification.
- Section 10, Appendix B presents the analysis of existing frameworks and architectures.
- Section 11, Appendix C presents a generic Machine Learning software development operations workflow.

2 A Vision for a Network Intelligence Framework

Throughout and beyond their fifth generation, mobile networks will undergo an architectural revolution, aimed at supporting the extreme requirements set by future services that will assume performance indicators like virtually infinite capacity or perceived zero latency. Current efforts in standardization reflect this trend and are pushing a number of distinctive novelties into the mobile network design.

The mobile network architecture is being redesigned for end-to-end softwarization and cloudification, completing the decoupling of network functions from the underlying hardware, and granting unprecedented capacities to control system-wide operations. A full range of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) and containerized Cloud-native Network Functions (CNFs) will complement traditional Physical Network Functions (PNFs). In these architectures, a variety of overarching entities are responsible for the orchestration (i.e., service and network functions lifecycles management, including their instantiation, scaling or termination) and control (i.e., the parameter tuning of deployed network functions according to context changes) of VNFs, CNFs and PNFs in different network domains.

At the same time, the atomization of the classical access-core dichotomy is paving the road for network micro-domains that substantially increase the management granularity of physical infrastructures. Distinct controllers and orchestrators are expected to operate in the following micro-domains:

- **Core:** This domain aggregates most of the computing infrastructure and network aggregation points in few centralized physical locations. This infrastructure hosts most of the core functions of the system, gateways to the Internet or Private Networks, and service function that do not require *close-to-the-edge* performance.
- **Transport:** The Transport domain comprises all network links (wireless or wired), switches (virtual, physical, programmable, or not, smart, or not) connecting the Core with each Cloud Unit User Plane (CU-UP) component of eNBs, gNBs or next-generation access points in the radio access network (RAN). In addition, the Transport domain provides distributed computing infrastructure, co-located with (smart) switches, for in-backhaul processing for VNFs (such as firewalls or deep packet inspection) and service providers functions.
- **Edge:** The Edge comprises of PNFs and/or computing infrastructure hosting VNFs dedicated to distributed units (DUs) and CUs for each radio access point in the system; it also encompasses the X-haul or midhaul networks connecting DUs and CUs. It supports edge computing applications for service providers with low-latency and high-bandwidth requirements.
- **Far Edge:** The Far Edge comprises the actual physical radio units (RUs), the fronthaul network connecting DUs and RUs, and the wireless medium connecting RUs and actual users.

The radical architectural transformations outlined above summarize the current state-of-the-art in standardization initiatives. Jointly, they will enable a very fine engineering of network configurations on the fly, so that the network functions and their allocated resources can be adapted to traffic demand dynamics and meet strict, heterogeneous Quality of Services (QoS) specifications. As such, these architectural changes will support network-on-demand schemes, multi-tenancy and emerging compelling paradigms for strong service differentiation such as network slicing that will characterize Beyond 5G (B5G) multi-service settings.

Fundamental to the optimal operation of the softwarized, cloudified and atomized network infrastructure will be the Network Intelligence (NI) responsible for managing the composite mosaic of network functions and associated resources in presence of a surging mass of services, tenants and slices. Given the variety of network management tasks and the many functions they involve, each orchestrator or controller shall run multiple NI instances, each implemented as a pipeline of supple yet effective algorithms that swiftly detect or anticipate new requests or fluctuations in the network activities, and then react to those by instantiating, relocating, or re-configuring network functions in a fully automated manner. By driving these decisions, NI is expected to meet a number of **key targets** that include:

- (i) Ensuring all traffic demands are accommodated in a timely fashion and in full conformity to QoS requirements;
- (ii) Maximizing infrastructure and resource reuse across multiple tenants or slices to reduce operating expenses;
- (iii) Taking full advantage of the novel flexibility to compensate for the reduced performance of equipment where software functions are parted from vendor hardware; and,
- (iv) Eliminating human intervention, hence fulfilling the vision of zero-touch network and service management in mobile systems.

These aspects are all highly critical, to the point that *the success and viability of B5G systems will largely depend on the quality and appropriate integration of NI solutions in the network infrastructure.*

Present trends in NI for next-generation network orchestration promoted by major standardization bodies pivot on the notion of **closed-loop Artificial Intelligence (AI)**. According to this paradigm, the NI instances deployed at centralized orchestrators and controllers work in closed control loops: abiding by the learning principles of modern AI, they record the context of management decisions, collect observations about the quality of such decisions via continuing monitoring, and then use the feedback to improve future choices. A closed-loop model lets NI apprehend what is important for an operator in a certain situation and learn over time to automate optimal decision making towards the expected targets (i)-(iv) listed before. The current, prevailing vision for closed-loop NI contemplates instances located at centralized orchestrators or controllers in the control plane that interact with VNFs deployed in the data plane. This model requires that network state information be gathered from the different VNFs and transported to a central entity, where they are processed by the pertinent AI algorithms; decisions must then travel back across the network before they can be enacted.

While present standardization efforts and the associated drafts stop at this point, we recognize that the architectural changes currently proposed, still yield the following two major limitations.

- First, there is a concrete risk that the latency in data transfer and decision communication ensuing from a strongly centralized closed-loop model hinders the effectiveness of NI, and limit its application in a number of critical network management scenarios. To be effective, many network functionalities must operate at timescales that are not compatible with the lengthy procedures of data gathering at VNFs, data processing in the control plane, and final restitution of actions to be implemented in the data plane. In these cases, the feedback loop between the control and data planes does not allow the NI to monitor the system in a continued manner, and to immediately intervene when required; instead, operators must just hope that the policies, VNFs and resources already in place are sufficient to cope with sudden fluctuations in traffic – or otherwise incur into service disruption and violations of the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) in place with tenants.
- Second, the current architectural models do not foresee any interaction among NI instances, which are left to operate in a vacuum, in spite of the fact the actions they take often yield reciprocal impact. As a simple but representative example, short-timescale network controllers operate on local resources allocated by orchestrators in charge of similar decisions at a wider scope and on longer timescales. Therefore, for NI to operate at its best, it is critical that NI instances can cooperate to ensure end-to-end synchronization, convergence and global optimality of the zero-touch network management process.

To overcome the limits of control plane-centric closed-loop approaches, we push the B5G architectural concept several steps beyond the current standardization trends, and posit a new mobile network architecture that enables a more systematic integration of NI in the B5G infrastructure, while staying fully aligned with emerging designs in standardization. The concept of the novel NI-native architecture we propose is illustrated in Figure 2-1, and its main novelties are presented next.

Figure 2-1. Concept of the DAEMON NI-native architecture.

The three levels of NI operation timescales are set apart by shaded areas that encompass the network entities belonging to each level; DAEMON brings pervasive intelligence into the real-time control domain of the network infrastructure, all the way within VNFs. The additional Beyond Edge micro-domain introduced by DAEMON and its associated entities are highlighted by the dashed line. The novel NI Orchestration layer introduces feedback loops across NI instances deployed throughout the network, including the new ones implemented at VNF level.

As a first provision, the DAEMON NI-native architecture introduces intelligence directly into the user plane, creating a hierarchy of NI instances for network management that removes the restrictions of closed-loop models. As illustrated in Figure 2-1, the project concept identifies three levels of NI, depending on their operation timescale.

- **NI at Orchestrators:** In Core Network (CN) deployments, and for service-related applications running in Private Network (PN) deployments, End-to-End Orchestrators operate at a global network level, whereas Edge/Fog Orchestrators focus on broad portions of the mobile edge. The NI integrated in these entities manage functions and resources at a broad network scope, taking decisions that affect large sets of Distributed Units (DUs) and Remote Units (RUs) at once. At this layer, the data traffic is aggregated over a vast population of User Equipment (UE) and its dynamics vary relatively slowly. Reconfiguration is performed at *timescales of minutes to hours*, and NI must take decisions that endure during large time windows by profiting from a better resource pooling available at more centralized locations.
- **NI at Non-Real-Time Controllers:** Shifting network functionalities closer to the user and substantially improving the versatility of Radio Access Networks are long-standing objectives in the evolution of mobile networks, which will finally become a reality with next-generation mobile systems. Here, Non-Real-Time RAN Controllers are responsible for less time-critical functionalities at a limited number of sites. Their associated NI operates at a local scope and takes decisions at *timescales in the order of tens of seconds*.
- **NI at Near-Real-Time Controllers:** Ambitious 5G targets like unperceivable latency or pseudo-infinite bandwidth require data analysis and decision-making at *timescales of milliseconds or lower*. Standardization activities within O-RAN [19] or FOG-05 [20] expect that NI deployed within Near-Real-Time RAN Controllers will ensure fast-timescale functionalities such as radio scheduling. We go beyond the vision of current standardization bodies, and pushes NI within VNFs in the Far Edge, Edge, Transport and Core micro-domains, as well as in a novel Beyond Edge micro-domain. In these cases, NI is implemented much closer or within in the user plane: instead of injecting direct policies into “dumb” VNFs, Controllers trigger highly specialized and lightweight NI algorithms that operate within each VNF, enabling, network functionalities to operate close to the line rate. As part of its approach, DAEMON introduces an original Beyond Edge micro-domain: in this micro-domain, dedicated Controllers run NI that handles Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), which effectively turn a traditionally passive environment where transceivers react to into a programmable environment that actively assist in the task of delivering data over the air.

The architectural changes above forward a much deeper integration of intelligence in 5G systems and create a considerably wider ecosystem of NI instances that populate the network infrastructure both in the control and data planes. The proposed changes allow breaking the centralized closed loop model, by enabling hybrid models where user-plane components make their own decisions for time critical operations, hence effectively addressing the first limitation identified above.

While they allow for very fast and localized decision-making, the range of NI instances foreseen by the model need to interact seamlessly to perform at their best, and exchange data and information so as to mutually improve both their learning and decision-making processes. Therefore, it is paramount that the network architecture fully supports the complex, pervasive and distributed NI environment envisioned by the project by enabling the reporting of NI-assisted provisions and of the associated contextual information across the NI hierarchy.

In order to address this challenge, and as an inherent part of its proposed NI-native architecture, DAEMON sets out a structured approach to system-wide NI coordination and management by introducing an original NI Orchestration layer. The NI Orchestration layer is responsible for supervising intelligence in the network architecture as a whole, ensuring the ideal functioning of each closed-loop NI instance, and overseeing interactions across closed loops that run NI at different timescales. The NI Orchestration layer is thus uniquely devoted to the following NI management tasks.

- Selecting the best NI algorithm within each NI instance from a predefined range of options. The variants of NI algorithms will be designed by employing different modelling strategies and adaptive learning techniques. Decisions on the most appropriate option will be based on contextual information (e.g., the reliability level of the traffic demand predictions), available system resources (e.g., the computational capacity that can be dedicated to the NI instance), performance requirements (e.g., the target precision of the algorithm), and amount of data to be processed (e.g.,

the lookback for a forecasting algorithm), concurrently across timescale levels. This flexibility will be beneficial for many Network Intelligence-assisted functions developed by Daemon. For instance, deploying NI at the edge for functions such as radio scheduling have stringent timing requirements (e.g., in the order of millisecond) which must be carefully considered when deploying them. In these cases, tailoring the NI model or internal parameters according to the available computing capacity is paramount to optimal operation.

- Coordinating all NI instances in the system to ensure gracious operation of all live mechanisms operating at different timescales and in different micro-domains. To this end, the NI Orchestrator will support the exchange of information via dedicated interfaces with the NI instances, and centrally solve trade-offs that may emerge from conflicting objectives in the control and data planes, including those associated to establishing policies (at short timescales) versus enforcing such policies (at faster timescales). For instance, this is what happens in the case of radio resource orchestration for bandwidth allocation (policy) versus radio scheduling within such bandwidth (enforcement), but it is in fact the case for many of the NI-assisted functionalities addressed by the project. Hence, the coordination envisioned by DAEMON goes beyond federated learning aspects and deals with the practical application of NI in multi-timescale environments where the network metric shall guide the zero-touch management process.

By implementing the tasks above, the NI Orchestration layer establishes and control a rich and organized set of feedback links between the NI at orchestrators, controllers, and VNFs, as highlighted in Figure 2-1. This allows the NI Orchestrator to help NI algorithms that run in the data plane to overcome the intrinsic limitations of their local view and close in on the optimal point of operation without sacrificing their reactivity. Similarly, the NI Orchestrator supports the NI algorithms in traditional End-to-End Orchestrators by feeding them with fresh local state and decisions at VNFs, so that they ensure system-wide stability without human intervention. Ultimately, these provisions address the second limitations indicated before.

3 Network Intelligence Use Cases

The project DAEMON focuses in a series of NI use cases:

- Reconfigurable Intelligent surfaces control (RISC);
- Multi-timescale Edge resource management (MTERM);
- In-backhaul support for service management (IBSSI);
- Compute-aware radio scheduling (CAWRS);
- Energy-aware VNF control and orchestration (EAWVNF);
- Self-learning MANO (SLMANO);
- Capacity forecasting (CFORE); and
- Automated anomaly response (AARES).

Table 3-1 maps each of these use cases with the three main 5G AI/ML use cases by 5GPPP [1] (i.e., Network planning, Network diagnosis and insights, and Network optimization and control). In the same table, we also summarize each NI use case in terms of the NI level, NI targeting controller, and NI operating micro-domain(s).

Table 3-1. Mapping of NI use-cases.

NI Use case	Acronym	NI level	NI targeting controller	NI operating micro-domain(s)	5GPPP B5G AI/ML use case
Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces control	RISC	Real-time NI	RIS controller	Beyond Edge, Far Edge	Network optimization and control
Multi-timescale Edge resource management	MTERM	Non-Real-time NI	Non-RT RAN controller	Edge	Network optimization and control
		Orchestrator NI	Edge/Fog orchestrator	Edge	Network planning
In-backhaul support for service intelligence	IBSSI	Non-Real-time NI	Non-RT RAN controller	Edge, Transport	Network optimization and control
Compute-aware radio scheduling	CAWRS	Real-time NI	RT RAN controller	Far Edge	Network optimization and control
Energy-aware VNF control & orchestration	EAWVNF	Orchestrator NI	Edge/Fog Orchestrator	Core	Network optimization and control
Self-learning MANO	SLMANO	Orchestrator NI	E2E orchestrator	Edge, Core, Transport	Network planning
Capacity forecasting	CFORE	Orchestrator NI	Edge/Fog Orchestrator	Transport	Network diagnosis and insights
Automated anomaly response	AARES	Non-Real-time NI	Non-RT RAN controller	Edge	Network diagnosis and insights

In the remaining of this section we summarize each of DAEMON's NI use cases, which can be associated with the following four critical challenges:

- **Fast network dynamics:** One challenge to applying NI is due to the fast-varying dynamics mainly caused by the air-interface conditions, and it especially will be encountered for RISC and CAWRS use-cases. This challenge will not only pose stringent requirements on the available decision-making time but also trigger the tradeoff consideration for NI between performance and efficiency.
- **Multi-time scales alignment:** Applying NI across multiple time scales incurs this challenge, and it will need further event synchronization, decision-making alignment, or even conflict resolution schemes. Particularly, this challenge is confronted by MTERM and CFORE use-cases since they aim to make alignment across different domains and different time scales, respectively.
- **Environmental awareness:** A further challenge shall be considered when integrating NI into network systems that possess specific environmental considerations. Specifically, both IBSSI and CAWRS use-cases are targeting resource-limited scenarios and thus the NI decision-making process shall be

revisited and even be split, after considering the computing resource consumption. Also, the EAWVNF use-case will take the energy footprint of VNF deployment options and the context of location into account when placing network functions.

- **Automation and Autonomous:** This challenge aims to apply the NI with few or even minimum human intervention to make the network systems more proactive than before. Therefore, it will need the NI to self-learn the relationships between high-level intent and low-level arguments based on the concerned use-case, specifically SLMANO, CFOR, and AARES. By doing so, the NI is expected to delay with frequently changing business KPI (SLMANO use-case), live streaming (CFOR use-case), and unexpected anomalies (AARES use-case).

3.1 Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces control

Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) are a very promising technology to enhance radio access performance towards the ambitious targets of B5G [2], [3]. RIS are continuous meta-surfaces that can be modelled as a grid of discrete unit cells, which can alter their electromagnetic response, such as phase, amplitude, polarization, and frequency in a controllable manner. For instance, RIS can be tuned so that signals bouncing off a meta-surface are combined constructively to increase signal quality at the intended receiver, i.e., performing passive beamforming, or destructively to avoid leaking signals to undesired receivers.

In this way, RIS have the potential to turn the stochastic and passive nature of the wireless environment into a programmable channel that plays an active role in how signals propagate. RIS have very low hardware footprint, consisting of a few layers of planar structures built using lithography or nano-printing methods, and are particularly attractive for seamless integration into walls, ceilings, object cases, or building glasses.

A major challenge with the deployment of RIS is their dynamic configuration. In order to be fully effective, RIS need to be configured at very fast time scales of tens of milliseconds or less, and in coordination with traditional RAN tasks such as power control or radio scheduling, as highlighted in Table 3-1. Additional challenges are the support of multiple (mobile) users concurrently and the estimation of the channel so as to optimize the passive RIS response (note that RIS have no active components and therefore are unable to decode feedback).

To date, however, RIS have been tested in isolated environments for specific applications (e.g., secure communications, non-orthogonal multiple access, or over-the-air-computation) without any consideration for coordination with other network functions [2], [3]. To this end, DAEMON will design a first-of-its-kind RIS controller, with a dedicated NI designed to manage the extremely distributed RIS environment in cooperation with the NI instances driving the other radio access network functionalities, demonstrating efficient RIS control at scale.

3.2 Multi-timescale edge resource management

As a part of an intrinsically heterogeneous 5G ecosystem (i.e., 5G radio access, 5G core, distributed service deployments, etc.), the edge computing paradigm has emerged as a promising solution to improve network performance by reducing computational delay, transmission delay, and bandwidth consumption. To this end, edge computing brings computing resources at the network edge, i.e., closer to the end users/devices where data is produced/consumed [4], [5], thereby exposing the resources to host and deploy numerous service applications that can be instantiated, re-configured, and terminated in a dynamic way.

Although provisioning of virtualized services on the distributed network edge contributes to decreasing the latency in communication and computation, i) resource constraints at the network edge, ii) uneven distribution of resources, and iii) mobility of users, still impose significant challenge for optimization of management and orchestration techniques, and to cope with such challenges these techniques need to pursue a real-time monitoring and automated configuration of distributed service deployments. Thus, a proper management and orchestration of these distributed services needs to be achieved. With the help of AI, management and orchestration solutions can support an automated service re-configuration to meet service KPIs that are specified in service requirements without any manual intervention. As shown in Table 3-1, multi-timescale edge resource management tackles both the network optimization and control, and network planning, by adopting the Non-Real-time NI and Orchestrator NI, which are performed by the Non-RT RAN controller, and Edge/Fog orchestrator, respectively. The network intelligence in the form of AI-based NI instances needs to be distributed to different tiers in the management and orchestration architecture to treat different service dynamics in coarse or fine granular timescale. For instance, the changes in network connectivity (i.e., network links and nodes) and resource availability should be monitored in a finer timescale than energy, which can be aggregated and monitored on the system level. Furthermore, the decisions made by NI instances distributed across

the edge networks might be out of sync with the NI instances running in a centralized cloud orchestrator, and hence, there is a need to assign the level of priority to decision-making entities in different tiers, and to have a control loop that will track the effect of these decisions on the service KPIs. Thus, the main objectives of the multi-timescale edge resource management are:

- i) to distribute NI across the edge infrastructure in the form of NI instances, and to dynamically adapt these NI instances to constrained environments and changing conditions,
- ii) to coordinate distributed orchestrators and controllers that perform their operations at different timescales, and
- iii) to enable zero-touch self-learning NI across orchestrators and controllers.

Therefore, the integration of management and orchestration frameworks with AI techniques will assist resource management and orchestration operations on decision making, providing them with reasoning capabilities to adapt to changing conditions dynamically, thereby enabling true automation.

3.3 In-backhaul support for service intelligence

The quest for ultra-low latency support for enhanced network services has brought the solution space of such resource consuming application towards the inclusion of computing power very close to the user (i.e., the so-called edge computing). However, sometimes the inclusion of such computing capacity at the edge is not possible due to the intrinsic limitation of the available resources (which may need, for instance, GPU accelerators). In DAEMON, we will study the applicability of this concept in an even more extreme configuration, allowing backhaul network function to process (either partially or entirely) the traffic related to a given service to make the tasks easier to the application network functions. Possible examples of this are the pre-processing of data for e.g., a machine learning task to be realized in the control plane [6], [7], [8], or implementing and running (part of) the actual inference processes directly in the network switches [9]. That is, moving the intelligence and the computing power closer to the user plane opens up new opportunities enabled by the enhanced capabilities of the network and adds new capabilities to the supporting architecture as the ones explained in this document. Mostly, they can be categorized into two main areas: the exposure of these capabilities into the orchestration and control framework, at any level, and their subsequent control. This has dependencies on how the different algorithms may interact according to the availability of the infrastructure, but they will also need to take decisions on how much resources shall be assigned to the specific network functions, at different time scales.

3.4 Compute-aware radio scheduling

While the kind of resources that have traditionally been considered for network function (including RAN ones) design included aspects such as spectrum, bandwidth or timeslots, there has been very little focus on the key resource that is available in a cloud environment such as the one targeted by next generation mobile networks: the computing ones. That is, current approaches for the virtualization of access network functions usually overprovision them with computing resources and memory. However, this approach can fall short in the near future as i) it might turn out to be extremely inefficient, according to [10] as low as 20% of the allocated resources are actually used in practice, and even with very static resource assignments, computing capabilities may fade away unexpectedly, as pointed out by [11].

Thus, this requires a re-design of VNF internals to take into account the possible fading in computing resources, with the goal of improving performance and resilience to resource shortages. This entails not only new VNFs but also the interfaces to accurately assign the computing resources to the VNFs, which will, in turn, use information about the past usage [12] of the network function to estimate the future consumption. As radio network functions are the most resource greedy ones, these are the ones that will benefit the most from this approach.

Thus, as shown in Table 3-1, the overall framework shall be capable of providing such information to the orchestration framework and eventually reconfigure them to provide the best performance (as targeted by DAEMON).

3.5 Energy-aware VNF control & orchestration

Energy consumption, and hence, electricity expenditure, is costly for mobile network operators even today. Part of the challenges posed by 5G implies a transition to a fully virtualized infrastructure, which will have a strong impact on energy expenditure [13], raising the power demands. Unfortunately, an important part of energy production is still based on fossil fuels. The use of non-renewable energy is one of the critical factors driving higher emissions of greenhouse gas, which contribute to global warming. Indeed, there are many governments that, following the sustainable development goals recommendations have initiated programs to reduce the consumption of non-renewable energies [14].

In addition to the current problem, the softwarization of networks is expected to increase further the energy consumption, so new approaches should be explored to priorities sustainability.

The sustainability of B5G networks will heavily depend on the capability of defining energy-aware orchestration of virtual network functions, and the enforcement of control frameworks to account for energy consumption figures when making resource management decisions. This energy-aware Orchestration NI level depicted in Table 3-1 shall provide tools for energy profiling in network environments, including software components implementing virtual network functions [15]. Also, it shall implement a coordinated intelligence that optimally deploys VNFs according to their energy footprints in different devices, while also duly considering the resources needed to support VNFs compute necessities with the capabilities of the different classes of network data centers where these software functions may be placed.

On the other hand, an energy-aware orchestration framework opens the possibility of optimizing implementations variants or versions of VNFs based on their power consumption and QoS. So that, this framework could take a decision making a trade-off between current available resources and the QoS demanded. Moreover, this framework will support the VNF placement considering energy concerns.

3.6 Self-learning MANO

MANO decides, when a desired service is requested, where the associated VNFs need to be fired up and how the flows between these VNFs need to be routed. Additionally, it tracks how many compute, storage and transport resources need to be allocated to these VNFs and flows. Automating this process relies on being able to monitor the consumption of these compute, storage and transport resources (i.e., observations) and the quality of experience (KPIs) of the service supported by the VNFs. Based on these observations and by comparing the KPIs with the predefined targets (i.e., intents), the MANO need to self-learn how to gradually update its policy, which produces actions to be taken for the sets of VNFs and flows associated to existing and new services, so as to maximize efficiency, while respecting all constraints. NI will enable self-learning, by determining the aforementioned optimal policy: specifically, the NI will learn a reward associated to each action given the observations and try to gradually increase that reward in alignment with constraints and requirements [1].

3.7 Capacity forecasting

Optimizing the utilization of resources across network micro-domains is vital to the reliable operation of B5G systems characterized by a very high degree of multi-tenancy, where strong service guarantees force isolating resources to slices. Previous measurement-driven studies show that, already under today's traffic demands, ensuring resource isolation among slices risks to yield unbearable costs for operators, as granting resources to slices under mildly efficient allocation strategies may require a six-fold increase of available capacity [16].

In this scenario, accurately anticipating the capacity needed to meet the future demand of slices is paramount to satisfying the complex service requirements that B5G systems will face. Unfortunately, current traffic predictors aim at forecasting traffic demands, and not the capacity needed to serve them, incurring in very frequent underestimation errors that lead to SLA violations and undermine the reliability of the network [17]. To address this problem, capacity forecasting models have been recently proposed that anticipate the optimal amount of resources to be allocated to individual slices at different network entities and at each reconfiguration opportunity. Specifically, breakthroughs were obtained using suitably tailored Deep Learning models [18], [19].

DAEMON will build on such results to improve the current state of the art in a number of directions, including by: (i) refining dedicated loss functions that are specifically designed so as to account for the actual technological limits and economic costs involved in the network operation; (ii) identifying solutions to the anticipatory allocation of capacity when the performance metrics are not directly observable by the operator and/or linked in entangled ways with the network functions (e.g., Quality of Experience of end users); and, (iii) supporting operation over streaming data. Experiments with real-world mobile data traffic demands of major services will allow training and evaluating the proposed solution in credible slicing conditions.

The notion of capacity above is deliberately general, as the problem of capacity forecasting arises across network micro-domains, where it applies to computing, transport, or radio resources depending on the target entity, and concerns timescales ranging from seconds to hours minutes. Within the scope of DAEMON, we will mainly target capacity forecasting for the orchestration of transport resources, with operation timescales of minutes, as highlighted in Table 3-1.

3.8 Automated anomaly response

Our activities in DAEMON relate to network resilience [20], i.e., the property of the network to sustain its normal operation and desired performance, when facing a number of hard-to-predict situations. Resilience will be investigated by DAEMON in the context of global operations in the cellular domain. One of the first aspects we will consider is that of anomaly detection, which has long been a question of great interest in a wide range of domains including network systems [21], [22]. The project will progress beyond the current efforts, by studying machine learning and deep learning tools to implement anomaly detection functionalities that (i) include root cause analysis and response measures, (ii) are trained with very large-scale measurement data, and (iii) will be prototyped in near-production systems; all these are original contributions with respect to the current state of the art. DAEMON will then take a second, different perspective to resilience, addressing the reliability of the machine learning and deep learning models we use for the design of the network intelligence modules. The attribution of artificial intelligence (AI) and other machine learning models with resilience in the specific networking context requires novel technologies that address fundamental questions such as (i) whether these modules are operating based on valid, non-poisoned, data [23], and (ii) if the NI algorithms are producing proper, un-biased outputs, with explainable behavior [24], [25], [26]. Finally, the project will consider a third, less direct viewpoint to resilience, by studying NI algorithms that enable rapid, anticipatory resource allocations capable of serving the future demand, including in anomalous situations. By jointly addressing multiple facets of network resiliency, we aim to make key contributions in a domain that is critical for gaining the trust of vendors and operators towards zero-touch network technologies.

Specifically, proactive monitoring and root cause detection of potential anomalies in mobile systems via performance metrics is an important goal of our project. We will use machine learning and deep learning tools (e.g., Variational Auto-Encoders, Generative Adversarial Networks) to run anomaly detection. Our goal is to build tailored anomaly detection solutions for the operators and maintainers of different systems, bridging the path from research to real-world impact in operational systems. For example, we propose to tackle several major deficiencies that we have identified within the roaming ecosystem, in order to enable a true global service. Support for things operating in a global manner has become critical for IoT verticals, from connected cars to logistic and wearables, and explains the commercial success of M2M platforms. All IoT device manufacturers need a global connectivity solution, and this requirement is bound to become urgent with the rapid acceleration of IoT deployments. IoT verticals rely on providers who can ensure reliable data connectivity across the globe, such as M2M platforms that depend on the cellular ecosystem. International mobile roaming is thus an essential service for IoT verticals. Depending on the use case (e.g., automotive, logistic tracking, smart meters), roaming may be required occasionally or persistently/permanently. Different IoT verticals come with potentially different requirements: while logistics services, for instance, may prioritize international roaming to track assets in flux, payment services depend on signal reliability, where terminals always connect, and select an alternative network in the event the first one fails. In the same time, there are well-known weaknesses that affect the current cellular ecosystem (e.g., roaming signaling equipment unsecured in the public Internet [1], advanced IPX network protocol vulnerabilities [2]) and translate into attacks on end-user privacy or on critical IoT platforms. While learning from vulnerabilities of older-generation cellular systems, we aim to build intelligent tools (using deep learning cutting-edge techniques) that can ensure the health of the roaming ecosystem, allowing us to tackle anomalies (malicious or unintended) that might occur.

4 Network Intelligence Functional Requirements

The DAEMON project proposes to address a set of eight innovative B5G network functionalities (see Table 4-1). These functionalities pose distinct but also similar requirements (data management and orchestration, monitoring, etc.) Also, there are dependencies among them, and a great number of stakeholders would be involved, making all these requirements specification a challenge.

We have followed the recommendation addressed in ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018¹ to create a methodology to elicit and specify the DAEMON's requirements. It suggests a split between what the framework shall do (**functional requirements**), and criteria that the framework shall meet or attributes that are required (**non-functional requirements**). This facilitates the verification of the functions described in the functional requirements, as well as constraints the framework architecture decisions with the non-functional requirements. For instance, the [FR-EAWVNF-001.00](#) requirement is a functional requirement that specifies that *DAEMON shall measure the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of CPU usage*. On the other hand, the [NFR-CAWRS-001](#) requirement is a non-functional requirement that imposes to *NI control solutions for vRAN to have reaction times below 100ms*.

The main functional and non-functional requirements are described in section 4.2. A complete description of them can be found in Appendix A. Aware of the importance of verifiable requirements, we have described in section 4.3 the verification procedure that should be performed per specified requirement.

4.1 Methodology

As we commented previously, the requirements have been clustered by the NI-assisted functionalities addressed by the project. These functionalities are divided into tasks at DAEMON, with corresponding responsible partners. Therefore, each functionality has been devoted to a leading partner in charge to drive the elicitation and specification of concrete NI-assisted functional and non-functional requirements (see Table 4-1). Another two partners experts in some functionalities were selected to review the requirements proposed by the partner in charge. The common and variable requirements were specified hierarchically, putting those requirements shared by many functionalities in the higher tree levels.

To promote a practical specification, the elicitation was partially done in the biweekly meetings during the first three months, being the partner leader of each functionality, the responsibility for specifying the corresponding requirements. The requirements specification was done iteratively and incrementally—partners included the feedback from reviewers and results from the elicitation in successive iterations.

Finally, one partner was assigned to manage a shared document with the complete requirements to keep track of changes and format editing. Functional requirements.

Table 4-1. Identifiers, partners in charge, reviewers, and project tasks of NI-assisted functionalities.

Id	Functionality	In charge	Related Task	Reviewers
RISC	Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces control	NEC	T3.3	IMDEA, UC3M
MTERM	Multi-timescale Edge resource management	IMEC	T3.2	NBL, UMA
IBSSI	In-backhaul support for service intelligence	UC3M	T3.4	IMDEA, TID
CAWRS	Compute-aware radio scheduling	UC3M	T3.1	IMEC, NEC
EAWVNF	Energy-aware VNF placement	UMA	T4.1	NBL
SLMANO	Self-learning MANO	NBL	T4.4	IMEC, UMA
CFORE	Capacity forecasting	IMDEA	T4.2	TID
AARES	Automated anomaly response	TID	T4.3	NEC

The norm ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018 recommends having the following attributes per requirement: unique identifier, version number, priority, risk, rationale and owner. We have adapted these attributes to DAEMON, including an extra attribute – parents - that track the requirement or requirements from which it inherits. Here are the adaptations to DAEMON:

¹ <https://standards.ieee.org/standard/29148-2018.html>

- **Unique identifier:** It shall never change or be reused. It is composed by a [TAG] denoting the type of requirement (functional [FR] or non-functional [NFR]), followed by [OTHER] tag for one of the eight functionalities (Table 4-1), and 3 digits followed by zero, one or two consecutives [dot digit digit]. For example: FR-RISC-000, NFR-CAWRS-013.02, or FR-DOCU-000.01.02. This nesting makes it easier to group requirements.
- **Version number:** to track requirements changes. In DAEMON, it is composed of the number of changes that the requirement undergoes, using 3 digits (e.g., 001, 013, 041), followed by the month of the last change (e.g., 001M3, 013M6 or 042M13).
- **Priority:** [High, Medium, Low]. Based on the stakeholder that needs the requirement.
- **Risk:** Range from 1 (low risk) to 5 (high risk).
- **Risk Description:** Risk value motivation, addressing feasibility/attainability of a certain technology, or excessive cost or problem foreseen for a testing environment. A link to the proposal risk can be done.
- **Rationale:** Describes the reason for what the requirement is needed. If it is the case, it should point out a relationship with the project KPIs. We have included a row with the KPI per the requirement to make KPIs tracking easier, which may help identify the requirement relationships.
- **Owner:** The entity oversees maintaining a concrete requirement, which has the right to approve, change and report its status.
- **Parents:** Requirement or requirements from which it inherits. We have used internal hyperlinks to enhance the readability.

4.2 Main requirements and analysis

Please note that we have done a very detailed description of DAEMON requirements. Indeed, seventy-six requirements have been specified during the first four months of DAEMON (see Section 9, Appendix A). The following tree (Figure 4-1) shows the top requirement per NI-assisted functionality cluster.

In addition, partners applied a top-down inheritance-based specification, creating trees of requirements.

- **RIS** cluster specifies a set of requirements that enable high-performing operation of the RIS. However, a series of requirements need to be satisfied to exploit RIS technologies to effectively increase the capacity of wireless access networks, reduce their energy footprint, or foster novel applications: (i) tight coordination between RIS controller, RAN controller and system orchestration, (ii) real-time control to adapt seamlessly to quick channel dynamics, and (iii) multi-user support, among others.
- **MTERM** cluster specifies the requirements to enable a multi-timescale resource management at the network edge. Most of the requirements cope with the distributed, heterogeneous and resource-constrained nature of the edge environments. Moreover, some of the requirements include the life cycle management not only of VNFs but also of NI instances, enabling training, monitoring of their performance and possible reconfiguration. This set of requirements will allow to treat different service dynamics in coarse/fine granular timescale in an automated way.
- **IBSSI** cluster sets some heterogeneous requirements. Some of them are grounded to the fundamental of the family of algorithm, so that the solutions we design can learn directly from the network data and providing this functionality to third parties. Others are related to the scalability that such features have to provide, that hence pose some requirements on the way they interact on the specific network functions, as also specified by the CAWRS cluster.
- **CAWRS** cluster is dealing with the specific constraints related to basically two main factors: the tight latency requirements that Radio Access Network Functions usually have and the integration of such functionality in a prototype implementation. The first aspect is also common to other clusters such as the IBSSI, as it deals with data plane function that shall run at wire speed. The second one is common to many of the cluster, for which DAEMON will provide a showcase of the performance.
- **EAWVNF** cluster specifies the requirements related to energy footprint monitorization, mainly for MANO. Several requirements have been identified related to the energy footprint comparison between different VNFs. For instance, it has been identified the CPU usage and communication traffic as the main factor that affects the energy footprint. Migration can be used to mitigate planned and unplanned VNFs outages. This migration has an energy footprint that has to be considered by DAEMON decision making mechanism for VNFs placement.
- **SLMANO** cluster specifies the requirements to automate the management and orchestration (placement, routing and scaling) of network slices. The required closed need to be designed such that the overall system is stable, i.e., small perturbations do not destabilize it. Moreover, the targets to optimize need to be metrics, referred to as "intents", that the applications running over the network slices need to be able to easily interpret.

Figure 4-1. NI use cases functional requirements.

- **CFORE** cluster specifies the requirements for forecasting models suited for supporting decisions about the amount of capacity (e.g., spectrum, transport bandwidth, computational resources) to be allocated to different network slices to serve the demand generated by their associated services. The requirements concern the capability of the predictors to operate at different timescales in diverse micro-domains and by accounting for real-world operational limits and costs of the network entities. It is strongly recommended that the predictors can produce information about the level of reliability of their output and can automatically adapt to objectives that may not be fully specified or observable. This cluster serves as an enabler to the MTERM and SLMANO requirements, which can benefit from anticipatory NI solutions empowered by the predictions of CFCORE. In addition, AARES can also take advantage of models that satisfy the CFCORE requirements, in case of a proactive anomaly detection and response.
- **AARES** cluster specifies the requirements to automatically detect, analyze, and act against anomalous behaviors in the different systems that DAEMON targets. The requirements concern the availability of monitoring data of the system in question, which are vital for building anomaly

detection solutions. These solutions should leverage historical data from the systems they monitor and operate at different timescales, depending on the operational needs of the team maintaining and managing the system. It is of paramount importance that the output of the anomaly detection mechanism is meaningful to the operation teams, while keeping the cost of operating within the specified budget. Moreover, DAEMON requires high performance of AI-driven anomaly detection approaches, which should ensure that the amount of false positives is minimal, and precision is high.

Also, the following non-functional requirements have been identified related to DAEMON:

- Capacity:
 - RIS should aid to increase wireless capacity (bits/m2) by 100% (NFR-RIS-000).
 - RIS units shall support more than one user concurrently (NFR-RIS-002).
- Timescale:
 - Capacity forecast shall operate at very different timescales (FR-AARES-001).
 - RIS controller shall reconfigure surfaces with a timescale below 1ms (NFR-RIS-001).
 - NI vRAN orchestration solutions shall have fast reaction times (below 10s) (NFR-CAWRS-000).
 - NI control solutions for vRAN shall have reaction times below 100ms (NFR-CAWRS-001).
- Performance:
 - NI solutions for vRAN shall achieve a bounded wireless performance wrt the optimal (NFR-CAWRS-002).
- Energy:
 - We will test if the energy-aware framework can scale up or scale down under varying conditions of users, heterogenous set of devices and network infrastructure FR-EAWVFN-001. The main objective of this testing is to determine when the DAEMON framework starts to degrade at a maximum load.
 - The framework shall save 50% of the energy cost, thanks to applying NI solutions to find out the energy-aware optimal placement of VNFs (NFR-EAWVNF-002).
 - The cost in terms of energy footprint of the NI solution for VNFs placing shall be less than the global energy saving (NFR-EAWVNF-003).

Figure 4-2 shows the percentage of requirements that address a specific KPI. It can be observed that all of them are addressed by some requirements. Most of the requirements are focused on saving computational resources at the edge K2 (28%), increasing reliability K5 (16%), improving vertical services response time K8 (15%), and VNF energy consumption reduction K1 (14%).

Figure 4-2. Percentage of requirements that address each KPI.

The exploration of innovative B5G network functionalities has risks. Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-4 show the risks percentage distribution in DAEMON. These risks are higher in the Energy-aware VNF placement than others, mainly due to the hardware and software variability.

Figure 4-3. Risk level percentages.

Figure 4-4. Risk level percentages per cluster.

4.3 Verification

Verification is the process of evaluating a system or component to determine whether the products of a given development phase satisfy the conditions imposed at the start of that phase (ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017). In the case of DAEMON, that implies providing objective evidence that the framework conforms to requirements. To achieve this, the requirements have been specified following the norm ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018. Therefore, each requirement has been worded such that its realization can be verified.

The top-down specification based on inheritance makes it easier to verify the NI-cluster by a down-top verification approach. Section 9.10 describes the tests that shall be done per each requirement to evaluate its completion.

5 Network Intelligence Analysis

In this section we first analyze the current state-of-the-art of network intelligence frameworks and architectures. Based on this analysis, we then analyze the challenges imposed by an edge-to-cloud environment to applications and systems for what concerns data distribution and management in such scattered infrastructure. Next, we investigate the impact of operating at different timescale for control systems and machine learning training. Finally, we provide a taxonomy of deep learning applications applied for wireless networks as well as identified key gaps and innovations. This analysis will serve as basis to design the end-to-end DAEMON architecture for the harmonized integration of NI in B5G systems.

5.1 Limits of existing frameworks and architectures

The future generations of network technologies will be built on top of the highly heterogeneous 5G ecosystems that span not only 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN), but also the strongly diversified virtualized network functions (e.g., traffic classifiers, load balancers, serving gateways, etc.) and Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) services (video analytics, data caching, etc.) deployed in the cloud and network edge infrastructure. The stringent Quality of Service (QoS) requirements promised by 5G and MEC [28] (e.g., greater coverage, end-to-end ultra-low latency of 1ms-10ms, massive connectivity, capacity above 100Mbps, etc.), accompanied by enormous heterogeneity in network resources, technologies, vendors, operators, user equipment, etc., make traditional manual network management impossible to scale and to maintain. Thus, it is an utmost challenge to achieve high QoS and Quality of Experience (QoE) without sophisticated management and orchestration solutions, which are, at the same time, compliant to the standards (i.e., ETSI NFV [27], ETSI MEC [28], ETSI NFV-MANO [29], ETSI ENI [30], Open RAN, ONAP). A detailed analysis of these frameworks can be found in Section 10 Appendix B.

5G and B5G, as well as cloud and edge computing solutions, reduce data transmission time for latency-sensitive use cases (e.g., vehicular communications), but require automated network management to cope with the network heterogeneity and users' mobility. Therefore, the aforementioned challenges press an urgent need for transition from a poorly scalable network management to its automation. In short, the beyond 5G networks require efficient management and orchestration of network services and resources that enables seamless service operation (i.e., service continuity) across different network domains, e.g., cloud and edge networks, and provides resources for virtualized services on optimal places wherever they are needed, see Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1. NI-assisted hierarchical multi-timescale management and orchestration of services and resources.

The edge clouds expose their resources to host and deploy numerous service applications that can be easily instantiated, and terminated in a dynamic way, and due to the opportunities to deploy these services in a lightweight manner (e.g., containerized services), management and orchestration solutions can also support a migration of services from one edge to another. Although provisioning of virtualized services on the distributed network edge contributes to decreasing the latency in communication, mobility of users still imposes significant challenge for optimization of orchestration and management techniques, and to cope with such challenge these techniques need to pursue a real-time monitoring and automated configuration of distributed service deployments. Therefore, such automated closed-loop life-cycle management and orchestration of network services and resources is based on the three inter-coupled activities, i.e., orchestration, control, and monitoring, which can be further optimized by making proactive decisions as an outcome of support provided by NI. The recent advances in Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) aim to facilitate network management automation to a great extent when incorporated in 5G and MEC architectures. In particular, SDN and NFV bring more flexibility and programmability to wired and wireless communication networks, while enabling higher resource utilization and lower costs, where the separation between control and data plane contributes to effective and dynamic resource and service management in modern computing environments. However, the rapid development of services and applications and the mobility of users still imposes significant challenge for traditional orchestration and management techniques. Therefore, there is a need of integrating different management frameworks and leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques to assist them on decision making, providing them with reasoning capabilities to adapt to changing conditions dynamically, enabling true automation.

5.2 Data management

Edge infrastructure typically encompasses a heterogeneous mix of resources that can be extremely diverse in terms of capabilities and operating conditions. In contrast, cloud infrastructure is stationary and highly homogeneous. Nevertheless, it would be naive to consider the cloud and edge as two discrete locations. Rather, they are the two extremities of a continuum inside which compute, storage, and networking resources can be deployed at any point and in any topology [31]. These resources are therefore expected to be heterogeneous in terms of capabilities like:

- **Computing power:** data center server vs end-user device vs embedded sensors
- **Energy requirements:** devices may be battery-powered
- **Mobility patterns:** on-board units embedded in cars/trains
- **Traffic patterns:** sensors producing large amount of data towards the network (push up) vs servers serving data/video (push down)
- **Activity pattern:** always on vs long sleep mode

Despite their diversity, resources are expected to collaborate at a certain degree to compose a unified infrastructure where network functions and end-user applications can be deployed on. This leads to the scenario where multiple application/system components (e.g., microservices) can run at very different locations within the network infrastructure: from the far edge up to the cloud. In this case, one fundamental problem is how to effectively enable an end-to-end data semantics in the whole application/system while easing the development, deployment, and management of the target application, either infrastructure-oriented or user-oriented. This is a fundamental requirement to truly enable an application 1) to run and 2) being migrated everywhere in the network without incurring in heavy reconfiguration. In every system, we can summarize the main data patterns as follow:

- **Data are pushed or pulled:** This kind of pattern is very common in reactive systems like cyber-physical applications (e.g., robotics) or event-driven software paradigm (e.g., in cloud web-based applications). According to this pattern, a publisher decides when to push data into the system which is then delivered to the subscribers.
- **Data are computed on demand:** In this case, fresh data can be requested whenever it is deemed necessary.
- **Data are stored:** Some data in the system requires to be stored temporarily or permanently to be processed later.
- **Data have different representations:** The format data are stored may be different from the format they were originally produced. In other terms, the format used when producing data may be different from the format used when consuming them.

As of today, a complex error-prone patchwork design is required to achieve an end-to-end data semantics integrating the above patterns across the whole infrastructure, from the tiny sensors up to the powerful data centers. Various multiple network protocols are needed nowadays to be stitched together

to provide the necessary support, with the inherent great burden on application complexity, system management and troubleshooting. Assuming the case where an operator/application developer is still willing to embrace all the above complexity for achieving an end-to-end semantics, this will still hinder the overall dynamic system optimization since of the hard limits (i.e., the boundaries of each network tier) this approach imposes.

To better frame the above in the NI Multi-timescale Closed-loop AI Framework, it can be seen how data produced in the network can be used for different purposes: e.g., on the wire transmission optimization, regional traffic capacity forecast, anomaly detection, pre-emptive replicas for redundancy, application migration to meet traffic demands, etc. In all these cases, NI models are interested in processing some data (on-line or off-line) and produce some action as result. These models are seldom interested in how to retrieve data (e.g., where data are stored) or what is the data format used when producing them. Their goal is to consume and process data without dealing with the whole network complexity laying underneath.

The NI Multi-timescale Closed-loop AI Framework should hence provide a decentralized and unified data management approach to facilitate the development, operation and management of any NI model. To that end, the envisaged requirements are:

- **Unification** of various data patterns in a single and harmonized platform supporting data in motion (i.e., pub/sub), data in use (i.e., caching), data at rest (i.e., storages), and on-demand computation (i.e., remote procedure calls).
- **Decentralization** by design to support the very distributed nature of the edge and fog computing where resources and applications are expected to be more mobile, and volatile compared to traditional cloud computing.
- **Heterogeneity** by design to account for the great diversity of devices, resources, applications, and traffic/mobility patterns that are expected to coexist in the edge and fog infrastructure.
- **Eventually consistency** to be more resilient to failures in the network and to guarantee that the overall system is brought to a halt in case of temporary inconsistencies (e.g., network partitioning).
- **Wire efficiency** to reduce the overhead in the network and hence reduce the overall energy consumption of the system.
- **Data pipeline** to support the staged processing of some data where multiple NI models may be chained together.

The data are the main input/output for the development, operation, and management of any NI model. An NI model may comprise several components that run at different locations in the network to accomplish an overarching goal. In case of NI, we can identify two main modes of operation: NI control and NI training. The former relates to the capability of running a trained model into the network to control it at different timescale according to its intended purpose (e.g., resource scheduling, link optimization, capacity forecasting, etc.). The latter relates to the capability of consuming data and produces a model as output to be later deployed in the network for control reasons.

5.3 Control

In B5G the automation of the orchestration and control of resources of access and edge infrastructure will play a crucial role. Decisions are being made on multiple layers:

1. The end-to-end orchestrator needs to make decisions (e.g., where to place or more virtual network function) related to the end-to-end performance without having a detailed view on the status from individual domains; and
2. The domain controllers that take local decisions for the domain they control (e.g., setting network schedulers, allocating compute resource for processes, routing traffic), both taking the interaction with adaptive applications into account.

Stability is of prime concern in these multi-layer control loops. Currently decisions are taken (often manually) prudently to avoid stability issues. Moreover, agility in terms changing objectives and system behavior (e.g., due to a new software release). Our goal is not necessary to improve the performance of algorithms, but rather the level of automation. A reasonably good enough algorithm that is likely to be more stable in changing circumstances is preferred than an algorithm that is over-engineered to cope with only few specific situations.

The timescale of decisions taken by the end-to-end orchestrator is between typical inter-arrival times of network slices (i.e., days, hours) and the typical duration of periods of elevated traffic load that users of the slice produce (which fluctuations might impact the orchestrator decision). The timescale at which the domain controllers need to make decisions is much shorter (seconds to sub-seconds).

The algorithms running in the orchestrator and the domain controllers will take their actions based on data that a monitoring system provides related to status of the hardware infrastructure, e.g., CPU load on servers, traffic load on links, latencies experienced by applications, etc. As explained above, the

orchestrator will only have a limited view on the details in the domain. Similarly, all desired data upon which the controller needs to make decisions will possibly not be available timely. Therefore, also the domain controllers will have to take decisions based on partial observations. One of the research questions to be tackled is to investigate how the status of the domains can be summarized concisely, so that the orchestrator can still benefit from it to make sensible decisions without requiring huge information flows, and to isolate the right domain data that allows the domain controller to make timely decisions.

Also, it is worth mentioning that such different timescales between orchestrator and local controller will pose the limitation to the design of algorithm. For instance, the real-time controller can make their local decisions over their working time interval (e.g., milliseconds, seconds) only based on the resource provisioned by the orchestrator; in contrast, the orchestrator monitors the performance statistics of individual controller and make the scaling and resource provisioning decision on a larger time interval (e.g., hours, days). Such hierarchical decision-making mechanism is beneficial to craft independent decision-making algorithms; nevertheless, it may pose significant manual bounds on the optimization goals, once such hierarchy under-utilize or over-utilize the information from the others. Therefore, another research question is to craft such multi-layer control loop in a reasonable hierarchy with few extra constraints and small performance bound, compared with the non-hierarchy one.

Orthogonally but heavily intertwined to intra-slice control and orchestration, is the dynamic scheduling of (typically scarce) shared physical resources between slices. Based on priority policies or relative weight policies, resources need to be assigned to different slices with different objectives. The importance of achieving intent X of slice A need to be expressed compared to achieving intent Y of slice B. This expression can be seen as the inter-slice intent driving a resource controller/orchestrator. A control and orchestration architecture should support a composition of multi-layer hierarchic intra- and inter-slice control and orchestration, each level driven by high-level intent objectives.

Last but not least, the aforementioned high-level per-slice intent itself shall be capable of being compared with each other to facilitate the decision making by the controller/orchestrator, under the provisioned comparison rules. These rules can be view as the inter-slice intent, which can be stateless or stateful. To be more specific, the stateless rules do the intent comparison without considering the per-slice current status (e.g., execution time, statistics, active end-users), whereas the stateful ones take the slice status into consideration and make the comparison correspondingly. To sum up, different intent comparison mechanisms shall be considered within the architecture.

For what concerns NI control, in the following we focus on the timescale at which data are produced, stored and consumed by considering the following:

- **Very short timescale (us-ms):** this may refer to the case where a constant stream of data is produced and consumed locally for taking localized optimization decisions. At this rate, it's not feasible to store the data produced for a long period of time (e.g., minutes or hours) given the large amount of space required. However, storing data in a small cache could be used to optimize the local system according to the recent history. The system is mainly characterized by **high-throughput data producers and consumers**. Data producer, consumer and storage need to be colocated for performance reasons. The task to be accomplished is very specialized leading to a very well-defined dataset and optimization procedures. The NI models target exclusively **on-line optimization**.
- **Short timescale (ms-s):** this case is like the previous one with the exception that data producer, consumer and storage may be distributed across neighboring nodes. The dataset and type of optimization procedures are still very specialized. However, at this timescale they can take the flavor of a local collaborative optimization with interaction between near components and systems. The NI models target exclusively **on-line optimization**.
- **Medium timescale (s-min):** more generic optimizations could be run in a limited portion of the overall system. Datasets are more heterogeneous where multiple states of the local system can be considered together (e.g., network load, traffic pattern, UE mobility) to perform a reactive/proactive optimization of the mobile network. In this case, a **balanced mix of data producers, consumers, and storages** are considered to both quickly reacting to events in the network and operating in response to the recent history of the system. Multiple NI models could be started to be chained together in a **decentralized data pipeline** where data are processed locally but decisions are taken at localized system level. The NI models target both **on-line and (limited) off-line optimization**.
- **Long timescale (min-h):** optimizations at complete system level start to be feasible. Datasets are heterogeneous and composed of aggregated data. In this case, the **data storages are the main source of data** whereas data producers serve the purpose of updating those storages with aggregated data. A decentralized data pipeline could serve the purpose of aggregating data first and processing them next. NI models for intelligently **aggregating data** will need to work in an **on-line** fashion while NI models performing **system-level optimization** are expected to work **off-line**.

- **Very long timescale (h-days):** at this timescale only system level optimization is performed. **Data storages are the only source of data.** Dataset and type of optimization procedures are extremely heterogeneous. A data pipeline is then advisable to perform a multi-stage optimization via the chaining of several NI models. **Optimization** is purely performed **off-line**.

Table 5-1 presents a summary of the different time scales characteristics. An additional important aspect related to control timescales is the capability of the control system to operate in a timely fashion, guaranteeing a response within a specified timing constraint. From a system-level point of view, we can say that the control system needs to operate in real-time according to the corresponding timescale(s). It's important to remark that in this case we refer to real-time not as a synonym of low latency but rather to express the capability of the control system to meet a given deadline at any timescale of interest as later described in Section 6.1.

Table 5-1. Summary of NI control timescale characteristics.

NI Control Timescale	Time units	Optimization level	On-line/off-line
Very short	Microseconds-Milliseconds	Local optimization	On-line
Short	Milliseconds-seconds	Local/collaborative optimization	On-line
Medium	Seconds-minutes	Local optimization	On-line and off-line
Long	Minutes-hours	System level optimization	Off-line
Very long	Hours-days	System level optimization	Off-line

5.4 Machine learning workflows

For what concerns NI training, in the following we focus on the timescale at which data are produced, stored, and consumed in the context of a single NI component. Different approaches exist in machine learning: (i) supervised learning when the data contains inputs as well as the output, (ii) unsupervised learning, when we only have inputs, and classify them using a similarity method, and (iii) reinforcement learning when we have input and a function that tell us how good our output is. Deep learning on the hand is a part of machine learning that leverages on multi-layer artificial neural networks. Like what done for the NI control case, the following puts in a timescale context the NI training:

- **Very short timescale (us-ms):** this is not applicable. Training NI models is a computing intensive task which requires longer timeframes. And, model validation is not achievable in such short timescale.
- **Short timescale (ms-s):** this is not applicable. Training NI models is a computing intensive task which requires longer timeframes. Moreover, model validation is not achievable in such short timescale.
- **Medium timescale (s-min):** leveraging Transfer learning when an already trained model is used as basis, small NI models could be trained. However, the size of the dataset needs to be small and the model easy to verify.
- **Long timescale (min-h):** Similar to the medium timescale case but with a dataset that might be larger. Leveraging on silicon that accelerates the training process could speed-up the training for small to medium models.
- **Very long timescale (h-days):** This is the usual timescale at which training happens. A simplified ML Workflow is illustrated in Figure 5-2, where data comes in and the output is the trained model. Human interaction is needed in non-trivial steps like Feature engineering and model building. Training and validation of different models can be run in parallel to save time when validating different models.

Figure 5-2. Simplified machine learning workflow.

Table 5-2 presents a summary of the different time scales characteristics.

Table 5-2. Summary of NI training timescale characteristics.

NI Training Timescale	Time units	Model Validation	Dataset size
Very short	Microseconds-Milliseconds	NA	NA
Short	Milliseconds-seconds	NA	NA
Medium	Seconds-minutes	Transfer learning	Small size NI models
Long	Minutes-hours	Transfer learning	Medium size NI models
Very long	Hours-days	Feature Engineering, Human in the loop	Real size NI models

AI/ML is a cornerstone in the design of DAEMON's architecture. The goal is to exploit AI/ML models to carry out tasks that have traditionally been done quasi-statically by human operators in the past or are overly complex tasks that never made the transfer from academia into production systems. These include tasks such as, for instance, zero-touch and automated resource control tasks, anomaly detection or traffic classification. However, creating ML models that work well in practice is only a small portion of the effort needed to deliver real ML solutions in production environments. DAEMON's architecture is being designed following the MLOps methodology, which operationalizes the development, training, and deployment of ML models in production environments (see more information about MLOps in Section 11 – Annex C).

Figure 5-3. DAEMON ML workflows.

Inspired by O-RAN [35], we follow the following general principles:

- Offline learning as a good practice **even for reinforcement learning (RL) algorithms**. This usually requires a labelled dataset or, in the case of RL, a digital twin, a simulator or a model the RL algorithm can interact with in an offline training environment.
- A model can be trained and deployed in a production-like environment (test), e.g., using network slicing, that is running in parallel with the production environment to exploit the richness of real data [32].
- A model can be trained with both real and synthetic data, e.g., from a digital twin, in order to mitigate the lack of large amount of real data required by Deep Learning algorithms and maximize the use of the easy-to-get synthetic data without negatively impacting the performance of model in real deployments [33], [34].

- A model should be trained and tested **before** its deployment in the network.
- ML applications shall be designed in a **modular** manner, with no dependencies on the location/nature of the data source.
- When deploying an ML model, a service provider should be able to **decide** which controller, orchestrator or VNF/PNF the model should be deployed into.

The overall AI/ML framework is illustrated in Figure 5-3. Following the MLOps methodology (Section 11 – Appendix C). We hence define **ML training host** as the entity (network function) that builds the ML model and performs its training offline. Similarly, an **ML inference host** corresponds to the network function that executes the ML model and/or performs online training. A ML model will usually be part of a larger decision-making solution, i.e., an ML-assisted solution, which is in turn hosted by **the actor**, the ultimate responsible to perform decisions or actions. These actions may be of different nature, including configuration management (CM) changes, policy management, or VNF/CNF/PNF control/policy parameters, depending on the deployment flavor of the ML hosts.

Three deployment scenarios are considered:

1. A Non-RT RAN controller, an edge orchestrator, or an end-to-end orchestrator take up both roles of ML training and inference host. In this case, the process of building the ML model, its life-cycle management and data provisioning is handled internally within the NI Orchestration layer. Two types of actions are considered in this case:
 - a. A policy for a controller, which is transferred through a **policy service** (e.g., as provided by A1 interface in O-RAN).
 - b. A VNF/CNF/PNF configuration parameter, which is enforced using appropriate interfaces (e.g., O1 in case of O-RAN's Non-RT RIC).
2. A Non-RT RAN controller, an edge orchestrator, or an end-to-end orchestrator take the role of ML training host, while a near-RT controller acts as ML inference host. The nature of the action may be twofold:
 - a. The near-RT controller itself, e.g., forecasting information for internal mechanisms, where an **enrichment data service** is used for data provisioning between non and near-RT controller or between the orchestrator and a controller.
 - b. A VNF/CNF/PNF configuration parameter, where appropriate interfaces (e.g., E2 in O-RAN) are used for both **data collection** and **enforcement of control or policy parameters**.
3. A Non-RT RAN controller, an edge orchestrator, or an end-to-end orchestrator acts as the ML training host and a VNF/CNF/PNF takes the role of ML inference host.

Regardless the deployment option and the type of AI/ML algorithm (supervised, unsupervised or reinforcement learning), there are a series of key steps that are relevant:

- **ML model capability query/discovery.** Whenever an ML-assisted solution requires to build an AI/ML model, the NI Orchestration layer shall discover some capabilities in the ML inference host, namely: HW processing capabilities (e.g., CPU/GPU resources, memory, etc.), supported ML models and engines (e.g., JSON, protobuf, etc.), NFVI-based architecture support, and data sources available.
- **ML model selection and training.** The ML model designer needs to make a series of choices, e.g., exploration-vs-exploitation intervals in reinforcement learning, format of the input and out data, etc.
- **ML model deployment and inference.** Models may be deployed via containerized images into the inference host.
- **ML model performance monitoring.** Explicit feedback of the performance of the ML model (e.g., for training in reinforcement learning mechanisms).
- **ML model update.** Online model updates (e.g., online training) or major model updates done by the ML designer.

5.5 Taxonomies of deep learning applications in wireless networks

Error! Reference source not found. shows a taxonomy of AI/ML applications at different layers of the network stack. At the physical layer, raw signals act as input to AI/ML algorithms. These raw signals are processed to identify the transmitting technology, transmission parameters (e.g., modulation), or design efficient error correction codes. At the data link layer, AI/ML algorithms are used as function approximators. Multiple transmission parameters (e.g., power level, frequencies, etc.) act as input features to the algorithm, which will provide an accurate model of channel conditions. The applications at the network layer mainly focus on traffic management. Some algorithms address the problem of how the traffic is routed through the network to optimize a given goal (e.g., minimize delay). Other algorithms identify the type of traffic that flows through the network, so differentiated treatment is performed (e.g., streaming video vs email). Or they can be used as a congestion control mechanism to specific parts of

the network or predict the traffic demand and achieve better optimization of network resources. At the upper layers of the network stack, AI/ML applications are mainly focused on the management of computing and networking resources, network security and network dimensioning.

Table 5-3. AI/ML applications in networking.

Network Stack	Network Planning	Network Diagnosis and Security	Network Optimization and Control
Upper layers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VNF Placement • Network dimensioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fault management • Intrusion and anomaly detection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource management • QoS and QoE management
Network layer	Traffic routing	Traffic classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic prediction • Congestion control
Data link layer	NA	Link evaluation	Spectrum allocation
Physical layer	NA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology recognition • Modulation classification 	NA

In addition to the previous classification, we consider a horizontal axis representing the area of application. Most of the proposed use cases can be classified into three application areas: network planning, network diagnostics and security and network optimization and control. Given the dynamicity of the network, traditional approaches in network planning are becoming obsolete. Therefore, most of the AI/ML solutions are focused on the dynamic re-configuration, allocation, distribution of the resources. Network diagnostics and security solutions focus on monitoring the network state and trigger higher-level decisions (e.g., re-route the traffic, deny admission, among others). Finally, network optimization and control solutions are targeted to make the network more autonomous in its decisions by accommodating the appropriate amount of resources depending on the demand's requirements.

5.5.1 Traffic Prediction

Traffic Prediction (TP) entails the forecasting of future traffic volumes based on previously observed traffic volumes. Thanks to these predictions, resource allocation algorithms can optimally operate. Traditionally, TP has been addressed through time series analysis, using Neural Networks [36], [37], [38], [39], [40], and achieving high long- and short-term accuracy at low complexity. However, it is challenging to measure the traffic volume on a given link, especially in high-speed links. Therefore, approaches that don't use time series analysis are proposed.

In such approaches [41], [42], [43], the traffic volume is inferred from flow information such as flow count and packet header fields. Nonetheless, methods based on time series analysis continue to have better prediction accuracy. More recently, RNN (LSTM + Autoencoders) approaches [44] have been proposed to exploit the spatiotemporal characteristics of the traffic with better accuracy than traditional models (ARIMA and SVR).

5.5.2 Traffic Classification

Traffic classification (TC) allows inferring the application that is generating the traffic flowing through the network. In this way, security and QoS policies can be enforced on each flow. In general, the TC task has been done using port numbers or inspecting the application payload. Using port numbers is nowadays unreliable due to dynamic port negotiation. Examining the application payload assumes that the inspected traffic belongs to the same network domain and over a byte/protocol representation of the packet at the Link Layer L2 (or above). These assumptions limit the capabilities of TC systems in wireless networks using a shared spectrum. Users' traffic transmissions can negatively impact the users' traffic from one wireless network domain without being noticed by the TC system. The transmissions from other wireless devices may not be demodulated, decoded, or delivered to the upper radio stack layers because either 1) the devices' wireless technologies are different, or 2) they are the same but belong to a different network domain (and its traffic can be encrypted). Flow-based approaches [45], [46], [47] have also been used for TC, but they are limited in the sense that they require to capture the beginning of the flow. More recently, Deep Learning (DL) approaches have been used [48], [49], [50], [51] to overcome the limitations of the approaches mentioned above. They report great accuracy and can work with encrypted and wireless traffic.

5.5.3 Link Evaluation

Given the size and the complexity of current network architectures, optimization problems in networking are intractable. Reducing the computational complexity is of paramount importance, as optimal allocation or decisions could be made. For instance, minimizing the overall power consumption of different transmission patterns in wireless networks can be formulated as a Linear Programming (LP) problem. However, the LP is not suitable for large-sized wireless networks (a large number of wireless links). To reduce the dimension of the optimization program, Liu et al. [52] propose to analyze the quality of every wireless link before solving the LP using a heuristic. In this way, the higher the quality of the link, the more likely the link will be used. Based on the predictions, the links that are not likely used are excluded from the LP formulation, reducing the problem size.

Another example of link evaluation is given in the WLAN performance prediction [53], [54], [55]. IEEE 802.11 (Wi-Fi) is one of the technologies that will provide reliable high performance with a high density of connected devices to support virtual and augmented reality services. However, in highly dense deployments, Wi-Fi performance is severely affected by interference. Therefore, accurate models that predict Wi-Fi performance are needed to evaluate the impact of potential changes (e.g., new user association, deployment of new devices, the introduction of new technology). ML can create accurate models for complex use cases by exploiting a rich amount of data (synthetic or real). In particular, an ML sandbox is proposed on [56] for training and evaluating ML models in a safe environment. The ML sandbox has been defined to mitigate the potential side effects that ML optimizations can have on communications systems.

5.5.4 Fault management

Abnormal situations in networks are more common than expected. To offer a service with 99% availability, network operators must develop strategies to overcome these abnormal situations. There are two approaches for fault management, namely, reactive and proactive. Reactive fault management mitigates the anomaly after its occurrence, while proactive fault management involves predicting the anomaly before its occurrence. Once the fault is detected or predicted, recovery mechanisms must take place. These mechanisms include the localization and determination of the root cause and the mitigation or reparation of the fault. Mainly supervised ML (e.g., [57], [58], [59]) has been used in all three stages of fault management. However, faulty data is difficult to obtain in production. Thus, training is only available on simulated data, which might not reflect the exact behavior of a production network. Consequently, the AI/ML models might not generalize well to unseen scenarios.

5.5.5 Congestion control

Congestion control mechanisms are employed to limit the number of packets that traverse a given link to ensure network stability, fairness in resource utilization, and acceptable packet loss ratio. Those mechanisms are mainly applied on TCP since it constitutes the basis of the current internet. Although TCP is independent of the transmission medium, most of the works have focused on wired networks. For wireless networks, packet loss, one of the clearest congestion indicators, is due to other factors, leading to an unnecessary reduction of the transmission rate. Therefore, most of the proposed approaches ([60], [61]) in this area focus on identifying the cause of the packet loss by using supervised learning on synthetic data. Another well-known congestion control mechanism is queue management [62], [63]. In this mechanism, supervised learning is also used to predict future traffic volumes or queue length values. Moreover, the congestion state can also be estimated by using other network parameters (e.g., RTT and throughput) [64], [65]. Nonetheless, this estimation is difficult to achieve since the relationship between different network parameters and the congestion state is not trivial.

More recently, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques have been used for congestion control ([66], [67], [68]). Here, an agent interacts with the network environment by performing some actions (e.g., changing transmission rate) according to a learned policy, so a reward metric is optimized (e.g., lower delay). The more interactions the agent has with the environment, the better actions it can take. Since congestion control is a continuous problem, the state space of the RL formulation tends to explode with the network size. Therefore, actor-critic mechanisms are normally employed ([69]).

5.5.6 Resource management for Network Resilience

Network resiliency, expressed by the ability to adapt to dynamic changes, is required in B5G network architectures. This property can be achieved by predicting the future demand and allocating the necessary resources in advance. Consequently, resource allocation is a decision problem that involves managing the resources to maximize a long-term objective. However, given the diversity of resources and a large number of network nodes, an optimal allocation is challenging for traditional approaches (e.g., mathematical optimization). In this regard, RL is becoming one of the mostly used tool for resource allocation ([70], [71], [72]), given its ability to learn directly from experience. This property makes RL

suitable for highly variable environments such as networks. Q-learning dominates the RL-based approaches, but they have the disadvantage of exploding the number of states, a difficulty that is overcome with DRL. Supervised Learning (SL) is also employed in resource allocation ([73], [74]) and offers better scalability than RL-based approaches. However, the size of their network architecture has to be adjusted to the problem size.

5.5.7 QoS and QoE management

Different decisions have an impact on network metrics. These metrics are usually expressed in terms of the QoS or QoE. A good QoS/QoE indicates that the decisions and allocated resources are appropriate for serving that service. QoS/QoE assessment can be seen as the feedback needed to guide the network management. Although straightforward and easy to implement, subjective QoS/QoE assessment can be highly unfair and biased, as it involves the individual perception and expectation of a user.

On the other hand, objective QoS/QoE assessment techniques are more accurate at the expenses of high computational effort. Linear and non-linear regressions and correlation models ([75], [76], [77]) are the most common AI/ML techniques used for quantifying the impact of different QoS parameters (e.g., delay, throughput, round-trip time, etc.) on the user's QoE. Nonetheless, there is a lack of common, standard QoE measures, making it difficult to compare the efficiency of different methods.

5.5.8 Intrusion and anomaly detection

Intrusion detection detects malicious attacks that might compromise the network. As with fault management, this is typically a classification problem (normal data vs anomaly data) using user's signatures. While intrusion detection methods are successful at identifying known attacks, they fail at identifying new ones. Therefore, sophisticated strategies for the identification of atypical behavior in the network are needed. Anomalies are treated as a deviation of the expected behavior, making them powerful against "zero-day" attacks (unseen behavior). Nonetheless, they are sensitive to false positives since it is challenging to construct a representation of network normality.

Given the massive volume of network data, manual classification is practically impossible, making ML an attractive option. ML's ability to find patterns in vast volumes of data fits perfectly in this kind of network problem. Moreover, ML offers the advantage to find complex correlations in the data that cannot be deduced from mere observation. DL and RL ([78], [79], [80], [81]) have been used to avoid human interaction and to overcome the challenges mentioned above. However, such approaches are limited by their applicability, as they are mostly trained on synthetic data, and their misclassification can be extremely costly on production networks.

5.5.9 Spectrum allocation

Due to the explosive growth of wireless connections and massive machine-to-machine communications in the IoT era, the spectrum has become a severely scarce resource. Therefore, providing an efficient solution in radio spectrum utilization is an aspect of paramount importance. Given the variability of the spectrum dynamics in wireless environments, identifying which spectrum allocation scheme is appropriate for every wireless transmission is challenging. Consequently, SL, but RL in particular, is mainly used in this aspect ([82], [83], [84], [85]). In RL, an agent explores different allocation schemes. Different network parameters such as throughput or delay act as the needed reward to identify the best configuration in a given transmission slot. However, the exploration stage is mainly based on an estimation of the channel conditions. Based on that estimation, the reward is assigned. Thus, the accuracy of the RL-based approach highly depends on the accuracy of such assessments, leading to wrong decisions if the channel is poorly estimated.

5.5.10 Modulation Classification

Modulation classification addresses the identification of the modulation scheme of received signals. By adapting the modulation scheme to channel conditions, the data transmission is optimized to maximize its throughput while minimizing interference. Previously, this classification was performed manually by experts, which however is impractical for today's high data rates. Automatic modulation classification approaches can be classified as likelihood-based and feature-based. Likelihood-based approaches are based on calculating the likelihood ratios of the received signal and comparing it to all candidate modulations. They provide the optimal solution at expenses of considerable computational complexity, making them impractical for real-time implementations. Feature-based approaches are nowadays possible thanks to AI/ML techniques ([86], [87], [88], [89]), as they allow a direct mapping between the features (e.g., maximum power spectral density, standard deviations amplitude, phase, frequency, and variance of the zero-crossing) and the modulations. However, most recent works employed supervised learning, requiring re-training if a new modulation scheme is introduced. Moreover, most of the results are obtained on offline datasets, using Deep Neural Networks (DNN), limiting their implementation in real-life deployments, especially in constrained-nature environments (e.g., wireless networks).

5.5.11 Technology Recognition

Similar to modulation classification, technology recognition identifies the technology that is accessing the spectrum to allow the management system to take appropriate measures to combat the performance degradation due to interference. AI/ML algorithms allow identifying the wireless technology without any signal pre-processing, such as channel estimation and timing or frequency synchronization ([90], [91], [92], [93]). Using supervised learning, DNNs extract features from raw radio signals to recognize the transmitting technology. However, as in modulation classification, a considerable amount of labeled data is required to obtain higher accuracy in their predictions; otherwise, the DNN model may overfit. Semi-supervised learning ([94]) can overcome the challenge mentioned above by using the unlabeled data to train a feature extractor and refine it with the labeled dataset.

5.5.12 Traffic Routing

One of the main pillars in network planning is traffic routing. SLAs can be fulfilled by finding the best route through a network, depending on the network operator's objectives (e.g., maximize QoS/QoE). Different routing strategies can evenly distribute the traffic to avoid bottlenecks, select the least congested path to route delay-sensitive traffic, or re-route traffic to avoid a network failure. However, given the size of current networks and the different services to support, finding the best suitable path among many candidates is a non-trivial task. Traditional routing protocols like Open Shortest Path First (OSPF) are typically optimized to maximize or minimize one metric.

Moreover, they may fail when dealing with variable traffic volume, as they repeatedly tend to make the same decision for similar scenarios. Benefiting from centralized control, SDN approaches ([95], [96], [97]) achieve a fine-control for packets and are faster in recovering from link failures, especially in large-size networks. At the same time, SDN has become an enabler for traffic routing using data-driven approaches ([98], [99], [100], [101][101]). Most of them use AI/ML to predict future traffic demand (see Traffic Prediction section) and route the traffic using a traditional approach. More recently, Graph Neural Networks have been proposed to learn from graph-structured data and have also been applied to the routing problem with the advantage of generalizing to unseen topologies [102]. In general, two approaches dominate the data-driven approaches, namely, centralized and decentralized routing. If a centralized routing approach is adopted, the controller is responsible for building the current network state, which involves a large amount of data (e.g., node's information, energy condition, queue size, transmission protocols, etc.). Therefore, this approach incurs much overhead. On the other hand, by using a decentralized approach, the routing decisions made by each node must converge to guarantee end-to-end connectivity and the realization of different SLAs.

5.5.13 VNF placement

The placement of the VNFs is of paramount importance, as they impact network metrics (e.g., delay, throughput, QoS, etc.). This problem has been solved using mathematical modeling, but given today's network complexity, these solutions are becoming intractable. Data-driven approaches using AI/ML are also suitable for this problem due to their ability to learn from data, generalizing to unseen scenarios ([103], [104],[104][105], [106]). Most of the existing approaches are based on SL, but as the network size increases, the models' complexity increases as well, which makes them unfeasible (i.e., cost-effective in training and maintaining) to implement. Moreover, they are unable to generalize to unseen network topologies. Although not frequently used, RL is also proposed for VNF placement ([107]). When combined with DL, RL-based approaches can predict the expected behavior of the hosting node (e.g., resource availability). Then, a RL-agent performs the placement following a threshold-based policy, i.e., place the VNF in the host node with highest reward.

5.6 Key Innovations, Gap Analysis

The 5G PPP Technology Board has recently released a white paper on AI and ML as enablers of beyond 5G (B5G) networks based on contributions from 5G PPP projects that research, implement and validate 5G and B5G network systems [108]. In this document, the most relevant current research on AI/ML applied on 5G and B5G networks in three major areas, namely i) Network Planning, ii) Network Diagnostics/Insights, and iii) Network Optimisation and Control, is presented. In particular, the AI/ML-based solutions pertaining to autonomous slice management, control and orchestration, cross-layer optimisation framework, anomaly detection, and management analytics, as well as aspects in AI/ML-as-a-service in network management and orchestration, and enablement of ML for the verticals' domain, and management of ML models and functions are presented.

Although these initiatives are first steps towards zero-touch network operation solutions, several key problems are not addressed and DAEMON aspires to fill this gap. More precisely, the issues that we foresee arising in the integration of AI/ML in the 5G and B5G network architectures associated with the presented 5G-PPP projects are the following:

1. The AI/ML in the 5G and B5G network architectures associated with the presented 5G-PPP projects are focused on integrating single instances of NI in mobile networks by 1) tweaking machine learning solutions so that they fit networking environments and 2) ignoring the need of coordinating many and varied NI deployed at different network segments beyond traditional centralized orchestration.
2. Most of the projects focus on analyzing the architectural requirements of the 5G/B5G networks by assuming one or two NI domains (slicing, control, network optimization, anomaly detection, etc.) and running in the same network segment (RAN, edge, cloud) or multiple network segments but with centralized management/control. This approach is limited as the resource management decisions at different network elements have significant reciprocal effects that cannot be detected, tracked and mitigated, as they are designed as operating in a vacuum. Moreover, the need for multi-time scale coordination and decision-making in distributed environments are not addressed.
3. Several projects are using AI/ML as a 'silver bullet' to solve networking problems and encourage using AI models such as standard DNN architectures to solve any NI task. DAEMON project argues that:
 - a. AI is not the best solution for every NI problem. There are multiple situations in network management where DNNs are unsuitable (e.g., due to hardware or time constraints).
 - b. The dominating approach of plugging 'vanilla' AI models into network controllers and orchestrators is not a sensible choice. Namely, using "default choices" for the design of the NI algorithms, e.g., regarding the loss function, can result in NI decisions that may not be aligned with the operational and/or business objectives, or result in performance that is far from optimal (even if they outperformed traditional methods).

DAEMON architecture goes several steps beyond the mission of these projects and brings many key and timely innovations:

1. It will design end-to-end NI-assisted functionalities and determine the functional and performance requirements. These span networking problems at different timescales (i.e., real-time control versus orchestration) and scopes (i.e., management/control plane versus user plane – e.g., VNF – intelligence).
2. It will spur coordination across multi-timescale NI closed loops in heterogeneous network domains; and (ii) provisioning a rich catalogue of NI models that meet diverse system requirements and are made available to network controllers and network orchestrators and user-plane intelligence.
3. It will include a NI orchestration layer that leverages the NI models devised in this project to provide a comprehensive NI management environment of all network intelligence in a mobile network.
4. It will enable integrating NI deep into the network infrastructure.
5. DAEMON NI design will go beyond the common practice of employing generic machine learning models for network operations and establish the ground for AI models that are natively shaped for network environments.
6. DAEMON NI design will tailor AI techniques to the specific needs of B5G operation, develop novel hybrid approaches, introduce appropriate cost functions for the networking context, and develop novel AI techniques that can adapt their requirements to the available network resources.

In general, the DAEMON project will 1) design an end-to-end architecture for the harmonized integration of NI in B5G systems and 2) develop a knowledge-base and rigorous methodology for developing AI tools assisting NI functionalities to be supported by such architecture.

6 DAEMON initial guidelines

We organize the initial guidelines set forth by DAEMON along two axes, by separating those specifications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Network Intelligence (NI) that stem from technological aspects of mobile network architectures, and those that are driven by requirements that are set by service providers through their application. We discuss in the following sections the two criteria and the associated initial DAEMON guidelines.

6.1 Network-driven specifications of AI for NI

Figure 6-1. Network Intelligence degrees of freedom, input-output relationship, and real-time constraints subject to infrastructure observability and controllability.

Figure 6-1 above depicts the trade-offs that an NI native framework shall be able to tackle; tradeoffs are intrinsically different, mostly driven by the monitoring and enforcement elements in the network (as depicted in the right hand side of the picture). Then, when such tradeoffs are associated to the deadline that each NI task has to fulfill, they result into another set of trade-offs that are related to the specific NI component. We discuss them next.

Based on the discussion on the workflows included in Section 5, we devise initial guidelines about how network specifications (i.e., the intrinsic limitations that the platform is posing) and requirements (of the NI task) affect decisions on the design of the network intelligence (NI), in terms of model selection, configuration and orchestration in all the domains of the mobile network. The main driver for the decisions related to Network Intelligence is **time**. Indeed, directly or indirectly, time is the factor that bounds the quality and selection of NI algorithms. Aspects such as data collection or data processing depend on the underlying infrastructure and its capability (hence yielding a higher or lower time) to complete the actions, or directly on the time needed to execute the NI algorithms.

In Figure 6-1, we present a schematic view of the different scenarios that may emerge when dealing with network intelligence. The figure shows the two main contextual environments in which the algorithms will run. On the left-hand side, Figure 6-1 presents the execution context dimensions, which are the conditions in which the algorithm has to be executed. For NI issues, these aspects are mainly categorized into two dimensions, as follows.

The infrastructure monitoring data consists of all the input data collected and provided by the many and varied measurement probes deployed in the infrastructure, at any level (e.g., central, edge, far-edge).

This could be monitoring data coming from the Network Functions themselves, from the infrastructure hosting them, or the transport network interconnecting them.

More specifically, the monitoring dimension could be further split into three sub-dimensions, which offer different trade-offs:

- **Data sampling rate:** the frequency at which data is gathered. Higher sampling rate force the infrastructure to have more capacity to support his.
- **Dataset richness:** the number of details associated to the data. For instance, a base station can report averaged values for the Signal to Noise ratio or directly, per UE values. This includes the data granularity and the dimension of each item
- **Data locality:** monitoring data can be sampled from specific location of the network or from the entire network. A similar concept can be applied to the same groups of functions: e.g., collect KPI throughput from both the radio and the core together or just from the core.

The infrastructure decision enforcement includes all the parameters that can be changed, reconfigured and orchestrated, typically in a programmatic way through APIs. Analogously to the monitoring data, the enforcement may happen at any level in the network.

Again, this dimension can be split into three sub-dimensions, according to their trade-offs:

- **Delay:** the time it takes to generate the output of the algorithm and inject it through the API into the specific asset (Network Function or Infrastructure). This time is consumed by the budget available for the action.
- **Availability:** actions may be enforced at every single opportunity or may be resilient to some missed opportunity. For instance, scheduling patterns may be enforced at every TTI or may be performed at coarser time granularities.
- **Granularity:** the granularity of the application of the given action. For instance, the maximum Modulation and Coding scheme that could be applied at a single base station level or specified for every single UE.

Given the time constraint and the underlying infrastructure capabilities, there is a finite set of feasible combinations that match all the requirements specified before. For instance, an algorithm may gather data at UE level but cannot enforce it again at UE level, if not on a subset of the gNBs. Or, if the algorithm requires a 1-ms sampling granularity and 1ms-bounded action enforcement, then the gathered metrics and the configurations that can be applied to the network infrastructure could only be very fine if applied very locally to the same network function. Clearly, these are just examples of a more formal analysis that we will execute in the subsequent releases of the WP document.

Once the timing constraint is in place, according to the specific network problem that has to be solved, then a class of NI is selected and implemented. As described in the right-hand part of Figure 6-1. However, there is a further degree of variability that has to be taken into account, which is intrinsic to the selected algorithm. Once more, this can be articulated into three subdimensions:

- **Robustness:** this value indicates the resiliency of the NI to missed inputs. For instance, a suitably trained Neural Network may be capable of extrapolating the output from past inputs, with a likely higher degree of uncertainty, but still providing a reliable outcome. Instead, an optimization algorithm without any memory may be very unreliable or directly not applicable when inputs are missing due to, e.g., delays in the monitoring infrastructure.
- **Optimality:** the robustness and the precision that data driven solutions such as the one based on Neural Networks may achieve come at a price of a higher resource utilization (complex models are fast mostly when used on a GPU), and a certain degree of obscurity in their decision. Hence, for some tasks, a trade-off between the optimality of the decision and the time needed to take it (e.g., with a simpler model or directly with a traditional optimization algorithm) shall be considered.
- **Control Timescale:** This dimension is similar to the infrastructure availability, which poses an upper bound to this value. NI algorithm can then decide to exploit all configuration opportunities or not.

Again, these dimensions pose a trade-off surface that needs to be addressed, especially by the NI Orchestration layer proposed by DAEMON. A fundamental factor here is, for instance, the dichotomy between AI and ML models and the ones based on traditional optimization, that stay at the different ends of the spectrum: resilient and slow the former, precise but potentially more fragile and certainly faster the latter.

An additional important aspect when dealing with control and optimization is the capability of operating real-time. As introduced in Section 5.3, real-time means the capability of the system to guarantee a response within a specified timing constraint (i.e. the capability of meeting a specified deadline). This imposes a specific time budget for NI operations. To keep the controllability of the network infrastructure it is important to understand the whole decision-making pipeline: from monitoring to decision and enforcement:

- **Monitoring:** data may be collected at a given time interval within the network. To properly control the network, monitoring data needs to be as fresh as possible to not incur in the risk of applying changes that are already out-of-date and potentially harmful. A time budget may therefore be considered for data collection in such a way the decision-making model can either falls back or apply protection schemes when data is not received in time.
- **Decision:** the NI needs to produce a response in time according to the control timescale. For this reason, a time budget may be associated to computation of the NI model in such a way some fallback mechanism can be triggered in cases the deadline is missed. Performance may degrade but the controllability of the network rests assured.
- **Enforcement:** finally, also the reconfiguration of the underlying network and infrastructure needs to comply with the target time scale and the associated time budget. In case of missed deadline, the decision-making model may decide to fall back to a longer time scale.

Integrating real-time deadlines in the whole NI orchestration process results in a framework that is easier to extend and integrate with multiple NI algorithms while keeping clear boundaries on the target timescale of the system or a sub-part of it.

Besides the impact on the NI Orchestrator itself, these specifications put some novel requirements on the overall legacy infrastructure composed by VNFs, Orchestration, and Management system.

The VNFs shall be able to run together with NI, hence incorporating mechanisms to report specific NI metrics (which are dependent to the chosen NI algorithms). Some VNFs will be specifically devoted to network intelligence (such as the NWDAF in the Core Networks), other will need to provide specific APIs for these approaches (see Section 5).

The orchestration framework shall also be able to interact with the NI framework, providing feedback about the infrastructure and the current status of the network, which is an incremental addition to the functionality orchestrators already fulfil. However, some specific algorithm such as the self-learning MANO have to be integrated into their architecture.

Finally, the management system shall expose relevant parameters to the service provider in a much finer and interactive way than the legacy solutions. That is, the management system shall be able to support service-driven AI for the NI, as discussed next.

6.2 Service-driven specifications of AI for NI

Specifications are not only driven by architectural and technological aspects, but are also induced by the services that run on top of the network infrastructure and the providers who control such services. At the time of preparing this document, the DAEMON project has identified three use cases where the specifications of AI for NI along depend on the application-level target, as follows.

6.2.1 Use cases with service-driven specifications

Allocation and configuration of resources. In the domain of allocation and configuration of resources, AI shall be designed for NI in concert with time-varying traffic demands and requirements of individual services in multi-tenant settings. The key problem is that of the anticipatory allocation of capacity in network elements, which must be solved in practical cases where the performance depends on the allocated capacity and actual traffic in entangled ways that are not known a priori or observable at decision time. In these cases, defining the loss or objective function is not simple or even possible (e.g., in case the metric is not differentiable, which makes gradient descent not feasible).

For instance, this is the case when the metric is known to the service provider, but not to the network provider, such as the QoE of end users. Indeed, QoE is a (complex) function of the network resource allocation, as SLA violations (which cause, e.g., video streaming freezing) and dimensioning (which enable, e.g., video streaming at better resolution) affect it in complex ways. The QoE of a particular service is well known to be linked to network Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in complex ways; considering that KPIs are in turn affected by resource allocation in non-trivial manner, it is easy to understand how the relationship between resources and QoE is very difficult to quantify or model.

End-to-end SLA across multiple domains. When an end-to-end SLA is to be decomposed over multiple domains, the cross-domain entity responsible for such a decomposition needs to be able to predict how each involved domain on the end-to-end path(s) will react to the part of the SLA it is attributed to. Often that entity does not know the detailed status of the domain at the moment the decomposition decision needs to be made. Instead, that entity can only rely on the previous reactions of a domain to parts of end-to-end SLAs that were previously attributed to that domain. The knowledge contained in these previous reactions needs to be captured in a model upon which the NI at the decomposing entity can base its decision. Such a model takes the part of the end-to-end delay as input and produces the potential reaction of that domain as output. Various types of models can be used, with a neural network classifier being the most promising.

In addition, a comprehensive NI solution requires an AI design based on the disentangling of the relations among satisfying multiple end-to-end SLAs. It turns out that often there is a partial order relation in SLAs, e.g., a more relaxed delay bound, or lower throughput requirement, will invariably lead to the domain reacting more favorably to than a stricter delay bound, or a larger throughput requirement, respectively. To capture this prior knowledge that inherited within the problem, the models envisioned to capture the reaction of the domain to the part of the end-to-end delay that is attributed to the domain, need to have a specific structure. These types of neural network models will be the focus of our attention.

Service provider and network operator integration. The integration between the service providers and the network operators envisioned by 5G networks is yet to be completed. services are currently provided Over-The-Top (OTT). However, next generation mobile networks will transition to a fully blended approach, in which service provider and network provider cooperate to fulfill the requirement of the service. Hence, the interactions between them shall be provided with a flexible and customizable interface, leveraging on an enhanced capability exposure.

- In existing examples of successful business models (e.g., the ones currently employed by Amazon AWS, Google Cloud Platform or Microsoft Azure), the user can freely configure the characteristics of the service they are running. In order to introduce similar models in DAEMON we need additional capability exposure, including the following.
 - Kind and locality of resources: in order to define details such as the kind of nodes running a network service, their power, their location
 - if they need or not special hardware (such as a GPU, a FPGA or a Smart NIC), the service provider needs to gain access (through secure and validated APIs) to the Orchestration platform. This can happen directly or through a more high-level (e.g., intent-based) interface.
- Continuous flow of metrics from the network, including standard QoS metrics (such as latency, aggregated bandwidth, number of users) but also the capability of gathering user defined metrics, by merging more simple metrics at once.
- Receiving suggestions from the network operator regarding business strategies, including information about subscription costs and dynamic SLA (e.g., quality upgrades) or proposal for re-orchestration of VNFs (scaling up or down, relocation to the edge).
- Link raw data analytics from the network infrastructure (including predictions) with the internal business logic of the service provider, which can then make decisions about how to reshape the service offer.

As an example, one can consider again a video streaming service provider using a richer interface that is advantageous compared to OTT operation. In this case, three domains (the network functions, management and orchestration) are still under the same stakeholder (i.e., the network operator), which offers access to the inter-domain bus (e.g., through an IP network) as the vertical service provider. Thus, the service provider can subscribe to continuous monitoring from the Orchestration and Network Functions domain to observe the current KPI and map them with QoE metrics available at the application layer. The service provider also subscribes to dynamic SLA events coming from the operator BSS Management, which informs about different subscription options. Thus, the Video Service Provider could offer the service using a "Silver" plan subscription, and the Operator could offer an upgrade to a "Gold" plan (with the information of the increased cost and the QoS improvements), or the downgrade to a cheaper and less powerful plan. Finally, through re-orchestration suggestions, the service provider has access to a rich version of the traditional OTT paradigm and also goes beyond the Network Slice as a Service (NSaaS) paradigm. So, the service provider can apply its business logic, taking re-orchestration and dynamic SLA decisions based also on metrics such as the current revenue flows, the subscribers' churn rate or the expected popularity of a video.

6.2.2 Customized and adaptable AI for NI

In situations such as those outlined in Section 6.2.1, there is a need for a customized and adaptable AI that is specifically intended for NI. DAEMON identifies several early requirements that are driven by application-level needs, as follows.

Closing the loss-metric mismatch. In all use cases in Section 6.2.1 above, it is important that the loss or objective function employed by the AI model aligns fully with the actual performance metrics of interest, e.g., customer QoE, network QoS indicators, or the monetary cost associated to system operation. Therefore, baseline loss functions that are common, such as L1, L2, Cross-Entropy or Logistic, may not be the ideal in networking environments. Here, the project identifies a need to derive general guidelines for the design of dedicated loss functions that are consistent with the network application requirements.

Designing a methodology for self-learning AI models. In the examples above, the metric is not directly observable by the operator as it maps to performance at the applications layer (i.e., in the service provider domain). Also, such a metric is often known only after the network management decision has

been taken by NI, which implies that the only way to obtain the metric value is by enacting a decision and measuring its effect on performance. This calls for AI models that dynamically and automatically balance costs and efficiency, by learning the loss function indirectly from the feedback of the end-customers (e.g., tenants), without requiring them to explicitly identify their objectives.

Developing adaptive AI models. A very desirable feature in several use cases is that of having elastic NI models capable of adapting their complexity to the mobile network environment, which is inherently different from, e.g., Cloud or High Performance Computing (HPC) settings typically considered for AI models. This involves that NI models can trade off computational complexity for accuracy, responsiveness or energy efficiency as needed (for instance, during network congestion, in presence of infrastructure faults, etc.).

Enabling exposure towards applications. Besides the requirements above, which are focused on the AI design for management decision-making, the use cases highlight a need for NI algorithms that empower the end-to-end network system to implement and leverage specific capabilities to expose network functionalities to tenants.

During the lifetime of the action, the DAEMON project will aim at developing original algorithmic solutions for AI dedicated to Ni, towards achieving NI solutions that can meet the above specifications.

7 Conclusions & Future Work

This deliverable presented the definition of initial requirements analysis and state-of-the-art frameworks and toolsets. During the design phase of the architectural framework for NI-native B5G networks, the project identifies the following objectives:

- Alignment with relevant standardization tracks.
- Alignment with other EU Horizon projects that are focused on network management techniques, and enhancing those techniques by bringing embedding NI functions and algorithms.
- Enhancement of traditional centralized closed-loop approaches in network management and orchestration, by distributing the network intelligence in the form of NI instances/algorithms at different levels in the network architecture.
- Cooperation between NI instances to increase the efficiency of their individual performance.
- Provision of the set of NI algorithms that can run in those NS instances, and selection of the most suitable NI algorithm based on a predefined criterion, and influenced by contextual information, available resources, performance requirements, and amount of data to be processed,
- Coordination of all network NI instances to ensure reliable and efficient operation of all operations that are running with different timescales, in different micro-domains.

Accordingly, Section 1 introduces the deliverable, describing the objectives, methodology and status of WP2; including the relationship of D2.1 with other WP2 deliverables, but also with those of other WPs. Section 2 details on the vision for a network intelligence framework, discussing the bottlenecks in current softwareized network architectures, such as i) the centralized closed-loop models that increase latency of the data transfer and decision-making processes, as well as ii) the insufficient cooperation between NI instances that leads to uncoordinated and suboptimal decisions by individual NI instances imposing risks of low efficiency in decision-making process. Section 2 also defines the role and importance of NI in B5G deployments, presenting the necessity for architectural changes in B5G infrastructure to bridge the identified gaps.

Section 3 presents NI functionalities and use cases that are aligned with the Network Intelligence Framework presented in Section 2, and are mapped to the three main B5G AI/ML use cases defined by 5GPPP [1], i.e., i) Network Planning, ii) Network Diagnosis and insights, and iii) Network Optimization and Control. All eight NI functionalities are thoroughly studied from a perspective of requirements, creating the extensive set of non-functional and functional requirements that are jointly analysed in Section 4, and presented in detail in Section 9 (Appendix A).

Section 5 discussed the NI workflows, as well as the details on existing multi-timescale architectural frameworks and architectures, considering different aspects of the closed-loop AI, such as data management, control, and training. In Section 5, ML workflows, and taxonomies of deep learning are presented, and they are followed by the gap analysis, which points at the main gaps where the DAEMON architecture is bringing innovation comparing to the 5G PPP projects when it comes to complete automation of network operations,

Furthermore, based on the NI workflows of Section 5, Section 6 derives initial guidelines on the i) selection, ii) configuration, and iii) orchestration of all NI instances deployed in the network. All three aspects are driven by the time constraints in NI functions execution, considering time as one of the most influential factors when making decisions on selection, configuration, and orchestration, of NI functions and algorithms. The specifications of AI for NI that are provided in Section 6 are studied from the perspectives of the network, and the service, thus the specifications are separately presented as network-driven, and service-driven ones.

The work presented in this deliverable has been carried out by WP2 partners, during the first six months of the project, and it tackles both engineering and research aspects that need to be addressed in the DAEMON project. All four tasks (T2.1, T2.2, T2.3, and T2.4) have produced various results, starting with the state-of-the-art analysis of architectural frameworks and toolsets for network management. Furthermore, all partners contributing to the WP2 have been involved in identifying the non-functional and functional requirements for the NI-assisted architectural framework, providing a detailed overview of requirements, and discussing their verifiability as well. The outcomes presented in this deliverable are being used in WP3 and WP4 to support the decisions to design and select the most appropriate models to address the concrete networking problems tackled by these WPs.

The future work in WP2 is based on an iterative process that will incorporate the feedback provided by WP3/WP4 (algorithms) and WP5 (performance evaluation), so the DAEMON's NI framework and tools keep evolving and are aligned with the NI-assisted functionality designed and developed in WP3 and WP4. At the NI functional and performance requirements (T2.1) and NI Multi-timescale closed-loop AI framework design (T2.2) tasks, the feedback from WP3/WP4 (Algorithms) and WP5 (performance evaluations) will be used to refine the functional and performance requirements together with the

interfaces and NI orchestration layer design. The initial taxonomy of NI approaches (T2.3), which includes both the network functionalities targeted by this project and additional ones in the same domain, will be extended by updating the existing ones and discovering new opportunities in hybrid approaches that combine AI models and more traditional ones. This information will allow WP3 and WP4 to support their decisions on the most appropriate models to address the concrete networking problems tackled in each of them. Finally, the methodology to adapt existing AI models to the specificities of real-world NI problems (T2.4.) will start being defined so that pure AI/ML models or hybrids ones, outlined in T2.3, can be integrated into NI solutions and achieve the expected performance. The resulting model customization methodology will provide general guidelines for designing dedicated loss functions, self-learning algorithms, and models that adapt to the context. The iterative process will be carried on at least twice during the execution of the project. The feedback from WP3/WP4 (algorithms design) and WP5 (algorithm efficiency) will be officialized via D3.1/D4.1 (M11) and D3.2/D4.2(M23), while the updates from WP2 to WP3 and WP4 will be at M16, M19 (D2.2), M27, and M30 (D2.3).

8 References

- [1] 5GPPP. 2020. AI and ML – Enablers for Beyond 5G Networks. White Paper. s.l. : 5GPPP, 2020. [Online] Available: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4299895>.
- [2] P. Mursia, V. Sciancalepore, A. Garcia-Saavedra, L. Cottatellucci, X. Costa-Perez, D. Gesbert. [RISMA: Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces Enabling Beamforming for IoT Massive Access](#). In *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 2020.
- [3] Dunna, Manideep, et al. "ScatterMIMO: Enabling virtual MIMO with smart surfaces." *Proceedings of the 26th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*. 2020.
- [4] S. Fu, F. Yang and Y. Xiao, "AI Inspired Intelligent Resource Management in Future Wireless Network," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 22425-22433, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2968554.
- [5] Slamnik-Kriještorac, N.; de Britto e Silva, E.; Municio, E.; Carvalho de Resende, H.C.; Hadiwardoyo, S.A.; Marquez-Barja, J.M. Network Service and Resource Orchestration: A Feature and Performance Analysis within the MEC-Enhanced Vehicular Network Context. *Sensors* 2020, 20, 3852. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20143852>.
- [6] A. Sapiro, I. Abdelaziz, A. Aldilajjan, M. Canini, and P. Kalnis, "In-network computation is a dumb idea whose time has come," in *Proceedings of the 16th ACM Workshop on Hot Topics in Networks*, pp. 150–156, 2017.
- [7] F. Yang, Z. Wang, X. Ma, G. Yuan, and X. An, "SwitchAgg: a further step towards in-network computation," arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.04024, 2019.
- [8] A. Sapiro, M. Canini, C.-Y. Ho, J. Nelson, P. Kalnis, C. Kim, A. Krishnamurthy, M. Moshref, D. R. Ports, and P. Richtárik, "Scaling distributed machine learning with in-network aggregation," arXiv preprint arXiv:1903.06701, 2019.
- [9] Z. Xiong and N. Zilberman, "Do switches dream of machine learning? toward in-network classification," in *Proceedings of the 18th ACM Workshop on Hot Topics in Networks*, pp. 25–33, 2019.
- [10] Cristina Marquez, Marco Gramaglia, Marco Fiore, Albert Banchs, and Xavier Costa-Perez. 2018. How Should I Slice My Network? A Multi-Service Empirical Evaluation of Resource Sharing Efficiency. In *Proceedings of the 24th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking (MobiCom '18)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 191–206. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3241539.3241567>.
- [11] Antonis Manousis, Rahul Anand Sharma, Vyas Sekar, and Justine Sherry. 2020. Contention-Aware Performance Prediction For Virtualized Network Functions. In *Proceedings of the Annual conference of the ACM Special Interest Group on Data Communication on the applications, technologies, architectures, and protocols for computer communication (SIGCOMM '20)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 270–282. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3387514.3405868>.
- [12] Jose A. Ayala-Romero, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, Marco Gramaglia, Xavier Costa-Perez, Albert Banchs, and Juan J. Alcaraz. 2019. VrAI: A Deep Learning Approach Tailoring Computing and Radio Resources in Virtualized RANs. In *the 25th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking (MobiCom '19)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 30, 1–16. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3300061.3345431>.
- [13] Vodafone Group Plc. 'Sustainable Business Report 2019'. [Online] Available: <https://www.vodafone.com/content/dam/vodcom/sustainability/pdfs/sustainablebusiness2019.pdf>.
- [14] Huawei Technologies Co.,Ltd 'GREEN 5G: BUILDING A SUSTAINABLE WORLD' . [Online] Available: https://www-file.huawei.com/-/media/corp2020/pdf/public-policy/green_5g_building_a_sustainable_world_v1.pdf.
- [15] Cañete, A., Amor, M., & Fuentes, L. (2020). Energy-efficient Deployment of IoT Applications in Edge-based Infrastructures: A Software Product Line Approach. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*.
- [16] C. Marquez, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, and X. Costa-Perez, 'How Should I Slice My Network? A Multi-Service Empirical Evaluation of Resource Sharing Efficiency', presented at the ACM MobiCom, New Dehli, India, 2018, doi: 10.1145/3241539.3241567.
- [17] D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, X. Costa-Perez, 'DeepCog: Optimizing Resource Provisioning in Network Slicing with AI-based Capacity Forecasting', *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 38(2), Feb 2020.
- [18] D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, X. Costa-Perez, 'DeepCog: Cognitive Network Management in Sliced 5G Networks with Deep Learning', *IEEE INFOCOM 2019*, Paris, France, Apr 2019.
- [19] D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, X. Costa-Perez, 'AZTEC: Anticipatory Capacity Allocation for Zero-Touch Network Slicing', *IEEE INFOCOM 2020*, Online (previously Toronto, Canada), Jul 2020.
- [20] P. Vlachas, V. Stavroulaki, P. Demestichas, S. Cadzow, D. Ikononou and S. Gorniak, "Towards end-to-end network resilience," *Int. J. Crit. Infrastruct. Prot.*, 2013.
- [21] M. Ahmed, A. N. Mahmood and J. Hu, "A survey of network anomaly detection techniques," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 60, 2016.

- [22] V. Chandola, A. Banerjee and V. Kumar, "Anomaly detection: A survey," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 41, 2009.
- [23] M. Barreno, B. Nelson, A. D. Joseph and J. D. Tygar, "The security of machine learning," *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 81, 2010.
- [24] Z. C. Lipton, "The mythos of model interpretability," *Queue.*, vol. 16, 2018.
- [25] S. Raaijmakers, "Artificial Intelligence for Law Enforcement: Challenges and Opportunities," *IEEE Secur. Priv.*, vol. 17, 2019.
- [26] J. Silberg and J. Manyika, "Notes from the AI frontier: Tackling bias in AI (and in humans)," *McKinsey Glob. Inst.*, 2019.
- [27] ETSI GS NFV 002: "Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV); Architectural Framework" [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/nfv/001_099/002/01_01_01_60/gs_nfv002v010101p.pdf.
- [28] ETSI GS MEC 003: "Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC); Framework and Reference Architecture" (2020-12) [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/MEC/001_099/003/02_01_01_60/gs_MEC003v020101p.pdf.
- [29] ETSI GS NFV-MAN 001: "Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV); Management and Orchestration" [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-MAN/001_099/001/01_01_01_60/gs_NFV-MAN001v010101p.pdf
- [30] ETSI GS ENI 001: Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI) (2020-12); ENI use cases. [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/ENI/001_099/001/03_01_01_60/gs_ENI001v030101p.pdf
- [31] Eclipse Foundation, "From DevOps to EdgeOps: A Vision for Edge Computing", White Paper, April 2021. [Online] Available: <https://outreach.eclipse.foundation/edge-computing-edgeops-white-paper>
- [32] Framework to Conduct 5G Testing, Federal Mobility Group, Nov 2020. [Online] Available: <https://www.cio.gov/assets/files/Framework-to-Conduct-5G-Testing-508.pdf>.
- [33] Tremblay, J., Prakash, A., Acuna, D., Brophy, M., Jampani, V., Anil, C., To, T., Cameracci, E., Boochoon, S. and Birchfield, S., 2018. Training deep networks with synthetic data: Bridging the reality gap by domain randomization. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops* (pp. 969-977).
- [34] Seib, V., Lange, B. and Wirtz, S., 2020. Mixing Real and Synthetic Data to Enhance Neural Network Training--A Review of Current Approaches. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.08781*.
- [35] O-RAN Alliance, "O-RAN Working Group 2. AI/ML workflow description and requirements (O-RAN.WG2.AIML-v01.01)," Technical Report, 2020.
- [36] Bermolen P, Rossi D. Support vector regression for link load prediction. *Comput Netw.* 2009;53(2):191–201.
- [37] Chabaa S, Zeroual A, Antari J. Identification and prediction of internet traffic using artificial neural networks. *J Int Learn Syst Appl.* 2010;2(03):147.
- [38] Cortez P, Rio M, Rocha M, Sousa P. Internet traffic forecasting using neural networks. In: *Proceedings of IEEE International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*. IEEE; 2006. p. 2635–42.
- [39] Eswaradass A, Sun XH, Wu M. Network bandwidth predictor (nbp): A system for online network performance forecasting. In: *Proceedings of 6th IEEE International Symposium on Cluster Computing and the Grid (CCGRID)*. IEEE; 2006.
- [40] Zhu Y, Zhang G, Qiu J. Network traffic prediction based on particle swarm bp neural network. *JNW.* 2013;8(11):2685–91
- [41] Chen Z, Wen J, Geng Y. Predicting future traffic using hidden markov models. In: *Proceedings of 24th IEEE International Conference on Network Protocols (ICNP)*. IEEE; 2016. p. 1–6.
- [42] Li Y, Liu H, Yang W, Hu D, Xu W. Inter-data-center network traffic prediction with elephant flows: IEEE; 2016b, pp. 206-13.
- [43] Poupart P, Chen Z, Jaini P, Fung F, Susanto H, Geng Y, Chen L, Chen K, Jin H. Online flow size prediction for improved network routing. *IEEE*; 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [44] J. Wang et al., "Spatiotemporal modeling and prediction in cellular networks: A big data enabled deep learning approach," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Commun. (INFOCOM)*, Atlanta, GA, USA, May 2017, pp. 1–9.
- [45] Jin Y, Duffield N, Erman J, Haffner P, Sen S, Zhang ZL. A modular machine learning system for flow-level traffic classification in large networks. *ACM Trans Knowl Discov Data (TKDD)*. 2012;6(1):4.
- [46] Shbair WM, Cholez T, Francois J, Chriment I. A multi-level framework to identify https services. In: *IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS) 2016*. p. 240–8.
- [47] Nguyen TT, Armitage G, Branch P, Zander S. Timely and continuous machine-learning-based classification for interactive ip traffic. *IEEE/ACM Trans Netw (TON)*. 2012;20(6):1880–94.
- [48] G. Aceto, D. Ciunzo, A. Montieriet al., "Mobile encrypted traffic classification using deep learning: Experimental evaluation, lessons learned, and challenges," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 445–458, 2019.
- [49] Lotfollahi, M., Siavoshani, M. J., Zade, R. S. H., & Saberian, M. (2020). Deep packet: A novel approach for encrypted traffic classification using deep learning. *Soft Computing*, 24(3), 1999-2012.

- [50] X. Wang, S. Chen, and J. Su, "Real network traffic collection and deep learning for mobile app identification," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol. 2020, 2020.
- [51] K. Ismailaj, M. Camelo, S. Latré, "When Deep Learning May Not Be The Right Tool For Traffic Classification", Sixth IEEE/IFIP International Workshop on Analytics for Network and Service Management (AnNet 2021), to be published.
- [52] Liu, L., Cheng, Y., Cai, L., Zhou, S., & Niu, Z. (2017, May). Deep learning based optimization in wireless network. In 2017 IEEE international conference on communications (ICC) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [53] L. Qiu et al., "A general model of wireless interference," in *Proceedings of the 13th annual ACM international conference on Mobile computing and networking*, 2007, pp. 171-182.
- [54] R. Karmakare et al., "A deep probabilistic control machinery for auto-configuration of wifi link parameters," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 19, no. 12, pp. 8330-8340, 2020.
- [55] M. A. Khan et al., "Real-time throughput prediction for cognitive wi-fi networks," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 150, p.102499, 2020.
- [56] ITU-T Rec. Y.3172, "Architectural framework for machine learning in future networks including IMT-2020," 2019.
- [57] Wang Z, Zhang M, Wang D, Song C, Liu M, Li J, Lou L, Liu Z. Failure prediction using machine learning and time series in optical network. *Optics Express*. 2017;25(16):18,553-18,565.
- [58] Moustapha Al, Selmic RR. Wireless sensor network modeling using modified recurrent neural networks: Application to fault detection. *IEEE Trans Instrum Meas*. 2008;57(5):981-8.
- [59] Khanafer RM, Solana B, Triola J, Barco R, Moltsen L, Altman Z, Lazaro P. Automated diagnosis for umts networks using bayesian network approach. *IEEE Trans veh technol*. 2008;57(4):2451-61.
- [60] El Khayat I, Geurts P, Leduc G. Enhancement of tcp over wired/wireless networks with packet loss classifiers inferred by supervised learning. *Wirel Netw*. 2010;16(2):273-90.
- [61] Fonseca N, Crovella M. Bayesian packet loss detection for tcp. In: *Proceedings IEEE 24th Annual Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies.*, vol 3. 2005. p. 1826-37.
- [62] Yan Q, Lei Q. A new active queue management algorithm based on self-adaptive fuzzy neural-network pid controller. In: *2011 International Conference on, Internet Technology and Applications*; 2011. p. 1-4.
- [63] Jain A, Karandikar A, Verma R. An adaptive prediction based approach for congestion estimation in active queue management (apace). In: *Global Telecommunications Conference, 2003. GLOBECOM '03*. IEEE, vol. 7. Piscataway: IEEE; 2003. p. 4153-7.
- [64] Silva AP, Obraczka K, Burleigh S, Hirata CM. Smart congestion control for delay- and disruption tolerant networks. In: *2016 13th Annual IEEE International Conference on Sensing, Communication, and Networking (SECON)*. 2016. p. 1-9.
- [65] Mirza M, Sommers J, Barford P, Zhu X. A machine learning approach to tcp throughput prediction. *IEEE/ACM Trans Netw*. 2010;18(4):1026-39.
- [66] Jay, N., Rotman, N. H., Godfrey, P., Schapira, M., & Tamar, A. (2018). Internet congestion control via deep reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.03259*.
- [67] Xu, Z., Tang, J., Yin, C., Wang, Y., & Xue, G. (2019). Experience-driven congestion control: When multipath TCP meets deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 37(6), 1325-1336.
- [68] Zhang, T., & Mao, S. (2020). Machine learning for end-to-end congestion control. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 58(6), 52-57.
- [69] Li, W., Zhang, H., Gao, S., Xue, C., Wang, X., & Lu, S. (2019). SmartCC: A reinforcement learning approach for multipath TCP congestion control in heterogeneous networks. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 37(11), 2621-2633.
- [70] Mijumbi R, Gorricho JL, Serrat J, Claeys M, De Turck F, Latré S. Design and evaluation of learning algorithms for dynamic resource management in virtual networks. *IEEE*; 2014, pp. 1-9.
- [71] Mao, H., Alizadeh, M., Menache, I., & Kandula, S. (2016, November). Resource management with deep reinforcement learning. In *Proceedings of the 15th ACM workshop on hot topics in networks* (pp. 50-56).
- [72] Zeng, D., Gu, L., Pan, S., Cai, J., & Guo, S. (2019). Resource management at the network edge: A deep reinforcement learning approach. *IEEE Network*, 33(3), 26-33.
- [73] Adeel A, Larijani H, Javed A, Ahmadinia A. Critical analysis of learning algorithms in random neural network based cognitive engine for lte systems. In: *Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC Spring)*, 2015 IEEE 81st. IEEE; 2015. p. 1-5.
- [74] Mijumbi R, Hasija S, Davy S, Davy A, Jennings B, Boutaba R. A connectionist approach to dynamic resource management for virtualised network functions. In: *Network and Service Management (CNSM) 2016 12th International Conference on*. IEEE; 2016. p. 1-9.
- [75] Sun Y, Yin X, Jiang J, Sekar V, Lin F, Wang N, Liu T, Sinopoli B. Cs2p: Improving video bitrate selection and adaptation with data-driven throughput prediction. In: *Proceedings of the 2016 conference on ACM SIGCOMM 2016 Conference*. ACM; 2016. p. 272-85.

- [76] Mushtaq MS, Augustin B, Mellouk A. Empirical study based on machine learning approach to assess the qos/qoe correlation. In: Networks and Optical Communications (NOC), 2012 17th European Conference on. IEEE; 2012. p. 1–7.
- [77] Demirbilek E, Grégoire JC. Machine learning-based parametric audiovisual quality prediction models for real-time communications. *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing. Commun Appl (TOMM)*. 2017;13(2):16.
- [78] Vinayakumar, R., Alazab, M., Soman, K. P., Poornachandran, P., Al-Nemrat, A., & Venkatraman, S. (2019). Deep learning approach for intelligent intrusion detection system. *IEEE Access*, 7, 41525-41550.
- [79] Shone, N., Ngoc, T. N., Phai, V. D., & Shi, Q. (2018). A deep learning approach to network intrusion detection. *IEEE transactions on emerging topics in computational intelligence*, 2(1), 41-50.
- [80] Chalapathy, R., & Chawla, S. (2019). Deep learning for anomaly detection: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.03407*.
- [81] Du, M., Li, F., Zheng, G., & Srikumar, V. (2017, October). Deeplog: Anomaly detection and diagnosis from system logs through deep learning. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security* (pp. 1285-1298).
- [82] Wang, Y., Ye, Z., Wan, P., & Zhao, J. (2019). A survey of dynamic spectrum allocation based on reinforcement learning algorithms in cognitive radio networks. *Artificial intelligence review*, 51(3), 493-506.
- [83] Azmat, F., Chen, Y., & Stocks, N. (2015). Analysis of spectrum occupancy using machine learning algorithms. *IEEE transactions on vehicular technology*, 65(9), 6853-6860.
- [84] Z. Xu, Y. Wang, J. Tang, J. Wang, and M. C. Gursoy, "A deep reinforcement learning based framework for power-efficient resource allocation in cloud RANs," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Commun. (ICC)*, Paris, France, May 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [85] O. Naparstek and K. Cohen, "Deep multi-user reinforcement learning for distributed dynamic spectrum access," *eprint arXiv:1704.02613*, Apr. 2017.
- [86] Mendis, G. J., Wei, J., & Madanayake, A. (2016, December). Deep learning-based automated modulation classification for cognitive radio. In *2016 IEEE International Conference on Communication Systems (ICCS)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [87] S. Peng, H. Jiang, H. Wang, H. Alwageed, and Y.-D. Yao, "Modulation classification using convolutional neural network based deep learning model," in *Proc. 26th Wireless Opt. Commun. Conf. (WOCC)*, Newark, NJ, USA, Apr. 2017, pp. 1–5.
- [88] Meng, F., Chen, P., Wu, L., & Wang, X. (2018). Automatic modulation classification: A deep learning enabled approach. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 67(11), 10760-10772.
- [89] Ali, A., Yangyu, F., & Liu, S. (2017). Automatic modulation classification of digital modulation signals with stacked autoencoders. *Digital Signal Processing*, 71, 108-116.
- [90] Shahid, A., Fontaine, J., Camelo, M., Haxhibeqiri, J., Saelens, M., Khan, Z., ... & De Poorter, E. (2019, June). A convolutional neural network approach for classification of lpwan technologies: Sigfox, lora and ieee 802.15. 4g. In *2019 16th Annual IEEE International Conference on Sensing, Communication, and Networking (SECON)* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
- [91] M. Kulin, T. Kazaz, I. Moerman, and E. De Poorter, "End-to-end learning from spectrum data: A deep learning approach for wireless signal identification in spectrum monitoring applications," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 18 484–18 501, 2018.
- [92] N. Bitar, S. Muhammad, and H. H. Refai, "Wireless technology identification using deep convolutional neural networks," in *2017 IEEE 28th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor, and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [93] S. Yi, H. Wang, W. Xue, X. Fan, L. Wang, J. Tian, and R. Matsukura, "Interference source identification for ieee 802.15.4 wireless sensor networks using deep learning," in *2018 IEEE 29th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*, 2018, pp. 1–7.
- [94] Camelo, M., Shahid, A., Fontaine, J., de Figueiredo, F. A. P., De Poorter, E., Moerman, I., & Latre, S. (2019, November). A semi-supervised learning approach towards automatic wireless technology recognition. In *2019 IEEE International Symposium on Dynamic Spectrum Access Networks (DySPAN)* (pp. 1-10). IEEE.
- [95] Zhang, H., & Yan, J. (2015, September). Performance of SDN routing in comparison with legacy routing protocols. In *2015 International Conference on Cyber-Enabled Distributed Computing and Knowledge Discovery* (pp. 491-494). IEEE.
- [96] Gopi, D., Cheng, S., & Huck, R. (2017, July). Comparative analysis of SDN and conventional networks using routing protocols. In *2017 International Conference on Computer, Information and Telecommunication Systems (CITS)* (pp. 108-112). IEEE.
- [97] Caria, M., Jukan, A., & Hoffmann, M. (2016). SDN partitioning: A centralized control plane for distributed routing protocols. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 13(3), 381-393.
- [98] N. Kato et al., "The Deep Learning Vision for Heterogeneous Network Traffic Control: Proposal, Challenges, and Future Perspective," *IEEE Wireless Commun.*, vol. 24, no. 3, June 2017, pp. 146–53.

- [99] Yahyaoui, H., Aidi, S., & Zhani, M. F. (2020, January). On using flow classification to optimize traffic routing in SDN networks. In 2020 IEEE 17th Annual Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC) (pp. 1-6).
- [100] Valadarsky, A., Schapira, M., Shahaf, D., & Tamar, A. (2017). A machine learning approach to routing. arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.03074.
- [101] Troia, S., Rodriguez, A., Martín, I., Hernández, J. A., De Dios, O. G., Alvizu, R., ... & Maier, G. (2018, September). Machine-learning-assisted routing in SDN-based optical networks. In 2018 European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC) (pp. 1-3).
- [102] Rusek, K., Suárez-Varela, J., Almasan, P., Barlet-Ros, P., & Cabellos-Aparicio, A. (2020). RouteNet: Leveraging Graph Neural Networks for network modeling and optimization in SDN. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 38(10), 2260-2270.
- [103] Subramanya, T., & Riggio, R. (2019, June). Machine learning-driven scaling and placement of virtual network functions at the network edges. In 2019 IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft) (pp. 414-422).
- [104] Bunyakitanon, M., Vasilakos, X., Nejabati, R., & Simeonidou, D. (2020). End-to-End Performance-Based Autonomous VNF Placement With Adopted Reinforcement Learning. *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, 6(2), 534-547.
- [105] Manias, D. M., Jammal, M., Hawilo, H., Shami, A., Heidari, P., Larabi, A., & Brunner, R. (2019, December). Machine learning for performance-aware virtual network function placement. In 2019 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM) (pp. 1-6).
- [106] Duc, T. L., Leiva, R. G., Casari, P., & Östberg, P. O. (2019). Machine learning methods for reliable resource provisioning in edge-cloud computing: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 52(5), 1-39.
- [107] Pei, J., Hong, P., Pan, M., Liu, J., & Zhou, J. (2019). Optimal VNF placement via deep reinforcement learning in SDN/NFV-enabled networks. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 38(2), 263-278.
- [108] Kaloxylou, Alexandros, Gavras, Anastasios, Camps Mur, Daniel, Ghorashi, Mir, & Hrasnica, Halid. (2020, December 1). AI and ML – Enablers for Beyond 5G Networks. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4299895>.
- [109] ETSI GS MEC 009: Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC); General principles, patterns and common aspects of MEC Service APIs. [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/MEC/001_099/009/02.02.01_60/gs_MEC009v020201p.pdf.
- [110] ETSI White Paper No. 34. Artificial Intelligence and future directions for ETSI 1st edition – June 2020. [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/ETSIWhitePapers/etsi_wp34_Artificial_Intelligence_and_future_directions_for_ETSI.pdf.
- [111] ETSI DGR/NFV-IFA041 (Draft), "Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV); Release 4 Management and Orchestration; Report on enabling autonomous management in NFV-MANO; Autonomous mgmt in MANO", 2021. [Online] Available: https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/NFV/Open/Drafts/IFA041_Autonomous_mgmt_in_MANO/NFV-IFA041v0110.zip.
- [112] ETSI TS 123 501- 3GPP TS 23.501 version 16.6.0. [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/123500_123599/123501/16.06.00_60/ts_123501v160600p.pdf.
- [113] 3GPP TR23.791 Study of Enablers for Network Automation for 5G. [Online] Available: <https://www.tech-invite.com/3m23/tinv-3gpp-23-791.html>.
- [114] E. Pateromichelakis et al., "End-to-End Data Analytics Framework for 5G Architecture," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 40295-40312, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2902984.
- [115] ETSI TS 128 533 - 3GPP TS 28.533 version 15.0.0 5G: Management and orchestration- Architecture framework. [Online] Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/128500_128599/128533/15.00.00_60/ts_128533v150000p.pdf.
- [116] Engineering MLOps, Emmanuel Raj, Packt Publishing, April 2021.

9 Appendix A: NI Use Cases Functional Requirements

Figure 9-1 shows the top-level requirements of DAEMON that are represented tree-shaped. Each requirement is colored considering the risk assessment (1 to 5), and the KPIs addressed by each requirement are showed at the bottom of each box. We represent both the functional and non-functional requirements, which can be visually distinguished using a dotted or continuous line.

Figure 9-1. NI use cases functional requirements.

9.1 RIS control

Figure 9-2. RIS control requirements.

Table 9-1. FR-RIS-000 description.

FR-RIS-000																	
Description	DAEMON shall integrate Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces technology into mobile networks.																
Version	001M1																
Owner	NEC																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	There is a mild risk that the project will not be able to build a RIS prototype. Should this happen, the project will rely on simulations and mathematical models.																
Rationale	RIS technologies will play a key role in increasing the wireless network capacity of next-generation networks, reduce energy consumption, and create new privacy and security applications. However, optimal RIS operation can only be achieved in coordination with the radio access network controller. To this end, native support by DAEMON platform and open interfaces that integrate RIS controllers into the rest of the mobile network control ecosystem is required.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6	X	K7		K8		K9	
Parents	None																

Table 9-2. FR-RIS-001 description.

FR-RIS-001	
Description	RIS controller shall interact with the system orchestrator and radio controllers
Version	001M1
Owner	NEC
Priority	High

Risk	1																
Risk Description	No risk																
Rationale	An interface between the mobile network orchestrator, the gNB controllers, and the RIS controller shall enable joint optimization of gNBs, UEs and surfaces.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6	X	K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-RIS-000-001M1																

Table 9-3. FR-RIS-002 description.

FR-RIS-002																	
Description	RIS controller shall receive feedback about the wireless channel																
Version	002M4																
Owner	NEC																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	Channel feedback may not be received in a timely manner or with the required accuracy so as to be useful information.																
Rationale	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces modify the propagation properties of impinging wireless signals in a controllable manner. To this end, good estimations about the wireless environment based upon feedback from users and gNBs, i.e., channel information, are required to perform optimal RIS operation.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6	X	K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-RIS-000-001M1																

9.2 Multi-timescale edge resource management

Figure 9-3. Multi-timescale edge resource management requirements – Part I.

Figure 9-4. Multi-timescale edge resource management requirements – Part 2.

Table 9-4. FR-MTERM-000 description.

FR-MTERM-000																	
Description		DAEMON shall integrate NI solutions for resource management															
Version		002M4															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		3															
Risk Description		Given the wide range of solutions for resource management in the edge domain, the project might not be able to integrate them all. In case that happens, the project will try to integrate those solutions that are able to fulfil the most of the KPIs.															
Rationale		NI can improve the resource control problems of Fog and Edge environments, which are domains highly distributed and highly heterogeneous in nature.															
K1	X	K2	X	K3		K4	X	K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	X
Parents		None															

Table 9-5. FR-MTERM-001 description.

FR-MTERM-001																	
Description		DAEMON shall support decentralized and unified data management															
Version		001M1															
Owner		ADL															
Priority		High															
Risk		1															
Risk Description																	
Rationale		<p>The NI Multi-timescale Closed-loop AI Framework should provide a decentralized and unified data management to ease the development, operation, and management of any NI model.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unification of various data patterns in a single and harmonized platform supporting data in motion (i.e., pub/sub), data in use (i.e., caching), data at rest (i.e., storages), and on-demand computation (i.e., remote procedure calls). • Decentralization by design to support the very distributed nature of the edge and fog computing where resources and applications are expected to be more mobile and volatile compared to traditional cloud computing. • Heterogeneity by design to account for the great diversity of devices, resources, applications, and traffic/mobility patterns that are expected to coexist in the edge and fog infrastructure. • Eventually consistency to be more resilient to failures in the network and to guarantee that the overall system is brought to a halt in case of temporary inconsistencies (e.g., network partitioning). • Wire efficiency to reduce the overhead in the network and hence reduce the overall energy consumption of the system. • Data pipeline to support the staged processing of some data where multiple NI models may be chained together. 															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-000-002M4															

Table 9-6. FR-MTERM-002 description.

FR-MTERM-002	
Description	DAEMON shall provide NI-assisted management and orchestration framework with control-loop to meet service KPIs at the network edge
Version	001M1
Owner	IMEC

Priority	High																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	Due to the resource-constrained nature of edge environments, provisioning required resources (both computing and network) to all services in order to meet all their KPIs is a challenging task. Thus, we need to provide a risk assessment for all types of services running on the edge, and considering offloading to cloud for those services that are not latency constrained.																
Rationale	The NI-assisted management and orchestration framework needs to provide a closed-loop of monitoring, orchestration and configuration, in order to enable automated service re-configuration. The main goal of enabling dynamic and automated service re-configuration is meeting service KPIs that are specified in service requirements without any manual intervention, thereby providing a service with more computing and network resources, while at the same time, considering resource requirements of all other services (e.g., MEC applications, value-added services) including management and orchestration entities.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-000-002M4															

Table 9-7. FR-MTERM-003 description.

FR-MTERM-003																	
Description	DAEMON shall perform management and orchestration of resources and services in two tiers, i.e., edge and cloud, observing service dynamics in distributed edges in different timescales																
Version	001M1																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	High																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	The decisions made by Network Intelligent Functions (NIFs) distributed across the edge networks might be out of sync with the NI instances running in a centralized cloud orchestrator. We might need to assign the level of priority to decision-making entities in different tiers, and have a control loop that will track the effect of these decisions on the service KPIs.																
Rationale	<p>Services are deployed in a distributed fashion, due to the high mobility of users, and an uneven distribution of resources across the edge networks. Thus, a proper management and orchestration of these distributed services needs to be achieved. The network intelligence in the form of AI-based NI instances needs to be distributed to different tiers in the management and orchestration architecture in order to treat different service dynamics in coarse/fine granular timescale. The changes in network connectivity (i.e., network links and nodes) and resource availability should be monitored in a finer timescale than energy, which can be aggregated and monitored on the system level.</p> <p>Services: MEC application services (specific to use cases, i.e., vertical services), Value-added services (e.g., location services, Radio Network Information Service), traffic analyzers, NI instances, energy consumption analyzers, etc.</p> <p>Resources: CPU, memory, storage, and network</p>																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-000-002M4															

Table 9-8. FR-MTERM-003.00 description.

FR-MTERM-003.00																	
Description		DAEMON shall perform management and orchestration of resources and services at the network edge															
Version		002M4															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		3															
Risk Description		Risk description FR-MTERM-003															
Rationale		Rationale FR-MTERM-003															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-003-001M1															

Table 9-9. FR-MTERM-003.01 description.

FR-MTERM-003.01																	
Description		The DAEMON shall perform management and orchestration of resources and services in the cloud															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		3															
Risk Description		Risk description FR-MTERM-003															
Rationale		Rationale FR-MTERM-003															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-003-001M1															

Table 9-10. FR-MTERM-003.02 description.

FR-MTERM-003.02																
Description		DAEMON's NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall continuously perform multi-timescale monitoring of computing and network resources in all edges														
Version		001M1														
Owner		IMEC														
Priority		High														
Risk		1														
Risk Description		The amount of data that is being collected might burden the resource-constrained edge nodes. Thus, we need to assess the resource requirements of monitoring services that will be running along with other services on the edge platforms, and to perform a corresponding management of these services in order to produce meaningful and credible results.														
Rationale		The constant monitoring input of computing and network resources will feed the orchestration entities that perform orchestration operations, to control and provide an on-the-fly reconfiguration of deployed virtualized network functions, to migrate them, and to identify anomalies in service and/or framework operation. These metrics shall be monitored at different timescales, depending on the granularity required by the service consuming the data and the available resources at the edge.														

K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents			FR-MTERM-003-001M1														

Table 9-11. FR-MTERM-003.03 description.

FR-MTERM-003.03																	
Description		DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall continuously perform multi-timescale monitoring of data traffic and mobility pattern of users															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		The value-added services that collect and parse data from the network traffic and UE mobility, impose additional burden to the resource-constrained edge nodes. Thus, we need to assess the resource requirements of those services that will be running along with other services on the edge platforms, and to perform a corresponding management of these service in order to produce meaningful and credible results.															
Rationale		The constant monitoring input of data traffic and mobility pattern will provide input about the UEs to the orchestration entities that perform orchestration operations, to proactively deploy additional VNFs when and where needed, to migrate them, and to reconfigure existing VNFs to meet demands of all UEs in the system. These metrics shall be monitored at different timescales, depending on the granularity required by the service consuming the data and the available resources at the edge.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents			FR-MTERM-003-001M1														

Table 9-12. FR-MTERM-004 description.

FR-MTERM-004																	
Description		DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall continuously perform a multi-timescale monitoring of energy consumption of deployed applications and orchestration entities in all edge networks															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		3															
Risk Description		The energy consumption calculation of isolated services might be a complex task, while at the same time, an aggregated energy consumption per edge platform might severely affect accuracy of energy-aware NI instances. Furthermore, although those NI instances that manage energy consumption in the whole system run in cloud, they still need to have probes installed on the edges, and proper assessment of their energy consumption and resource requirements needs to be obtained.															
Rationale		The constant monitoring of energy consumption per service/per edge platform is needed to make an optimal decision on VNF placement and VNF migration from one edge to another. With such an energy consumption footprint in the whole system, cloud orchestrator can perform load balancing between edge platforms, and accordingly turn off certain NI instances and deployed services if energy consumption needs to be decreased.															
K1	X	K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	

Parents	FR-MTERM-003-001M1
----------------	------------------------------------

Table 9-13. FR-MTERM-005 description.

FR-MTERM-005																	
Description	DAEMON shall be able to assess performance of NI instances to facilitate their replacement/retraining by permanent monitoring.																
Version	001M1																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	High																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	The definition of the evaluation metrics that are used to assess performance of NI instances (i.e., to evaluate whether they are performing as expected or not) can be cumbersome, unclear, and ambiguous. Thus, it is possible that the designed NI instances will need to be self-managed to alleviate its management and orchestration by a central entity. This central entity performs management and orchestration of all NI instances within its scope, and since NI instances can run intrinsically diverse ML algorithms (e.g., different data types, different timescales of producing results, etc.), it can be difficult for the central entity to notice that NI instance performance is compromised. Moreover, the performance of NI instances deployed on the network edge might be affected by other services and applications (i.e., noisy neighbor problem), due to the resource constraints, which is complex to identify and properly solve.																
Rationale	Different Network Intelligent Functions (NIFs) are deployed in a distributed manner to help/assist the management and orchestration framework. Therefore, the output of such NI instances must be accurate in order to increase reliability. Thus, NI-assisted management and orchestration framework needs to provide feedback on the NI instances performance so higher-level decisions can be made (e.g., that the model can be updated or replaced).																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-003-001M1																

Table 9-14. FR-MTERM-006 description.

FR-MTERM-006																	
Description	DAEMON shall provide the value-added services, such as location service, and Radio Network Information Service (RNIS)																
Version	001M1																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	Different timescales of location services and RNIS need to be synchronized in order to generate credible and meaningful decisions in NI instances.																
Rationale	The location services and RNIS provide a valuable input for NI instances and orchestration and management tasks, as they generate statistics about the movement of UEs, and about the network infrastructure, thereby improving the efficiency of NI instance operations by providing sufficient training data.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-000-002M4																

Table 9-15. FR-MTERM-007 description.

FR-MTERM-007																	
Description		DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall provide on-the-fly reconfiguration of VNFs															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		The reconfiguration of VNFs in the service function chain might impose a risk of service unavailability during the reconfiguration.															
Rationale		Following the cloud-native service design, the service function chains consist of loosely-coupled VNFs that can be replaced and separately configured. Orchestration entities can make decisions to scale up/down/out/in any of these VNFs, and to replace the faulty ones, while maintaining the service continuity.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-006-001M1															

Table 9-16. FR-MTERM-007.00 description.

FR-MTERM-007.00																	
Description		DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall provide on-the-fly VNF scaling															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		The VNF scaling in the service function chain might impose a risk of service unavailability during the reconfiguration.															
Rationale		Rationale FR-MTERM-007															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-007-001M1															

Table 9-17. FR-MTERM-007.01 description.

FR-MTERM-007.01																	
Description		DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall provide on-the-fly update of VNFs															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		VNF update (e.g., change of VNF image or descriptor, IP address) in the service function chain may entail a risk of service unavailability during reconfiguration.															
Rationale		Following the cloud-native service design, the service function chains are consisted of loosely-coupled VNFs that can be replaced and separately configured. Orchestration entities can make decisions to update VNFs e.g., if an updated image or descriptor are needed.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-007-001M1															

Table 9-18. FR-MTERM-008 description.

FR-MTERM-008																	
Description		DAEMON shall provide basic data learning, and feature analysis functionalities to evaluate the performance of deployed applications.															
Version		002M4															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		Low															
Risk		1															
Risk Description		Applications are normally designed by service providers. As orchestrator, DAEMON shall trust service providers to not deploy faulty applications in production. However, due to different situations (version update, component upgrade, hardware mismatch, among others) an application might become faulty.															
Rationale		DAEMON should be able to determine if the running service(s) are healthy or if a component of the service(s) is faulty and needs to be replaced or restarted. Also, if the component is being a bottleneck for the service(s) and needs to be migrated to a more performant machine or closer to the user.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4	X	K5	X	K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-006-001M1															

Table 9-19. FR-MTERM-009 description.

FR-MTERM-009																	
Description		DAEMON shall measure resource footprint of cloud and edge orchestration tiers in NI-assisted management and orchestration framework															
Version		002M4															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		1															
Risk Description		The resource-greedy NI instances might consume a significant amount of computing and network resources that are needed for proper operation of UE services, which leads to service disruption and insufficient level of promised KPIs.															
Rationale		As long as NI instances and management and orchestration entities are deployed along with UE services, the consideration of the resource footprint of both orchestration layers, considering the resource and network requirements for optimal operation of these orchestration entities is extremely important, with specific focus on the edge-level orchestration layer that runs on the resource-constrained edge clouds.															
K1	X	K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-006-001M1															

Table 9-20. FR-MTERM-010 description.

FR-MTERM-010													
Description		DAEMON shall make an optimal decision on using the communication framework for sharing information between monitoring systems and NI-assisted management and orchestration framework											
Version		001M1											
Owner		IMEC											

Priority	High																
Risk	1																
Risk Description	Additional benchmarking of communication systems (e.g., message broker) that will be used for sharing information between framework entities is needed, and different systems might be suitable for different types of applications.																
Rationale	As communication systems/platforms enable either synchronous or asynchronous communication between different orchestration components and NI instances, it is important to consider the complexity of using and managing the communication system (e.g., RabbitMQ is a simple and often used in most of the existing MANO solutions) for pub/sub purposes, but also the additional latency this entity involves in the communication (e.g., RabbitMQ inevitably generates additional latency because of message queuing on a central node, comparing to ZeroMQ).																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-000-002M4																

Table 9-21. FR-MTERM-011 description.

FR-MTERM-011																	
Description	DAEMON shall provide openness of interfaces between orchestration tiers to mitigate the dependence on specific network operators/vendors/infrastructure providers/service providers																
Version	001M1																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	High																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	The vulnerability of open interfaces between management and orchestration tiers, and between NI instances, might impose certain security risks that need to be properly handled.																
Rationale	Distributed edge networks and cloud can be deployed by different vendors/infrastructure providers, belonging to different Mobile Network Operator (MNO) domains. Thus, it is utmost important to provide open interfaces between NI instances and management and orchestration tiers (i.e., edge and cloud) in order to facilitate orchestration operations, and to mitigate the dependence on the vendor-specific configuration of NI instances.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-010-001M1																

Table 9-22. FR-MTERM-012 description.

FR-MTERM-012																
Description	DAEMON shall provide support for multiple virtualization environments for deploying services/applications in distributed edge clouds															
Version	001M1															
Owner	IMEC															
Priority	High															
Risk	1															
Risk Description	The diversity in virtualization environments needs specific maintenance, and virtualization-specific policies for orchestration operations, which significantly increases complexity of orchestration operations in both tiers within NI-assisted management and orchestration framework.															

Rationale		With regards to the limited resource availability within the edge platforms, comparing to the large and resourceful data-center, the lightweight virtualization, and orchestration solutions for small-size programmable devices are required. Thus, containerization proves to be the suitable candidate to deliver a lightweight deployment of services and applications suitable for network edge deployments.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-010-001M1															

Table 9-23. FR-MTERM-013 description.

FR-MTERM-013																	
Description		DAEMON shall provide support for federated multi-domain management and orchestration															
Version		002M4															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		Medium															
Risk		3															
Risk Description		Management level agreements are necessary for establishing collaboration between orchestration and management entities, and NI instances in different edge domains.															
Rationale		Due to the high mobility of users in 5G and beyond 5G ecosystems, applications are deployed in distributed way across different edge platforms. Thus, NI-assisted management and orchestration framework needs to support cross-domain/cross-edge service orchestration for achieving seamless service operation.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-010-001M1															

Table 9-24. FR-MTERM-014 description.

FR-MTERM-014																	
Description		DAEMON shall use third-party systems or define its own system for data handling.															
Version		002M4															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		Medium															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		Besides managing the lifecycle of different NI instances, the burden of managing data can be too big as it involves a multiplicity of data sources and data types. Therefore, a framework for data management might be useful.															
Rationale		DAEMON will require to gather data from multiple data-sources (e.g., end-users, edge orchestrators, radio resource managers, applications, infrastructure) to i) directly feed NI instances that perform online learning or ii) build datasets using historical data on which the NI instances will be offline trained. Additionally, the data should be normalized or unified so it can be reused by multiple NI instances.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-010-001M1															

Table 9-25. FR-MTERM-014.00 description.

FR-MTERM-014.00																	
Description		DAEMON shall gather data from multiple data-sources															

Version	002M4																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	1																
Risk Description	To make system wide decisions with a sufficient level of accuracy, DAEMON will consume data from different domains. Given the limitations of possible DAEMON implementation (PoC, Simulations), it is possible that the diversity of the collected data might not be significant as expected.																
Rationale	The data from multiple data-sources, such as: end-users, edge orchestrators, radio resource managers, applications, infrastructure, is needed to feed NI instances.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	X
Parents	FR-MTERM-014-002M4																

Table 9-26. FR-MTERM-015 description.

FR-MTERM-015																	
Description	DAEMON shall provide the interfaces with the NI-assisted management and orchestration framework to trigger the execution/termination of NI instances																
Version	002M4																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	When to execute/terminate a NI instance is a tunable parameter that highly depends on the context and the location where that NI instance is deployed. Moreover, a NI instance can be using data for training or for making inference, and in both cases the data handling can change. Therefore, DAEMON needs a way to differentiate either operation modes, when a NI instance starts or stops training or testing.																
Rationale	The NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall be able to trigger the training of different NI instances that help it to achieve different goals (e.g., network and computing optimizations, energy consumption). The NI instances remain active for the time that the NI-assisted management and orchestration framework consider necessary. Therefore, a communication interface between DAEMON and the NI-assisted management and orchestration framework needs to be enabled.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-010-001M1																

Table 9-27. FR-MTERM-015.00 description.

FR-MTERM-015.00																	
Description	DAEMON shall enable execution of NI instances																
Version	002M4																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	Risk description FR-MTERM-015																
Rationale	Rationale FR-MTERM-015																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-015-002M4																

Table 9-28. FR-MTERM-015.01 description.

FR-MTERM-015.01																	
Description		DAEMON shall enable termination of NI instances															
Version		002M14															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		Risk description FR-MTERM-15															
Rationale		Rationale FR-MTERM-015															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-015-002M4															

Table 9-29. FR-MTERM-016 description.

FR-MTERM-016																	
Description		DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall be able to enforce NI instances' outcomes.															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		3															
Risk Description		There are two risks in enforcing NI instances' outcome, i) that the NI instances' outcome is not appropriately translated into an action that the management and orchestration framework is able to understand, and ii) that outcomes of different NI instances produce contradictory policies/actions.															
Rationale		The outcomes that are produced by NI instances need to be translated into decisions, policies, and/or actions that will guide and support the NI-assisted management and orchestration framework.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-000-002M4															

Table 9-30. FR-MTERM-017 description.

FR-MTERM-017																
Description		DAEMON shall provide synchronization between decision making processes with different timescales between two management and orchestration tiers in NI-assisted framework														
Version		001M1														
Owner		IMEC														
Priority		High														
Risk		3														
Risk Description		The complexity of the control loop between NI instances is increasing with the number of NI instances running in both edge and cloud, thereby significantly increasing the risk of conflicts and imposing additional delay in selecting the more convenient decision among the ones that are in conflict.														
Rationale		Both management and orchestration tiers in the NI-assisted framework can simultaneously make decisions on VNF placement and migration (e.g., edge orchestrator requesting to migrate VNFs from its edge domain to another due to the lack of computing resources, while cloud orchestrator refuses to migrate them due to the energy saving in other edges). Thus, the control loop between NI														

		instances running in different tiers needs to be achieved, with the defined policies on how to proceed in conflicting situations, with conflicting decisions.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	X
Parents		FR-MTERM-016-001M1															

Table 9-31. FR-MTERM-018 description.

FR-MTERM-018																	
Description		DAEMON shall be able to perform policy/action/decision conflict resolution to guarantee the stability of the assisted system.															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		3															
Risk Description		To determine which action/policy/decision has priority on optimizing a given function is not trivial and it depends on multiple factors that need to be evaluated. Therefore, the initial selection of policies/actions/decisions is highly coupled with the use case.															
Rationale		Optimizations will take place in different domains of the assisted system. Therefore, the decisions/policies/actions that are taken to optimize a certain objective function (e.g., business goal, SLAs) can be counterproductive to other policies/decisions/actions. Thus, a conflict resolution system is needed that can guarantee that the system is evolving towards a stable state.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	X
Parents		FR-MTERM-016-001M1															

Table 9-32. FR-MTERM-019 description.

FR-MTERM-019																	
Description		DAEMON shall select the NI instance running at the edge according to the system constraints (energy, computation, network, KPIs)															
Version		002M4															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		It is possible that the available NI instances do not address the system constraints. In this case, NI instances that try to fulfil system constraints as close as possible will be selected.															
Rationale		Depending on the available resources and the business goals or SLAs, DAEMON will select the best NI instance model that suits the assisted system. For example, in some cases it might be feasible to sacrifice accuracy at the expenses of a lower computational complexity.															
K1	X	K2	X	K3		K4	X	K5	X	K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-016-001M1															

9.3 In-backhaul support for service intelligence

Figure 9-5. IBSSI functional requirements.

Table 9-33. FR-IBSSI-000 description.

FR-IBSSI-000																	
Description	DAEMON shall learn network policies using the data-plane itself																
Version	002M4																
Owner	UC3M																
Priority	Low																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	To ensure fast reaction times for orchestration mechanisms upon network changes, the network shall learn directly from data-plane network functions, providing triggers for the required re-orchestrations.																
Rationale	Besides monitoring of KPIs, the network shall already understand and detect malfunctioning already from the analysis of specific traffic patterns or control-plane interactions. This is especially important for operations such as anomaly detection.																
K1		K2		K3	X	K4		K5		K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents	None																

Table 9-34. FR-IBSSI-001 description.

FR-IBSSI-001																	
Description	DAEMON shall provide Intelligence-as-a-Service to vertical 3rd parties																
Version	002M4																
Owner	UC3M																
Priority	High																
Risk	4																
Risk Description	Third parties will be allowed to be included in the network operation through specific APIs that are used to i) manage the kind of provided intelligence and ii) ensure that the resources are provided to them.																
Rationale	DAEMON will provide algorithms for the execution of network intelligence directly related to the vertical service (e.g., video analytics directly in the u-plane) and allow the efficient and secure resource provisioning through the usage of solutions based on e.g., distributed ledger platform.																
K1		K2		K3	X	K4		K5		K6		K7		K8	X	K9	
Parents	FR-IBSSI-000-002M4																

Table 9-35. FR-IBSSI-002 description.

FR-IBSSI-002																	
Description		DAEMON shall integrate Network Intelligence within programmable switches															
Version		001M3															
Owner		IMDEA															
Priority		Low															
Risk		4															
Risk Description		Programmable switches have extremely limited computational capabilities and memory, which constrains substantially what they can do in terms of learning.															
Rationale		Programmable user planes are starting to be leveraged for network telemetry functionalities. However, these are limited to data collection and pre-processing, which are then fed to NI located in the control plane in order to take network management decisions. DAEMON will investigate what portion of the decision process can be moved to the switches directly, at line rate and avoiding the delay of interacting with the control plane.															
K1		K2		K3	X	K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-IBSSI-000-002M4															

9.4 Compute-aware radio scheduling

Figure 9-6. CAWRS non-functional requirements.

Table 9-36. FR-CAWRS-000 description.

FR-CAWRS-000																	
Description		DAEMON shall integrate NI solution in vRAN systems															
Version		001M3															
Owner		UC3M															
Priority		High															
Risk		1															
Risk Description		There is a low risk that DAEMON will not integrate NI solutions into vRAN systems, as DAEMON partners were already capable of integrating such kind of solutions in Open Source vRAN environments.															
Rationale		The mobile network industry is moving towards virtual network function solutions, and RAN Functions are not an exception. Being among the most resource consuming functions (in terms of computation), thus allowing the re-design of such function by taking into account the computing resource optimization as further objective will improve the overall spending (both CAPEX and OPEX, for the resource provisioning) for the network operation.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		None															

Table 9-37. NFR-CAWRS-000 description.

NFR-CAWRS-000																	
Description		NI orchestration solutions for vRAN shall have reaction times below 10s															
Version		001M1															
Owner		UC3M															
Priority		High															
Risk		1															
Risk Description		There is a low risk that DAEMON will not integrate succeed to provide such timings for the NI-based network orchestration. In preliminary works, DAEMON partners were able to achieve computing resources orchestration within a 10s constraint. This constraint may be lowered with the usage of more complex orchestration solutions.															
Rationale		In Invalid source specified. , DAEMON authors were able to orchestrate computing resources for vRAN by using the Docker API, with a 10 seconds granularity. This value is already enough to bring down the computing resource usage by more than 30% in some scenario. By using directly the cgroups API offered by the Linux system, we may achieve even lower values.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-CAWRS-000-001M3															

Table 9-38. NFR-CAWRS-001 description.

NFR-CAWRS-001																
Description		NI control solutions for vRAN shall have reaction times below 100ms														
Version		001M1														
Owner		UC3M														
Priority		High														
Risk		2														
Risk Description		There is a mild risk that NI cannot achieve sub-second timings for the vRAN control algorithms such as the radio scheduling (which needs 1ms timings). If these timings cannot be achieved, DAEMON partners will use solutions such as slower scheduling patterns, enforced every 50-100 TTIs														
Rationale		Ideally, scheduling decisions are taken every TTIs, thus in the ms range scale. This requirement is quite stringent and may require specialized hardware such as GPUs deployed at the edge if deep learning solutions shall be put in place. Alternatives could be the usage of mixed models between machine learning and traditional optimization														
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9
Parents		FR-CAWRS-000-001M3														

Table 9-39. NFR-CAWRS-002 description.

NFR-CAWRS-002																
Description		NI solutions for vRAN shall achieve a bounded wireless performance wrt the optimal														
Version		001M1														
Owner		UC3M														
Priority		High														
Risk		2														
Risk Description		There is a mild risk that NI cannot achieve bounded performance for the wireless performance (i.e., spectrum efficiency, leading to bandwidth and latency figures). In this case, specific boundaries to the achievable computing resource saving will be defined.														
Rationale		With unbounded computing resource savings, the spectral efficiency may be unacceptably low. In Invalid source specified. , DAEMON partners were capable of achieving very good tradeoffs between the achievable savings and the pure performance, by correctly understanding the traffic patterns. Other solutions may have to be designed to guarantee that this tradeoff (the ratio between the best possible performance without computing resource optimization and the one obtained by DAEMON solutions never falls below certain thresholds).														
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9
Parents		FR-CAWRS-000-001M3														

9.5 Energy-aware VNF placement

Figure 9-7. EAWVNF functional and non-functional requirements.

Table 9-40. FR-EAWVNF-000 description.

FR-EAWVNF-000																	
Description	DAEMON shall profile the energy footprint of those network tasks that influence the network global power consumption.																
Version	001M1																
Owner	UMA																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	The reliability of the measurement depends on a complete identification of the external factors that affect the energy footprint (e.g., temperature, processor, or noisy neighbor problem), the accuracy of the energy measurement methods used, and the dependency on specific hardware. We should be able to estimate the energy consumption of VNFs both in simulated and real environments, obtaining possibly similar results.																
Rationale																	
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	None																

Table 9-41. FR-EAWVNF-001 description.

FR-EAWVNF-001																	
Description	DAEMON shall measure the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of CPU usage and communication traffic.																
Version	001M2																
Owner	UMA																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	The reliability of the measurement depends on the ability to identify and quantify the influence of external factors in the energy consumption calculation (e.g., noisy neighbor problem or distance to base station). Calculating the cost of executing code and transmitting and receiving information on specific hardware accurately is a complex task. It is possible to mitigate this risk by going through calculating an upper bound of its energy footprint.																
Rationale	The main factors that influence the energy consumption are the CPU usage and the data sent and received by a given VNF. We need to identify what are the factors that should be considered in the formula that calculates the total energy footprint of the network, in terms of computation and communication. We should consider not only the internal factors, as we said, computation and communication, but also the external ones, such as the neighboring traffic. Since our main goal is not to report absolute energy footprint values, but relative ones, we need to find a sound method to quantify the revenue of placing a VNF in one or another location in terms of power saving.																
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-EAWVNF-000-001M1																

Table 9-42. FR-EAWVNF-001.00 description.

FR-EAWVNF-001.00	
Description	DAEMON shall measure the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of CPU usage.
Version	001M2
Owner	UMA
Priority	High
Risk	2
Risk Description	Calculating the cost of executing any kind of code, on specific hardware accurately is a complex task, since there are several factors that we need to quantify in order to calculate the energy footprint. The theoretical values given by CPU providers usually do not coincide with the real ones.

Rationale		We need to identify what are the factors that should be considered in the formula that calculates the global energy footprint of the VNFs instantiated for each application, in terms of computation. We know that the processor type of the device where a VNFs is running influences the energy footprint, but there are also other parameters that make the software provoke the hardware to consume more energy, like the size of VNF input.															
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-EAWVNF-001-001M2															

Table 9-43. FR-EAWVNF-001.01 description.

FR-EAWVNF-001.01																	
Description		DAEMON shall measure the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of data transmission															
Version		001M2															
Owner		UMA															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		Calculating the cost of data transmission over different types of network links, accurately is a complex task, since there are several factors that we need to quantify in order to calculate the energy footprint. The network throughput is something that varies a lot and depends on some external factors like the current traffic or transmitting neighboring devices.															
Rationale		In the energy footprint calculation, we need to consider that some VNFs will produce some data that might need to be transmitted to other devices. We know that the transmission power, the payload and the transmission rate should be considered, along with other terms.															
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-EAWVNF-001-001M2															

Table 9-44. FR-EAWVNF-002 description.

FR-EAWVNF-002																	
Description		DAEMON shall measure the impact of hardware resources usage by VNFs in the calculation of the energy footprint															
Version		001M2															
Owner		UMA															
Priority		Low															
Risk		4															
Risk Description		The accuracy of the energy consumption measurement depends on specific hardware, including not only the computing device processor. Other hardware, such as memory use or access to HDD, could also influence the total energy footprint, but it is difficult to assess in which percentage. So, it is not easy to estimate it accurately.															
Rationale		Measuring the hardware resources usage of VNFs and their energy footprint provides extra information to accurately estimate the overall energy footprint of a VNF. We are seeking to find additional factors to the energy consumption formula, to calculate more precisely the network energy footprint. Although the DAEMON approach does not need absolute values of energy consumption, we need to find out if there are certain situations where the excessive use of additional resources by a certain VNF, strongly impact the decision of, for example, migrating it to another location.															
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-EAWVNF-000-001M1															

Table 9-45. FR-EAWVNF-003 description.

FR-EAWVNF-003																	
Description		DAEMON shall measure the energy footprint of VNFs migration.															
Version		001M2															

Owner	UMA															
Priority	High															
Risk	4															
Risk Description	The cost in terms of energy consumption of code migration in general, and in particular considering VNFs, depends on several factors that we need to identify. Also, there are different mechanisms to perform code migration and each of them requires a different formula for energy footprint calculation, affecting the accuracy of the final result.															
Rationale	The migration of a certain VNF has an energy cost that should be analyzed. It is essential to understand this energy cost to prioritize migrations to other systems if needed.															
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9
Parents	FR-EAWVNF-000-001M1															

Table 9-46. FR-EAWVNF-003.00 description.

FR-EAWVNF-003.00																
Description	DAEMON shall measure the energy footprint of VNF migration due to virtualization cost.															
Version	001M2															
Owner	UMA															
Priority	High															
Risk	3															
Risk Description	The main risk is that we do not consider all the factors relative to virtualization that affect the energy consumption of migrating a certain VNF. Another risk is that, even when we find a formula to calculate this energy footprint for a certain virtualization technology (or a few of them), later new technologies may appear.															
Rationale	The virtualization has an energy cost and should be analyzed. We should find out if this cost depends on the device (mainly Edge devices and Cloud), and how we can calculate it for both simulated and real environments. It is essential to understand this energy cost to prioritize migrations to other systems if needed. Also, we need to choose the list of virtual machines we are going to consider in this requirement.															
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9
Parents	FR-EAWVNF-003-001M2															

Table 9-47. FR-EAWVNF-003.01 description.

FR-EAWVNF-003.01																
Description	DAEMON shall measure the energy footprint of VNF migration due to transmission cost.															
Version	001M2															
Owner	UMA															
Priority	High															
Risk	4															
Risk Description	The main risk is that we do not consider all the factors relative to virtualization that affect the energy consumption of migrating a certain VNF. Another risk is that, even when we find out a formula to calculate this energy footprint for a certain virtualization technology (or a few of them), later new technologies appear.															
Rationale	The main factors that affect the energy footprint of VNF migration are the code and data transmission. There are different mechanisms to move a VNF to a different location and each one implies to transfer more or less data. So, the code migration mechanism strongly influences the energy footprint since it varies the amount of information to be transmitted. We should find out how we can calculate it for both simulated and real environments. It is essential to understand this energy cost to prioritize migrations to other systems if needed. If possible, we need to have a single migration mechanism to calculate its energy footprint.															
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9
Parents	FR-EAWVNF-003-001M2															

Table 9-48. FR-EAWVNF-004 description.

FR-EAWVNF-004															
Description		DAEMON shall consider how the context of the location of VNFs affects the energy footprint of VNFs.													
Version		001M3													
Owner		UMA													
Priority		High													
Risk		4													
Risk Description		The main risk is to do not model the context properly due to external and non-measurable artifacts. Moreover, DAEMON could not capture all the possible scenarios related within the location context to model the data's location to feed													
Rationale		The VNF placement cost in terms of energy footprint should consider the execution context where a VNF will be running, and the location of the data that will feed this function. The goal is to adapt the energy footprint of the needed VNFs to the context of the location where they are running.													
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8	K9
Parents		FR-EAWVNF-000-001M1													

Table 9-49. FR-EAWVNF-004.00 description.

FR-EAWVNF-004.00															
Description		DAEMON should define an energy profile with the dependency relationships of the different possible locations of VNFs.													
Version		001M3													
Owner		UMA													
Priority		High													
Risk		4													
Risk Description		One possible risk is that we cannot capture all the possible scenarios related with the location context. The variability of execution location contexts and their relationship with the energy footprint could be so high that it is not possible to consider all the cases in the AI algorithms that compute the best solution to deploy a set of VNFs.													
Rationale		To compute the energy footprint of a VNF we need to consider the energy cost depending on the location of the input data, and also the context of the execution location. One possible context could be the quality of the energy consumed, if it is green and renewable energy or polluting energy.													
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8	K9
Parents		FR-EAWVNF-004-001M3													

Table 9-50. FR-EAWVNF-004.01 description.

FR-EAWVNF-004.01															
Description		DAEMON should characterize the different variants of VNFs regarding to the context of the location where the VNF will be running.													
Version		001M3													
Owner		UMA													
Priority		High													
Risk		5													
Risk Description		Sometimes the proposed solutions for energy saving cost about the same or sometimes even more than applying a non-energy aware policy. So, we need to assess the cost of computing NI solutions in terms of energy, by adding this cost to the global energy footprint of the solution proposed by DAEMON.													
Rationale		The energy footprint of a VNF could depend on the energy cost of getting the input information depending on the location of the input data. Sometimes, the best solution could be to migrate the VNFs, but other times DAEMON could propose to adapt VNFs so that we can instantiate the most energy efficient version.													
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8	K9
Parents		FR-EAWVNF-004-001M3													

9.6 Self-learning MANO

Figure 9-8. SLMANO functional and non-functional requirements.

Table 9-51. FR-SLMANO-000 description.

FR-SLMANO-000	
Description	DAEMON shall design autonomous and self-learning orchestrators and controllers that can operate with minimal human intervention.
Version	001M2
Owner	NBL
Priority	High
Risk	2

Risk Description	The main risk is that the behavior of system that the orchestrator and controllers need to govern fluctuate too fast or have a too large stochastic component to them, so that it may be hard to find a suitable learning rate or exploitation versus exploration balance can be identified. Moreover, the behavior of the system can change suddenly (when, e.g., new software is installed on some of the components, which makes the previously learned policy outdated. Therefore, a system is needed to detect when learned information becomes stale.																
Rationale	Any decision that the orchestration and control functions can be envisioned to be automatized in the following way. First, the software agent taking the decisions needs to be provided (in a timely way) with the data necessary to take its decisions. With each action taken (given the provided data) the agent is provided with feedback that expresses how good that action was given the current data. Based on this feedback the agent can change its policy to steer the system in the desired direction.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents			None.														

Table 9-52. FR-SLMANO-001 description.

FR-SLMANO-001																	
Description	DAEMON controllers and orchestrators should be steered by high-level QoE targets and business KPIs (high level intents), rather than strict QoS goals and technical KPIs.																
Version	002M4																
Owner	NBL																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	The problem may be that it may be difficult to describe expected behavior in a concise way.																
Rationale	Application developers should have an easy way of specifying intended behavior based on their application level knowledge and requirements to guarantee QoE for their users.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents			FR-SLMANO-000-001M2														

Table 9-53. FR-SLMANO-002 description.

FR-SLMANO-002																	
Description	DAEMON controllers and orchestrators should support diverse intent based objective combinations provided by application developers, in terms of high-level application properties (possibly unknown at design time).																
Version	001M2																
Owner	NBL																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	Can a single algorithm fulfil this requirement? Will it be too complex? Is it better to train multiple competing algorithms for each specific use case and select the best performing?																
Rationale	Business KPIs will change frequently due to highly varying markets. The algorithms provided by DAEMON need to be flexible enough to self-learn and converge to sufficiently optimized behavior to avoid human intervention for retuning or redesigning the algorithms and mechanisms.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents			FR-SLMANO-000-001M2														

Table 9-54. FR-SLMANO-003 description.

FR-SLMANO-003																
Description	DAEMON controllers and orchestrators should self-converge to stable control loops.															

Version	001M2																
Owner	NBL																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	Can we capture realistic dynamic behavior in the systems, emulators or simulators that we will use? How can stability be verified?																
Rationale	<p>Different parts of the system will have different dynamics, potentially changing over time due to SW and HW upgrades. The algorithms provided by DAEMON need to be intelligent enough to self-learn and converge to a stable though responsive behavior to avoid human intervention for retuning or redesigning the algorithms and mechanisms.</p> <p>In general, a system operating in steady state is stable if after a infinitesimally short, small enough perturbation applied to it dies out exponentially fast so that it returns to that steady state working point. The perturbation needs to be short compared to the reaction time inherent to the system and small so that it does not jump to another working point.</p>																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-SLMANO-000-001M2																

Table 9-55. FR-SLMANO-004 description.

FR-SLMANO-004																	
Description	DAEMON controllers and orchestrators should be trustworthy and explainable, where decisions can be traced back to the key intents that have driven a specific action.																
Version	002M4																
Owner	NBL																
Priority	Low																
Risk	5																
Risk Description	Often ML tools are black boxes that after training work well, but do not give a clue of why they work. Network operators might distrust such tools and hence, be reluctant to use them. Moreover, when decisions are taken at multiple layers at different timescales, conflicts may arise amongst agents operating at different timescales (possibly due to a human error when setting the goals).																
Rationale	In a complex composition of multi-layer controllers, conflicts between different levels of intents need to be visualized, such that unexpected unwanted behavior can be analyzed and revised in terms of the active and potentially erroneously specified intents (due to human errors).																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-SLMANO-000-001M2																

Table 9-56. FR-SLMANO-005 description.

FR-SLMANO-005																	
Description	DAEMON controllers and orchestrators should be able to report that the systems they control behave unexpected, indicating possible need for retraining to cope with unseen or changed dynamics.																
Version	001M2																
Owner	NBL																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	There is a risk that spurious changes are seen by the system as changes in the environment, causing the system to retrain (doing a lot of exploration and making the associated wrong decisions) where it is not needed.																
Rationale	If online retraining is prohibited, or if the algorithms are incapable of self-converging to a sufficient solution, the need for human intervention needs to be reported.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-SLMANO-000-001M2																

Table 9-57. FR-SLMANO-006 description.

FR-SLMANO-006																	
Description		DAEMON shall implement mechanisms to detect when learned information becomes stale.															
Version		001M2															
Owner		NBL															
Priority		High															
Risk		2															
Risk Description		The behavior of the system can change suddenly (when, e.g., a flash crowd arrives generating a lot of traffic, when new software is installed on some of the components, when there is an outage of part of the infrastructure), which makes that the policy learned on past system behavior is n longer applicable. Therefore, a system is needed to detect when learned information becomes stale indicating when retraining is required.															
Rationale		In the framework defined under FR-SLMANO-000-001M2, where the software agent taking the decisions is provided (in a timely way) with the data necessary to take its decisions and where with each action taken (given the provided data), the agent is provided with feedback that expresses how good that action was, a change in behavior can be detected by observing the evolution of the feedback. If there is a drastic change, the balance between exploration and exploitation needs to be tilted in favor of exploration so that the system can be retrained to work properly in the new environment.															
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents		FR-SLMANO-000-001M2															

9.7 Capacity forecasting

Figure 9-9. CFORE functional and non-functional requirements.

Table 9-58. FR-CFORE-000 description.

FR-CFORE-000																	
Description	DAEMON shall design capacity forecast models that can support Network Intelligence (NI) algorithms across the mobile network architecture																
Version	001M2																
Owner	IMDEA																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	The main risk is that the forecasting models do not achieve the accuracy needed to support efficient decision-making, hence limiting the effectiveness of NI.																
Rationale	Many decisions to be taken by orchestrators and controllers deployed across different micro-domains of the mobile network must be taken in anticipatory manner, i.e., proactively with respect to the actual demand or requirements. Such decisions concern the capacity that orchestrators and controllers shall allocate in their micro-domain of competence. Predicting such capacity is thus a key enabler for the NI operating across the whole network.																
K1		K2		K3		K4	X	K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	None																

Table 9-59. FR-CFORE-001 description.

FR-CFORE-001	
Description	DAEMON capacity forecast models shall operate at very different timescales

Version	001M2																
Owner	IMDEA																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	The risk of insufficient accuracy in the prediction is exacerbated in as timescales become faster, as traffic demands are increasingly bursty, and the changes in requirements more and more rapid.																
Rationale	Orchestrators and controllers operate at very different timescales across the diverse network domains, and take decisions over intervals that range from hours to seconds or less depending on the nature of the concerned resources (e.g., computing resources, transport capacity, spectrum, etc.). Capacity forecasting models must be adapted to such diverse settings.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4	X	K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-CFORE-000-001M2																

Table 9-60. FR-CFORE-002 description.

FR-CFORE-002																	
Description	DAEMON capacity forecast models shall account for monetary costs in order to produce a practical prediction																
Version	001M2																
Owner	IMDEA																
Priority	High																
Risk	4																
Risk Description	Considering a high number of cost sources makes the forecasting problem more involved, and identifying the correct capacity prediction becomes harder in general.																
Rationale	Predicting the sheer capacity needed to accommodate the traffic demand is not sufficient in many practical applications of capacity forecasting to network orchestration and control. Often, decisions on the allocation resources and Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) must consider the costs incurred by the network operator (e.g., unnecessarily assigned resources that go unused, Service Level Agreement violations, VNF reconfiguration delays that determine subscriber churn, energy consumption generated by running VNFs at different network elements, etc.). Designing models that can capture such costs, and output a capacity that jointly reduces them, is critical to the economic sustainability of the network management process.																
K1	X	K2		K3		K4	X	K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-CFORE-000-001M2																

Table 9-61. FR-CFORE-003 description.

FR-CFORE-003																	
Description	DAEMON capacity forecast models shall operate over streaming data																
Version	001M5																
Owner	IMDEA																
Priority	High																
Risk	4																
Risk Description	Adapting capacity forecasting to support a streaming model adds complexity and challenges to the design of the solution, which may reduce its efficiency.																
Rationale	While many traffic forecasting models are trained off-line and tested on historical data, the operation of such models in production calls for training and operation on traffic data as it is measured in the network. This implicitly means that capacity forecasting models must be adapted to work on streaming data.																
K1		K2		K3	X	K4	X	K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-CFORE-000-001M2																

9.8 Automated anomaly response

Figure 9-10. AARES functional requirements.

Table 9-62. FR-AARES-000 description.

FR-AARES-000																	
Description		DAEMON shall automatically detect, analyze, and act against anomalous behaviors.															
Version		002M5															
Owner		TID															
Priority		High															
Risk		5															
Risk Description		Anomaly detection tasks might not correctly capture new previously unseen anomalies.															
Rationale		Most communication platforms use a reactive approach to deal with communication issues (i.e., operation teams reacts when incidents are severe only, and the service is often compromised already). DAEMON requires a proactive approach to anomaly detection that can detect both malicious and benign anomalies in the different systems it integrates.															
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7	X	K8		K9	
Parents		None															

Table 9-63. FR-AARES-001 description.

FR-AARES-001	
Description	DAEMON anomaly detection shall operate at different timescales, depending on the input from the system DAEMON is monitoring.
Version	002M5
Owner	TID
Priority	Medium
Risk	2
Risk Description	Each anomaly detection task should take into consideration the requirements in terms of the timescale it needs to generate anomaly warnings. For finer granularities, the performance of the models might implicitly decrease, as the time available for the model to produce results also decreases. We will work to find the best tradeoff between the most fitting timescale and the performance requirements for the DAEMON anomaly detection tasks.

Rationale		Anomalies can become easier to spot depending on the timescale that fits to the particular system with which DAEMON interacts.															
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7	X	K8		K9	
Parents		FR-AARES-000-001M2															

Table 9-64. FR-AARES-002 description.

FR-AARES-002																	
Description		DAEMON anomaly detection models have specific data requirements, including a sizable amount of historical data to establish normal behavior and ground truth occurrences of anomalies to develop a feasible solution.															
Version		002M5															
Owner		TID															
Priority		High															
Risk		4															
Risk Description		The lack of high quality historical data to establish the baseline behavior of the system (i.e., anomaly-free state for training) poses a high risk to developing anomaly detection approaches for DAEMON. Similarly, the lack of ground truth anomalies that have been detected in the system will make the validation of any anomaly detection approach challenging. Finally, the lack of expert knowledge brings an extra risk when building data features to train the anomaly detection tools for DAEMON.															
Rationale		The data quality is of paramount importance for the anomaly detection approaches we aim to integrate in DAEMON. Specifically, we aim to build on high quality ground truth for establishing the normal baseline for the system DAEMON monitors. Similarly, in order to validate the performance of our DAEMON anomaly detection solutions, we require a diverse set of ground-truth anomalies that operators previously captured in the systems DAEMON integrates. Furthermore, in order to craft data features that respond to the purpose of each system, we require expert knowledge and the operators' support in this process.															
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7	X	K8		K9	
Parents		FR-AARES-000-001M2															

Table 9-65. FR-AARES-003 description.

FR-AARES-003																	
Description		DAEMON shall take into consideration the cost of system monitoring, developing, and deploying the anomaly detection models in order to produce a feasible anomaly detection solution.															
Version		003M5															
Owner		TID															
Priority		Low															
Risk		1															
Risk Description		The high cost of training and running DAEMON anomaly detection tools might suppose a high expenditure for the operators' of the system in question.															
Rationale		DAEMON anomaly detection tools must run in real-world production systems, where we must also consider the actual monetary cost of running a state-of-the-art system for ML/DL tasks. We will work to produce solutions that adapt to different tiers of existing resources.															
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7	X	K8		K9	
Parents		FR-AARES-000-001M2															

9.9 Non-functional requirements

This section contains the non-functional requirements for the different NI use cases.

Table 9-66. NFR-RIS-000 description.

NFR-RIS-000																	
Description	RIS should aid to increase wireless capacity (bits/m ²) by 100%																
Version	001M1																
Owner	NEC																
Priority	High																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	There is a risk that the performance attained in realistic environments fall below 100%																
Rationale	This will allow surfaces to adapt in a timely manner, following the channel dynamics.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6	X	K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-RIS-000-001M1																

Table 9-67. NFR-RIS-001 description.

NFR-RIS-001																	
Description	RIS controller shall reconfigure surfaces with a timescale below 10ms																
Version	002M4																
Owner	NEC																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	This requirement shall be satisfied at all times. There is a mild risk that the controller or the interface is congested, leading to violating this requirement.																
Rationale	This will allow surfaces to adapt in a timely manner, following the channel dynamics.																
K1		K2		K3	AZ	K4		K5		K6	X	K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-RIS-000-001M1																

Table 9-68. NFR-RIS-002 description.

NFR-RIS-002																	
Description	RIS units shall support more than one user concurrently																
Version	002M4																
Owner	NEC																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	4																
Risk Description	Tight and timely coordination between gNB MAC schedulers may be required																
Rationale	This enables increasing the system capacity for multiple users.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6	X	K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-RIS-000-001M1																

Table 9-69. NFR-EAWVNF-001 description.

NFR-EAWVNF-001	
Description	DAEMON energy-aware solution, will scale considering a heterogeneous set of devices and network infrastructure FR-EAWVFN-001 .

Version	001M2																
Owner	UMA																
Priority	High																
Risk	4																
Risk Description	The variety of devices																
Rationale	DAEMON should be able to consider the global footprint of VNFs placement solution for a large number of different IoT and Edge devices with variable resources and networking infrastructure. The upper values of the devices' resources considered in DAEMON will be taken from the software and hardware network or devices specifications of the underlying infrastructure.																
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-EAWVNF-001-001M1																

Table 9-70. NFR-EAWVNF-002 description.

NFR-EAWVNF-002																	
Description	DEAMON expect to save the 50% of the energy cost, thanks to applying NI solutions to find out the energy-aware optimal placement of VNFs of FR-EAWFN-000																
Version	001M2																
Owner	UMA																
Priority	High																
Risk	3																
Risk Description	We cannot achieve the 50% of energy saving in all cases, only in some of them, or simply DAEMON solutions save an inferior percentage of energy.																
Rationale	The performance in terms of energy consumption of the DAEMON solution should improve the current solutions in a 50%.																
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-EAWVNF-001-001M1																

Table 9-71. NFR-EAWVNF-003 description.

NFR-EAWVNF-003																	
Description	The cost in terms of energy footprint of the NI solution for VNFs placing shall be less than the global energy saving																
Version	001M2																
Owner	UMA																
Priority	High																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	The cost of the NI-assisted VNF placement could be not much less or even higher than the energy consumption savings of the proposed solutions.																
Rationale	The energy saving obtained by applying energy profiling to the NI algorithms for the VNFs placement should be less than the global energy saving, to be worthy. So, the cost of the energy-awareness mechanism should be a lot less than the 50% of the energy saving proposed in NRF-EAWVNF-002.																
K1	X	K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-EAWVNF-001-001M1																

Table 9-72. NFR-CFORE-001 description.

NFR-CFORE-001																
Description	DAEMON capacity forecast models shall provide information about their level of accuracy															
Version	001M2															
Owner	IMDEA															
Priority	Medium															

Risk	3																
Risk Description	The additional output concerning the accuracy of the capacity prediction is a forecast on its own, and is thus subject to errors. If the accuracy information is completely off, it may damage the NI decision, rather than helping it.																
Rationale	While the capacity prediction is the main output of a capacity forecasting model, it is highly desirable that such information is coupled with a notion of the level of accuracy of the prediction. This knowledge enables a more informed decision by the relevant orchestrator or controller.																
K1		K2		K3		K4	X	K5	X	K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-CFORE-000-001M2																

Table 9-73. NFR-CFORE-002 description.

NFR-CFORE-002																	
Description	DAEMON capacity forecast models shall be able to learn autonomously their objective/loss function																
Version	001M2																
Owner	IMDEA																
Priority	Medium																
Risk	4																
Risk Description	Automated design of objective/loss functions is a new topic in machine learning, hence there is limited literature to build upon. It is also an especially hard subject to address in general.																
Rationale	In some cases, the relationship between the performance metric of interest (e.g., end user Quality of Experience, or subscriber churn rate) and the actionable network parameters (e.g., allocated resources, or VNF configuration) is not easy to determine a priori. In those cases, the NI needs to learn such relationship in an automated fashion, devising the correct objective/loss function.																
K1		K2		K3		K4	X	K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-CFORE-000-001M2																

Table 9-74. NFR-MTERM-001 description.

NFR-MTERM-001																	
Description	DAEMON shall provide an exhaustive list of orchestration operations within the NI-assisted management and orchestration framework																
Version	001M1																
Owner	IMEC																
Priority	High																
Risk	1																
Risk Description	The list of orchestration operations might involve subgroups of operations, depending on the policies defined for specific types of applications (e.g., value-added services require different orchestration operations than services that are directly consumed by users).																
Rationale	The NI-assisted management and orchestration framework needs to provide support for at least a basic set of orchestration operations, such as on-boarding (i.e., preparation of application descriptors and images on all required edge platforms), instantiation (on all required edge platforms), scaling up/down/out/in depending on the resource (computing and network) requirements and current resource consumption, termination (i.e., releasing the allocated resources so they can be consumed by other applications, or to save energy), and state/context migration (i.e., migrating the state/context of the application from one edge to another due to the UE mobility, resource availability, or energy saving purposes).																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-016-001M1																

Table 9-75. NFR-MTERM-002 description.

NFR-MTERM-002																	
Description		DAEMON shall provide compliance of NI-assisted management and orchestration framework with standardized frameworks (e.g., ETSI NFV MEC, ETSI NFV MANO, and O-RAN) running at the network edge.															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		1															
Risk Description		The insufficient level of compatibility between different standardization tracks (ETSI MEC/ETSI NFV MANO & O-RAN) can potentially lead to complex and application-specific orchestration platforms, limiting their exploitability among research tracks.															
Rationale		As the standardization plays a key role in ensuring that a software tool meets certain requirements that guarantee proper work in various conditions, and expanding the exploitability of such solution, NI-assisted management and orchestration framework needs to be designed and developed in accordance with the existing standardization efforts.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-003-001M1															

Table 9-76. NFR-MTERM-003 description.

NFR-MTERM-003																	
Description		DAEMON shall provide NI instance modularity and reusability among different players (e.g., network operators/vendors, service providers, etc.)															
Version		001M1															
Owner		IMEC															
Priority		High															
Risk		1															
Risk Description		The lack of NI instance complexity and an increased level of openness of I/O interfaces might decrease the accuracy in decision-making processes performed by those NI instances.															
Rationale		Due to the heterogeneity of resource and service deployments across edge networks, the NI instances running in both framework tiers need to be application/service-agnostic. Thus, no application-specific data should be considered apart from the resource requirements and KPIs stated in SLAs. With such configurations, NI instances can be maintained and used by different stakeholders.															
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents		FR-MTERM-002-001M1															

Table 9-77. NFR-MTERM-004 description.

NFR-MTERM-004													
Description		The system constraint for NI instance selection at the edge are energy, computation, network, and KPIs											
Version		001M1											
Owner		IMEC											
Priority		High											

Risk	1																
Risk Description																	
Rationale	Depending on the available resources and the business goals or SLAs, DAEMON will select the best NI instance model that suits the assisted system. For example, in some cases it might be feasible to sacrifice accuracy at the expenses of a lower computational complexity.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-MTERM-016-001M1																

Table 9-78. NFR-SLMANO-001 description.

NFR-SLMANO-001																	
Description	DAEMON shall define metrics to check the stability of a control algorithm.																
Version	001M1																
Owner	NBL																
Priority	high																
Risk	2																
Risk Description	Although a rough definition of a stable control system is easy to understand, i.e., if after exciting the system with a short, small perturbation, it returns fast enough to the original equilibrium, it is hard to make that definition precise for nonlinear systems.																
Rationale	It is well-known that closing the control loop may lead to instable systems. In linear systems instability stems from the fact that the closed loop transfer function has poles in the positive half plane, leading to a impulse response that exponentially increases. Although some ideas some chaos engineering may be applied, in non-linear systems there is no rigorous equivalent.																
K1		K2		K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	X
Parents	FR-SLMANO-003-001M2																

Table 9-79. NFR-CAWRS-000 description.

NFR-CAWRS-000																	
Description	NI orchestration solutions for vRAN shall have fast reaction times (below 10s)																
Version	001M1																
Owner	UC3M																
Priority	High																
Risk	1																
Risk Description	There is low risk that DAEMON will not integrate succeed to provide such timings for the NI-based network orchestration. In preliminary works, DAEMON partners were able to achieve computing resources orchestration within a 10s constraint. This constraint may be lowered with the usage of more performing orchestration solutions.																
Rationale	In Invalid source specified. , DAEMON authors were able to orchestrate computing resources for vRAN by using the Docker API, with a 10 seconds granularity. This value is already enough to bring down the computing resource usage by more than 30% in some scenario. By using directly the cgroups API offered by the Linux system, we may achieve even lower values.																
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9	
Parents	FR-CAWRS-000-001M3																

Table 9-80. NFR-CAWRS-001 description.

NFR-CAWRS-001																
Description		NI control solutions for vRAN shall have very fast reaction times (below 100ms)														
Version		001M1														
Owner		UC3M														
Priority		High														
Risk		2														
Risk Description		There is a mild risk that NI cannot achieve sub-second timings for the vRAN control algorithms such as the radio scheduling (which needs 1ms timings). If these timings cannot be achieved, DAEMON partners will use solutions such as slower scheduling patterns, enforced every 50-100 TTIs														
Rationale		Ideally, scheduling decisions are taken every TTIs, thus in the ms range scale. This requirement is quite stringent and may require specialized hardware such as GPUs deployed at the edge if deep learning solutions shall be put in place. Alternatives could be the usage of mixed models between machine learning and traditional optimization														
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9
Parents		FR-CAWRS-000-001M3														

Table 9-81. NFR-CAWRS-002 description.

NFR-CAWRS-002																
Description		NI solutions for vRAN shall achieve a bounded wireless performance with respect to the optimal														
Version		001M1														
Owner		UC3M														
Priority		High														
Risk		2														
Risk Description		There is a mild risk that NI cannot achieve bounded performance for the wireless performance (i.e., spectrum efficiency, leading to bandwidth and latency figures). In this case, specific boundaries to the achievable computing resource saving will be defined.														
Rationale		With unbounded computing resource savings, the spectral efficiency may be unacceptably low. In [12], DAEMON partners were capable of achieving very good tradeoffs between the achievable savings and the pure performance, by correctly understanding the traffic patterns. Other solutions may have to be designed to guarantee that this tradeoff (the ratio between the best possible performance without computing resource optimization and the one obtained by DAEMON solutions never falls below certain thresholds).														
K1		K2	X	K3		K4		K5		K6		K7		K8		K9
Parents		FR-CAWRS-000-001M3														

9.10 Verification

This section contains the different verification mechanism for the NI use cases.

9.10.1 Functional requirements: RIS control

FR-RIS-000 (DAEMON shall integrate Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces technology into mobile networks) shall be verified by verifying [FR-RIS-001](#) and [FR-RIS-002](#)).

FR-RIS-001 (RIS controller shall interact with the system orchestrator and radio controllers) shall be verified by testing the corresponding interfaces between the RIS controller and the radio controllers or orchestrator. This test can be implemented with dummy controllers/orchestrators making a variety of policy or configuration requests and confirm that the appropriate policy or configuration is set up in the RIS controller.

FR-RIS-002 (RIS controller shall receive feedback about the wireless channel) shall be verified by testing the interface between the radio access network controller and RIS controller. This test can be implemented with a dummy radio access controller that populates wireless channel information into the RIS' database using the interface under test.

9.10.2 Functional requirements: Multi-timescale Edge resource management

FR-MTERM-007 (DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall provide on-the-fly reconfiguration of VNFs) shall be verified by verifying [FR-MTERM-007.00](#) and [FR-MTERM-007.01](#)

FR-MTERM-007.00 (DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall provide on-the-fly VNF scaling) shall be verified by testing the scaling operation during the VNF runtime. If scale up/down operation is initiated by NI-assisted management and orchestration entities, on the specific VNF (i.e., use case application or NI instance), the procedure should be performed via assigning more/less resources (CPU, memory, storage) to the VNF, and it should result in more/less resourceful VNF. Similarly, if scale out/in operation is requested, then the procedure should be performed via increasing/decreasing the number of VNF replicas. Depending on the virtualization type (e.g., VMs or containers), verification should include checking the number of resources allocated to the VNF after performing scaling operation. Also, specific case that needs to be verified is a scale-in operation on the VNF that is running as a single replica, which should result in a warning/error due to the need to avoid a termination of the VNF. The *on-the-fly* characteristic shall be verified by checking if VNF is compromised during scaling (e.g., VNF stopped, VNF not stopped but performance affected, etc.).

FR-MTERM-007.01 (DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall provide on-the-fly update of VNFs) shall be verified by updating any of the VNF parameters (e.g., VNF configuration stated in VNF descriptor, VNF image, etc.) and checking if the requested change is applied afterwards. In addition, the performance of NI instances that are predicting the resource consumption can be also verified during these two operations, as NI instances might preempt the need for more/less resources, providing framework entities with sufficient time to prepare for the operation, and to perform it in a more efficient way in order to avoid compromising VNF and its performance. Thus, the success of NI instance operation shall be verified along with the verification of [FR-MTERM-007.00](#) and [FR-MTERM-007.01](#).

FR-MTERM-015 (DAEMON shall provide the interfaces with the NI-assisted management and orchestration framework to trigger the execution/termination of NI instances) shall be verified by verifying [FR-MTERM-015.00](#) and [FR-MTERM-015.01](#)

FR-MTERM-015.00 (DAEMON shall enable execution of NI instances) shall be verified by i) testing if NI instance is being supplied with training and testing data by monitoring and value-added services, and ii) testing if NI instances is able to produce any outcome, i.e., decision (the validity of such decision is out of scope of this verification process). Thus, if i) an interface between NI instance, and monitoring and value-added services, is established, i.e., NI instance can be fed with required data, and ii) NI instance is providing decisions as an outcome, the verification process is successful.

FR-MTERM-015.01 (DAEMON shall enable termination of NI instances) shall be verified by performing NI instance teardown operation, thereby checking if previously allocated resources for the NI instance are released, and if there is no NI instances running with this unique NI instance ID. To complete the verification procedure, the termination requesting entity shall receive an acknowledgement about the outcome of such operation.

FR-MTERM-016 (DAEMON NI-assisted management and orchestration framework shall be able to enforce NI instances' outcomes.) shall be verified by i) testing the procedure of translating an NI instance outcome (i.e., decision) to the policy/action that NI-assisted management and orchestration entities are performing on the operating VNFs, and ii) testing if this translation is unambiguous, by checking if the policy/action is performed by framework entities in an expected way (e.g., NI instance outcome states

that resource consumption of the VNF has an increasing trend, being translated to scale up/out operation. After executing the operation, [FR-MTERM-007.00](#) shall be verified).

FR-MTERM-18 (DAEMON shall be able to perform policy/action/decision conflict resolution to guarantee the stability of the assisted system.) will be verified in the verification procedure that should include at least two NI instance outcomes (e.g., from two different NI instances) that are simultaneously translated to policies/decisions for the same VNF, and then performed by framework entities resulting in expected updates of the VNF (e.g., VNF scaling/termination/update/migration), verifying the capability of framework entities to resolve conflict between two NI instance outcomes that refer to the contradictory policies/actions. The procedure should also involve verifying if expected reconfiguration of the VNF is performed based on the translated policy/action (i.e., verification of [FR-MTERM-007](#)). The verification procedure of [FR-MTERM-18](#) will help verifying the [FR-MTERM-016](#).

9.10.3 Functional requirements: In-backhaul support for service intelligence

FR-IBSSI-000 and its child requirement [FR-IBSSI-001](#) will be validated in terms of response time of the AI-Based algorithms, to study the feasibility of the proposed algorithms. This metric will be tested through simulated / emulated environments, or via analytical evaluation.

FR-IBSSI-002 will also be validated in terms of its feasibility through the response time. However, [FR-IBSSI-002](#) will be verified through experimental evaluation on real prototypes.

9.10.4 Functional requirements: Compute-aware radio scheduling

FR-CAWRS-000 shall be verified by the child requirements [NFR-CAWRS-000](#), [NFR-CAWRS-001](#), and [NFR-CAWRS-002](#). However, [FR-CAWRS-000](#) shall be verified as well in terms of impact on the targeted KPI such as the cost savings.

NFR-CAWRS-000 will be benchmarked with available virtual infrastructure managers such as Kubernetes or OpenStack, or directly with the underlying virtualization system like KVM or Linux Containers.

NFR-CAWRS-001 will be verified through real prototypes, directly embedding the controller.

NFR-CAWRS-002 will be benchmarked with simulators/emulators and real prototypes of mobile virtual network functions implementing Radio Access Network functions.

9.10.5 Functional requirements: Energy-aware VNF placement

FR-EAWVNF-000 shall be verified by [FR-EAWVNF-001](#), [FR-EAWVNF-002](#), [FR-EAWVNF-003](#), [FR-EAWVNF-004](#).

FR-EAWVNF-001 shall be verified by [FR-EAWVNF-001.00](#) and [FR-EAWVNF-001.01](#).

FR-EAWVNF-001.00 shall be verified by performing two groups of tests. First, it shall test selected VNFs with high CPU impact -that will be used as the benchmarks- on a cluster of devices to measure their CPU computation energy cost (related with the CPU cycles/instructions the VNF requires). It shall then test the accuracy in the energy estimation of those selected VNFs (also by changing randomly their parameters, considering constraint). It shall use an external device and/or software to measure the accuracy of those estimations.

FR-EAWVNF-001.01 shall be verified testing different workloads in selected VNFs over different types of network links. Different transmission powers or transmission rates shall be tested.

FR-EAWVNF-002 shall be verified in the same way that [FR-EAWVNF-001.01](#). First, VNFs with impact on some hardware resources, such as HDD or RAM, will be measured using an external device and/or piece of software. It shall then test the accuracy in the energy estimation of those selected VNFs (and by changing their parameters randomly, considering constraint). It shall use an external device and/or software to measure the accuracy of those estimations.

FR-EAWVNF-003 shall be verified by [FR-EAWVNF-003.00](#) and [FR-EAWVNF-003.01](#).

FR-EAWVNF-003.00 shall be verified by virtualizing a set of selected VNFs in different devices (virtualization and/or containerization) and identifying the energy cost of removing the previous VNF and deploy the new one on the target node.

FR-EAWVNF-003.01 shall be verified by virtualizing a set of selected VNFs (virtualization and/or containerization) and migrating them between different devices, identifying the amount of data transmitted.

FR-EAWVNF-004 shall be verified by [FR-EAWVNF-004.00](#).

FR-EAWVNF-004.00 shall be verified by using the factors involved to consider energy consumption sustainable. It must also be considered the energy footprint of the incoming communications. So, shall

be tested [FR-EAWVNF-001.00](#) and [FR-EAWVNF-001.01](#) in different -and simulated- energy consumption sustainable environments.

9.10.6 Functional requirements: Self-learning MANO

[FR-SLMANO-000](#) shall be verified by simulating realistic scenarios to assess to what extent human intervention can be avoided given the dynamicity of the problem to be solved.

[FR-SLMANO-001](#) and [FR-SLMANO-002](#) shall be verified by constructing network intents for several example use cases. On the one hand they should be readily understandable by a human operator and on the other hand they should be easily translatable in verifiable network metrics.

[FR-SLMANO-003](#) shall be verified by simulating systems fed traffic that tries to destabilize the system as much as possible using the framework of generative adversarial networks.

[FR-SLMANO-004](#) shall be verified by investigating whether or not the state-of-the-art techniques to render AI techniques explainable are applicable to the problems at hand.

[FR-SLMANO-005](#) shall be verified by simulating chaining circumstances and checking if the ML algorithm goes into retraining mode.

9.10.7 Functional requirements: Capacity forecasting

[FR-CFORE-000](#) (capacity forecast models shall support NI across the mobile network architecture) shall be verified by [FR-CFORE-001](#) and [FR-CFORE-002](#).

[FR-CFORE-001](#) (capacity forecast models shall operate at very different timescales) shall be verified via large-scale simulations of anticipatory resource allocations based on real-world traffic measurements, and demonstrating that such allocations are correct for traffic aggregated at different network elements, such as individual antennas, edge datacenters, or core datacenters, and for orchestration/control decisions occurring at diverse timescales, from minutes to hours or more.

[FR-CFORE-002](#) (capacity forecast models shall account for monetary costs) shall be verified via large-scale simulations of anticipatory resource allocations based on real-world traffic measurements, and demonstrating that such allocations driven by dedicated loss functions are correct under realistic models of the economic costs incurred by network operators.

9.10.8 Functional requirements: Automated anomaly response

[FR-AARES-000](#) (anomaly detection and response) will be verified via data-driven experimentation and small-scale pilot integration. We aim to design the anomaly detection solutions tailored to the specific system that we monitor (e.g., radio access network, international mobile roaming platform). We will collect representative datasets from the system we monitor in order to train state-of-the-art models to detect and proactively tackle anomalies. We will verify the performance of these models by [FR-AARES-001](#) and [FR-AARES-002](#).

[FR-AARES-001](#) (anomaly detection timescales) shall be verified via extensive data-driven testing and, also, based on the input of the operation teams performing the maintenance and monitoring actions of the different systems DAEMON will integrate. We aim to produce solutions that aid the operators by allowing them to move from a reactive approach to dealing with anomalies to a proactive approach. Together with different operators we aim to demonstrate how we integrate anomaly detection solutions in their systems.

[FR-AARES-002](#) (data for anomaly detection) shall be verified by the deep analysis of monitoring datasets from real-world operational systems. Together with operators, we will build high-quality datasets that will enable DAEMON to offer high performance in terms of anomaly detection (i.e., high precision and recall, over 0.85).

[FR-AARES-003](#) (the cost of running anomaly detection) shall be verified by running extensive simulations of anticipatory resources needed for deploying anomaly detection solutions in the real-world systems that we will monitor.

9.10.9 Non-functional requirements

[NFR-RIS-000](#) (RIS should aid to increase wireless capacity (bits/m²) by 100%) shall be verified either via simulations or via a small experimental proof of concept by (i) estimating the attained capacity in a wireless channel between one transmitter and one receiver in different physical locations, and (ii) comparing the observed capacity when the communication is RIS-aided and when it is not.

[NFR-EAWVNF-001](#) shall test selected VNFs in different IoT and Edge devices with variable resources and networking infrastructure and provide their global footprint.

NFR-EAWVNF-002 DAEMON shall be tested in different scenarios to be defined, with the energy goal activated and without it. Statistical significance will be checked regarding the energy saving.

NFR-RIS-001 (RIS controller shall reconfigure surfaces with a timescale below 1ms) shall be verified by three means: (i) measuring the elapsed time of the NI processing data and computing RIS parameters, (ii) measuring the latency it takes to propagate the computed policy between the controller and the RISs, and (iii) measuring the elapsed time for the RIS to enforce the computed policy. The aggregate latency shall be within 1 ms.

NFR-RIS-002 (RIS units shall support more than one user concurrently) shall be verified by simulations or via experiments with a small-scale prototype with one transmitter, at least two receivers, and at least one RIS. The measurement should indicate wireless capacity gain when using RIS with respect to not using RIS.

NFR-CFORE-001 (capacity forecast models shall provide information about their level of accuracy) shall be verified by demonstrating that the models output information on the accuracy or uncertainty level of the prediction, in addition to the forecast itself.

NFR-CFORE-002 (capacity forecast models shall be able to learn autonomously their loss function) shall be verified by demonstrating that the models can integrate in the learning process the parameters or shape of the loss function to optimize, in addition to traditional hyperparameters.

NFR-SLMANO-001 (definition of metrics to check the stability of a control algorithm) shall be verified by evaluating a number of metrics that capture the notion of stability and selecting the best one by also comparing how they perform in linear systems where stability is precisely defined.

10 Appendix B: Analysis of Existing Frameworks and Architectures

This appendix reports on the review of the state-of-the-art of existing frameworks and architectures related to edge computing, network function virtualization, and machine learning.

10.1 ETSI MEC

Multi-access Edge Computing enables the implementation of MEC applications as software-only entities that run on top of a Virtualization infrastructure, which is located in or close to the network edge. Figure 10-1 depicts a variant of the multi-access edge system reference architecture [28] for the deployment in a Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) environment [27].

Figure 10-1. Multi-access edge system reference architecture variant for MEC in NFV [28].

10.1.1 MEC platform functions

The **MEC platform** is responsible for the following functions:

- Offering an environment where the MEC applications can discover, advertise, consume, and offer MEC services, including, when supported, MEC services available via other platforms (that may be in the same or a different MEC system).
- Receiving traffic rules from the MEC platform manager, applications, or services and instructing the data plane accordingly. When supported, this includes the translation of tags representing UEs in the traffic rules into specific IP addresses.
- Hosting MEC services.

The MEC platform may be accompanied by API gateway functionality for MEC applications to access the MEC service APIs. Note that the exhaustive list of MEC platform functions can be found in [28].

MEC applications run as a Virtualized application, such as a Virtual Machine (VM) or a containerized application, on top of the Virtualization infrastructure provided by the MEC host and can interact with the MEC platform to consume and provide MEC services. In certain cases, MEC applications can also interact with the MEC platform to perform certain support procedures related to the lifecycle of the application, such as indicating availability, preparing relocation of user state, etc. A **MEC service** is a service provided and consumed either by the MEC platform or a MEC application. When provided by an application, it can be registered in the list of services to the MEC platform over the Mp1 reference point. The **Mp1 reference point** between the MEC platform and the MEC applications provides service registration, service discovery, and communication support for services. This reference point can be used

for consuming services and providing service specific functionality. Recently, ETSI MEC started looking into distributed MEC deployments with **inter-MEC system communication** where a MEC application should be able to exchange information in a secure manner with other MEC applications that may belong to different hierarchical MEC systems.

10.1.2 Gaps

When dealing with MEC services and MEC APIs, the general assumption is that those APIs are based on a RESTful interface [109]. The main drawbacks of such approach are the following:

- A RESTful interface is host-centric, that means that the parties involved in the communication are always required to know the host they need to connect to. In very decentralized environment, notably when system dynamically changes overtime, this could lead to a non-negligible discovery overhead.
- A RESTful interface is query-response, which means that other patterns as pub-sub are not considered leading to artificially complex design choices and implementations only to comply with such requirement.
- RESTful was originally designed for the web, where human interactions are the norm and high responsiveness (for machine standards) are not required.

Summarizing, ETSI MEC service-based architecture relies to well-established Cloud technologies that show some limitations when applied to non-static environments that can be found at the far-Edge and beyond-Edge, including subscribers.

10.2 ETSI NFV

The management and orchestration (MANO) aspects of a VNF include traditional Fault Management, Configuration Management, Accounting Management, Performance Management, and Security Management (FCAPS), and ETSI ISG NFV standardized the NFV-MANO framework to simplify and automate FCAPS, and to provide life-cycle management of deployed VNFs and resources deployed within NFV Infrastructure (NFVI) [27].

By decoupling network functions from the physical infrastructure, i.e., deploying virtualized functions on top of the virtualized NFV infrastructure (e.g., computing and network resources), a basic set of MANO operations is focused on the VNF deployment and life-cycle management on NFVI resources, and it consists of: a) instantiation (creating VNFs using the on-boarded VNF descriptors), b) scaling (increasing/decreasing the capacity of the VNF), c) updating/upgrading (reconfiguration of VNFs), d) termination (releasing allocated NFVI resources), etc.

Figure 10-2. The ETSI NFV-MANO architectural framework with reference points.

In Figure 10-2, the NFV-MANO architectural framework defined by ETSI NFV is presented, together with the reference points, including Execution reference points, Main NFV reference points, and other reference points. In particular, ETSI NFV MANO framework consists of the three main components [29]:

- NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) – in charge of orchestration of NFVI resources across multiple VIMs, and of performing life-cycle management operations on virtualized network services; it has reference points to external systems (OSS/BSS)
- VNF Manager (VNFM) – in charge of life-cycle management of VNFs (instantiation and runtime operations such as scaling up/down/in/out); each VNF manager can manage only one VNF, or multiple VNFs
- Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) – in charge of orchestrating the allocation/upgrade/release/reclamation of NFVI resources (e.g., computing and network resources)

ETSI NFV also provides set of reference points that connect different architectural framework elements, defining the operations that can be executed via those reference points. Furthermore, ETSI NFV MANO defines an additional element, i.e., WAN Infrastructure Manager (WIM), on top of the existing VIMs to extend connectivity of network services to multiple domains, e.g., MEC sites. To provide collaboration between different domains on the orchestration level, ETSI NFV MANO also specifies Or-Or reference point between NFVOs in respective domains.

The two main challenges arise in ETSI NFV standardization tracks:

- 1) **Heterogeneity**, which requires managing end-to-end services across a mixture of NFV functions, infrastructure, and legacy interconnected network systems in a highly dynamic NFV environment. In particular, heterogeneity requires:
 - a) convergence on a common approach to present management service from both legacy network systems and NFV based systems needed;
 - b) a common way to integrate an end-to-end view across multiple resources:
 - i) to describe the semantics and relationships of information exchanged across management interfaces;
 - ii) to lower integration complexity by defining a set of common interface operations following a request/response pattern;
 - iii) to improve consistency in representing information in end-to-end applications, providing common data types and common vocabularies (e.g., specification of fault codes and location codes across multiple resources).
- 2) **Automation**, as an ability to dynamically incorporate changes in NFV MANO, which leads to an agile management of network functions, applications, and services, thereby reducing the costs. In particular, automation brings to NFV MANO a flexible and dynamic NFV management and orchestration via policy-based management approach, and real-time processing of huge amount of data. Such support for automation can be provided by:
 - a) open and standardized interfaces
 - b) common information models
 - c) mapping to different data modes
 - d) ability to incorporate real-time data analytics

Furthermore, to enable dynamic/automated NFV MANO, the architecture shall support run-time integration of management functions and processes, unlike the usual static integration

- a) this means that interfaces defined in ETSI NFV MANO need to be loosely coupled, allowing different entities to consume the information based on service necessity
- b) such interfaces will allow services and applications to be data-driven and controlled by policies

Concerning the automation challenge stated above, [110] identifies ML and in general AI as key enablers for increasing automation, where AI-powered mechanisms require fast access to data, abstraction of intelligent and contextual information from events and rule-based systems, supervision, streamlined workflows and lifecycle management.

Various data types can be collected from many sources on a daily, weekly, monthly, etc. basis, to enable incorporation of AI in NFV MANO. Some of them are:

- data from network functional elements
- data from infrastructure (including cloud)
- data from user equipment
- data from management systems
- data from external systems (databases, applications, etc.)

Network optimization with the aid of AI can operate at different time scales and may have a broader scope that includes intelligent management and control of resources and parameters of a network and of particular services.

Such management and control intelligence provides Autonomic (i.e., Closed loop) configuration management, autonomic fault management, autonomic performance management, autonomic security management, autonomic monitoring management, which are currently not specified by ETSI NFV MANO, no support for monitoring in general, neither for any automation of management procedures, see Figure 10-3.

According to [110], ISG NFV considers AI as a tool that will eventually become part of the MANO stack, although NFV is not explicitly considering AI, except in requirements to properly feed data and collect actions from AI modules [111].

The goal of the Work Item presented in [111] is to study and evaluate possible enhancements to NFV-MANO to improve its automation capabilities and introduce autonomous network mechanisms. This work will align with automation related work in organizations such as **ETSI ISG ZSM**, **ETSI ISG ENI** and **3GPP SA5**. Recommendations for normative work to enable autonomous management in NFV-MANO need to be made. As stated in [111], although NFV MANO has some fundamental automation mechanisms, such as policy management, it still requires improvements with respect to automation, along with the transformation from NFV to cloud-native. According to [111], the transformation of virtualized network functions to cloud-native brings a higher demand of automation to the management and orchestration of NFV to satisfy unprecedented operational agility and efficiency. The study presented in [111] investigates the feasibility whether the automation mechanisms can be adapted to NFV-MANO during the NFV evolution to cloud-native, in order to provide a higher level of automation to MANO operations.

Currently, the automation mechanisms in NFV-MANO are only the rule-based auto-scaling and auto-healing operations that are treated as policies, which are written in VNF descriptors (VNFDs). These descriptors provide the description of scale or heal actions to be executed when a condition involving monitoring parameters or VNF indicators is satisfied. The enforcement of auto-scale rule or auto-heal rule occurs in the VNFM and the NFVO automatically. However, **automation procedures are not tackled by ETSI NFV MANO** but by standardization groups such as 3GPP SA5, ETSI ISG ZSM, and ETSI ISG ENI.

- 1) 3GPP SA5
 - a) Intent driven management services for mobile networks
 - b) Study on enhancement of Management Data Analytics Services
 - c) Study on concept, requirements and solutions for levels of autonomous network
 - d) Study on the Self-Organizing Networks (SON) for 5G networks
 - e) Study on integration of Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP) and 3GPP management for 5G networks
- 2) ETSI ISG ZSM
 - a) Requirements on the zero-touch E2E (End-to-End) network and service management
 - b) End to end management and orchestration of network slicing
 - c) Inter management domain lifecycle management
 - d) Closed-loop automation

Figure 10-3. High-level overview of steps in a closed loop.

3) ETSI ISG ENI

- a) ETSI ISG ENI focuses on improving the operator experience, adding closed-loop artificial intelligence mechanisms based on context-aware, metadata-driven policies to faster recognize and incorporate new and changed knowledge, and hence make actionable decisions. **Table 10-1** presents the description of ENI use cases.

Table 10-1. ENI use cases.

ENI use cases	Description
Intent based network service management (intent based service instantiation, intent based service scaling, and intent based service termination)	Intent is described in a declarative way, and intelligent NFV MANO entities should know how to interpret them and to react accordingly, thereby translating them automatically in the set of actions
	Intent management -- a set of logical functions incorporated within existing NFV MANO entities, and it <u>doesn't necessarily mean that any new functional block will be added to the existing NFV MANO architectural framework</u>
	It is not explicitly stated in network service and VNF descriptors, but it can be interpreted by NFV MANO elements as a need for instantiation to fulfil the requirements and achieve desired performance (OSS/BSS might not be aware of instantiation as a process at all) -- the same applies to scaling and termination
Management Data Analytics assisted management	Management Data Analytics (MDA) is initially specified in 3GPP TS 28.550, which refers to management services using management analytical data in network and service management -- in conjunction with AI and ML techniques (as parts of internal implementation of the MDA), MDA brings intelligence and automation to the network service management & orchestration.
	Network service alarm incident analysis - complex topological relationship between constituent components of a network service (VNFs chained in NS) might imply series of alarms in NFV MANO, which might have the same root cause; complexity of alarm management is high -- alarms propagated via multiple MANO components; huge number of alarms -- AI/ML models and algorithms can be used to group or filter correlated alarms and indicate the root cause.
	Network service health analysis -- NS health is a high-level metric of the NS runtime status, which reflects whether the NS runs normally or not during one period of its lifecycle -- NFVO might trigger LCM operation to return NS to a healthy state.
	Network service resource utilization analysis -- MDA collects resource utilization input for NFVO, and NFVO might initiate operations for resolving issues with resource utilization.
	Cross administrative domain management data analytics -- network service might be composed of components that belong to different administrative domains (e.g., composite network services); analysis of the health of a composite NS in one administrative domain with assistance of the health analysis result of the nested NS in a different administrative domain.
Closed loops automation (CLA) in the context of NFV framework	The zero-touch automation goal is to remove the need of human execution of manual tasks in the network operation and in the creation and delivery of services.
	The CLA outcome is to make a system autonomous, capable to continuously monitor its behaviour and performance, evaluate and take any necessary actions when the goals are not fulfilled.

	Not fully independent from human intervention à in autonomous systems needed if policy failed, while in cognitive systems, the system can, reactively or pro-actively, create a new policy simply based on its policy learning mechanisms, which is useful when a human intervention is not possible at a specific time e.g., during policy failure.
Autonomous container infrastructure management	Defines Container Infrastructure Service Management (CISM) function that supports NFV MANO to manage container infrastructure in intent based, declarative way. Offloads complex container infrastructure management from NFVO and VNFM, which can further focus on management logic of containerized workloads.

10.3 ETSI ENI

The ENI System functional architecture, with or without an API Broker, consists of three types of Functional Blocks, in Figure 10-4, as follows.

- 1) One or more Functional Blocks for ingesting and normalizing data.
- 2) One or more Functional Blocks for denormalizing and generating recommendations and/or commands.
- 3) One or more Functional Blocks for analyzing ingested data, determining if the Assisted System is operating as expected, and if not, providing a set of recommendations and/or commands.

A key assumption is that the ENI System functionality evolves over time. It is anticipated that the capabilities of various Functional Blocks also evolve over time. As human operators gain confidence in automated decision-making, it is likely that ENI Functional Blocks operate with different and increased levels of autonomy. Therefore, no attempt is made to standardize the interaction among internal blocks.

Figure 10-4. High-Level Functional Architecture of ENI When an API Broker Is Used.

API Broker: The purpose of the API Broker is to decouple the ENI System from other external systems that it communicates with. In general, each Assisted System has its own unique functionality and set of APIs. This implies that the ENI System would have to understand each of these different sets of APIs in order to communicate with them. This is not desirable, and makes the building of ENI very complex. Instead, the present document defines an API Broker to aid in the translation between external systems and the ENI System. This enables the ENI System to define a single set of APIs. Therefore, the purpose of the API Broker is to: 1) translate data communicated from the Assisted System (or its Designated Entity) into a normalized form that all ENI Functional Blocks are able to understand; and 2) translate recommendations and

commands from the normalized form of ENI to a form that the Assisted System (or its Designated Entity) is able to understand.

Input Processing: Input processing consists of two Functional Blocks: the Data Ingestion and the Normalization Functional Blocks. All external data enters the Data Ingestion Functional Block. It is possible to combine the functionality of the Data Ingestion and Normalization Functional Blocks into a single Functional Block if desired.

Analysis: Knowledge Management and Processing consists of three Functional Blocks: Knowledge Management, Context Awareness, and Cognition Management Functional Blocks. It is possible to combine the functionality of these three Functional Blocks into a single Functional Block if desired.

Situation-based, Model-driven, Policy Generation: Situation-based Policy Generation Functional Block consists of three Functional Blocks: Situation Awareness, Model Driven Engineering, and Policy Management Functional Blocks.

Output Generation: Output Generation consists of two Functional Blocks: Denormalization and Output Generation Functional Blocks. It is permissible that the functionality of these two Functional Blocks is combined into a single Functional Block if desired.

Challenges:

- Currently, it is assumed that ENI works as its own discrete System external to the Assisted System. The alternative (ENI working as an embedded System within the Assisted System) is currently not supportable because the appropriate APIs, models and other required artefacts do not yet exist for ENI.
- How different information model fragments are exchanged between ENI and the Assisted System (or its Designated Entity). This has important security ramifications since this information represents critical assets of both ENI and the Assisted System.
- Knowledge representation.
- How knowledge is distributed to other ENI Functional Blocks.

As ENI exposes new interfaces, new APIs and Reference Points may expose new attack surfaces. ENI shall provide mitigation against attacks from those new attack surfaces.

10.4 ORAN

The architecture of O-RAN is presented in Figure 10-5. Doubtlessly, the most important functional components introduced by O-RAN are the Non-Real-Time (Non-RT) Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC) and the near-RT RIC. While the former is hosted by the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework of the system (e.g., integrated within ONAP), the latter may be co-located with 3GPP gNB functions, namely, O-RAN-compliant Cloud Unit (O-CU) and/or Distributed Unit (O-DU), or fully decoupled from them as long as latency constraints are respected. The figure also depicts the O-Cloud, an O-RAN compliant cloud platform that uses hardware accelerator add-ons when needed (e.g., to speed up FFT or decoding workflows) and a software stack that is decoupled from the hardware to deploy eNBs/gNBs as virtualized network functions (VNFs) in vRAN scenarios. In the following, we detail the jurisdiction and roles of each functional component defined above.

Service Management and Orchestration (SMO). The SMO consolidates several orchestration and management services, which may go beyond pure RAN management such as 3GPP (NG-)core management or end-to-end network slice management. In the context of O-RAN, the main responsibilities of SMO are (i) fault, configuration, accounting, performance and security (FCAPS) interface to O-RAN network functions; (ii) large timescale RAN optimization; and (iii) O-Cloud management and orchestration via O2 interface, including resource discovery, scaling, FCAPS, software management, create, read, update, and delete (CRUD) O-Cloud resources.

Non-RT RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC). As mentioned earlier, this logical function resides within the SMO and provides the A1 interface to the Near-RT RIC. Its main goal is to support large timescale RAN optimization (seconds or minutes), including policy computation, ML model management (e.g. training), and other radio resource management functions within this timescale. Data management tasks requested by the Non-RT RIC should be converted into the O1/O2 interface; and contextual/enrichment information can be provided to the near-RT RIC via A1 interface.

Near-RT RAN intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC). Near-RT RIC is a logical function that enables near-real-time optimization & control and data monitoring of O-CU and O-DU nodes in near-real-time timescales (between 10ms and 1s). To this end, Near-RT RIC control is steered by the policies and assisted by models computed/trained by the Non-RT RIC. One of the main operations assigned to the near-RT RIC is radio resource management (RRM) but near-RT RIC also supports 3rd party applications (so-called xApps).

Figure 10-5. O-RAN architecture.

This architecture inherently enables three independent control loops—yet with sporadic interactions:

- **Non-RT RIC control loop:** Large timescale operation of the orders of seconds or minutes. The goal is to perform O-RAN specific orchestration decisions such as policy configuration or ML model training.
- **Near-RT RIC control loop:** Sub-second time scale operation with the goal of performing tasks such as policy enforcement or radio resource management operations.
- **O-DU Scheduler control loop:** Real-time operation performing legacy radio operations such as HARQ, beamforming or scheduling—out of O-RAN's scope.

O-RAN's disposition towards software-defined AI-assisted RAN control fosters different degrees of openness, namely, systems comprised of (i) O-RAN-compliant PNFs exposing and using O-RAN interfaces so different vendors can interplay (lowest degree of openness); (ii) chassis of servers and racks in a cloud shared among multiple vendors (higher degree of openness); and (iii) one or multiple O-Clouds, a fabric of COTS servers (including FGPA or GPU accelerators) and networking infrastructure hosting O-RAN software that is decoupled from the hardware at different layers: hardware (e.g. ETSI NFVI hardware sub-layer), middle (e.g., ETSI NFVI virtualization sub-layer + VIM) and a top layer hosting virtual RAN functions (highest degree of openness).

Figure 10-6. O-RAN Deployment Models.

Such openness enables substantial flexibility to deploy each of the logical functions introduced earlier, e.g., O-DU and O-RU can be co-located or not depending on the context and particular needs of the operator and these decisions may be changed over time with minimal cost. Specifically, O-RAN functionality may be deployed across different key locations, namely, cell site, edge cloud and/or regional cloud. The cell site refers to the location of the radio units (RUs). The edge cloud is a location that may centralize virtualized RAN functions for multiple cell sites. Note that the specific coverage area of an edge cloud depends on the operator's use case but must satisfy the network latency requirements between O-DUs and O-RUs. Finally, the regional cloud may also host virtualized RAN functions and must satisfy the latency requirements between near-RT RIC and O-CUs/O-DUs. Figure 10-6 summarizes six different deployment scenarios, which are further described in the following:

Scenario A. In this scenario, one edge cloud centralizes all near-RT RIC, virtual O-CU and O-DU functions to support very dense deployments (e.g., dense urban areas) that provide a high-capacity fronthaul network. This type of deployment expects edge clouds with substantial hardware acceleration capabilities.

Scenario B. This scenario separates the virtual O-CU and O-DU functions from the near-RT RIC, which can be placed in a regional cloud and uses E2 interface for interaction with O-CUs and O-DUs. This allows near-RT RIC to have a global view for optimization.

Scenario C. Virtual O-CU network functions are co-located with the near-RT RIC in a regional cloud. Regional cloud and edge cloud(s) must, in this case, satisfy the latency requirements of 3GPP-defined F1 interface. This scenario enables deployment in locations with limited fronthaul capacity and number of O-RUs. There are two additional variations of this scenario to support specific network slices needs. On the one hand, Scenario C.1 allows certain O-CU-UP functions to be deployed at the edge cloud to meet the requirements of latency-stringent slices. On the other hand, Scenario C.2 allows certain O-CU-UP to be deployed at the edge cloud and multiple instances of O-DU functions to support specific network slices.

Scenario D. This scenario is a replica of Scenario C in which O-DU functions are *not* virtualized in an O-Cloud but rather supported by an O-RAN-capable PNF.

Scenario E. This scenario is a replica of Scenario C in which the O-RU functions are virtualized into a common O-Cloud, in addition to the O-DU functions.

Scenario F. This scenario is a replica of Scenario E in which O-DU and O-RU functions are virtualized into separate O-Clouds.

10.5 OSM

Open Source MANO (OSM) is an ETSI-hosted project to develop an Open Source NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) software stack aligned with ETSI NFV. The goal of ETSI OSM is the development of a community-driven production-quality E2E Network Service Orchestrator (E2E NSO) for telco services, capable of modelling and automating real telco-grade services, with all the intrinsic complexity of production environments. OSM provides a way to accelerate the maturing of NFV technologies and standards, enable a broad ecosystem of VNF vendors, and test and validate the joint interaction of the orchestrator with the other components it has to interact with: commercial NFV infrastructures (NFVI+VIM) and Network Functions (either VNFs, PNFs or Hybrid ones).

OSM's approach aims to minimize integration efforts thanks to four key aspects:

- A well-known **Information Model (IM)**, aligned with ETSI NFV SOL006, that is capable of modelling and automating the full lifecycle of Network Functions (virtual, physical or hybrid), Network Services (NS), and Network Slices (NST/NSI), from their initial deployment (instantiation, Day-0, and Day-1) to their daily operation and monitoring (Day-2). OSM IM augments ETSI NFV SOL006 by adding the support of Network Slices, day-1 and day-2 primitives at VNF and NS level, and Enhanced Platform Awareness for dataplane workloads.
 - Actually, OSM's IM is completely infrastructure-agnostic, so that the same model can be used to instantiate a given element (e.g. VNF) in a large variety of VIM types and transport technologies, enabling an ecosystem of VNF models ready for their deployment everywhere.
- OSM provides a **unified northbound interface (NBI)**, based on NFV SOL005, which enables the full operation of system and the Network Services and Network Slices under its control. In fact, OSM's NBI offers the service of managing the lifecycle of Network Services (NS) and Network Slices Instances (NSI), providing as a service all the necessary abstractions to allow the complete control, operation and supervision of the NS/NSI lifecycle by client systems, avoiding the exposure of unnecessary details of its constituent elements.
- The **extended concept of "Network Service"** in OSM, so that an NS can span across the different domains identified—virtual, physical and transport—, and therefore control the full lifecycle of an NS

interacting with VNFs, PNFs and HNFs in an undistinguishable manner along with on demand transport connections among different sites.

- In addition, OSM can also manage the lifecycle of **Network Slices**, assuming when required the role of Slice Manager, extending it also to support an integrated operation.

OSM provides the capability of realizing one of the main promises derived from NFV and the dynamic capabilities that it brings: creating networks on demand (“Network as a Service” or NaaS) for either their direct exploitation by the service provider or for their potential commercialization to third parties. In that sense, OSM works as a Network Service Orchestrator (NSO) intended to provide the capability of creating network services on demand and returning a service object ID that can be used later as a handler to control the whole lifecycle and operations of the network service via subsequent calls to OSM’s northbound API and monitor its global state in a convenient fashion.

In the case of OSM, there are two types of NaaS service objects that OSM is able to provide on demand to support the NaaS capability: the Network Service (NS) and the Network Slice Instance (NSI), being the latter a composition of several Network Services that can be treated as a single entity (particularities of both types of NaaS service objects will be described in the next sections).

OSM, as manager function of a service platform, consumes services from other service platforms and controls a number of managed functions in order to create its own composite higher-level service objects. Thus, OSM consumes services provided by the platform(s) in charge of the Virtual Infrastructure (to obtain VMs, etc.) and the platform(s) in charge of the SW-Defined Network (to obtain all the required kinds of inter-DC connections). Once assembled, it configures and monitors the constituent network functions (VNFs, PNFs, HNFs) to control the LCM of the entire NS/NSI to be offered on demand.

This view of OSM as part of a service platform architecture for NFV is summarized in Figure 10-7.

Figure 10-7. OSM as a network service orchestrator for NaaS.

Gap analysis. OSM is a first-of-its-kind effort by ETSI, which has historically focused on standards, to expand the focus of the organization to open-source tools. Its implementation is therefore fully aligned with the NFV reference architecture developed by ETSI. However, it also inherits all the limitations of ETSI NFV MANO, which are also discussed in this document.

10.6 3GPP

Traditionally, procedures related to network management, network orchestration, and network control have been developed by different tracks of the standardization activities. Hence, the functions that execute these procedures (i.e., OSS functions, element managers, orchestrators, or radio and core NFs) have been designed in a domain-specific and, in some cases, even proprietary manner, with possible optimizations happening only in a “per domain” way, leaving the interaction limited to peer-to-peer reference points within a domain, e.g., between control plane (CP) and UP.

In such reference-point-based setups, optimizations are either open-loop (i.e., no feedback among different modules in the system) or require very expensive human engineering procedures to close the loop. This approach has been deemed valid within legacy networks due to their limited number of possible configurations. However, in a 5G environment, this approach clearly falls short. Also, as legacy

NFs either have function-specific data acquisition and processing procedures or no procedure at all, simple configurations or rulesets are usually sufficient to achieve optimization goals.

In 5G, network slicing, among others, has imposed a more modular design of NFs, allowing these NFs to be shared and re-used across slices in a more fine-grained and targeted manner. That is, a single Network Slice Subnet Instance (NSSI) and its constituent NFs may be used across several slices and services (e.g., common radio access NFs across slices). Thus, interfaces devoted to the data acquisition and processing from NFs or even to feed and push data to specific AI modules shall be designed. In order to “close the loop” in an automated manner, by adding AI and big data solutions, new interfaces and functionalities are needed:

- Flexible data exchange across domains. Different network domains shall be able to exchange information among them using, e.g., a publish-subscribe methodology.
- Reliable and scalable configurations. Besides producing and consuming the data, the NFs in all domains shall offer ways to allow authorized configuration of their relevant parameters, possibly with different levels of authorization, e.g., depending on the enforced resource provisioning scheme. For instance, some service providers may have full configuration capabilities while others may only have limited visibility of configurable parameters.

For these reasons, the current exposure framework shall be extended, to allow the vision proposed by DAEMON.

3GPP Architecture does not deal directly with algorithms that provide the NI functionalities, it introduces the needed boxes that are devoted to the data collection and analytics in the network. This has been initially discussed especially by the 5G-Core Network Functions.

Figure 10-8. 5G System architecture.

3GPP Architecture (see Figure 10-8) does not deal directly with algorithms that provide the NI functionalities, it introduces the needed boxes that are devoted to the data collection and analytics in the network. This has been initially discussed especially by the 5G-Core Network Functions and implemented in the NWDAF (Network Data Analytics Function, Figure 10-9), which is in charge of achieving the data analytics functionality for the 5GC. This concept is the cornerstone of the application of the NI in the network, as also discussed in the 3GPP documents.

Figure 10-9. Analytics for the 5G System [113].

However, as discussed before, this vision is currently limited to the core only, and just few other initiatives are devoted to provide such elements each network segment (i.e., RAN, Core, Management) defined by 3GPP. The application of such paradigm in all of them is currently just left to research effort, such as the one discussed in and depicted in Figure 10-10, with specific elements running in all of them.

Figure 10-10. Extended data analytics for the 5GS [114].

Currently, just the management plane is including similar characteristics, although in very early stages through the MDAF (Management Data Analytic Function) providing the MDAS (Management Data Analytic Service) [115], which is capable of interfacing with the NWDAF to provide data exchange (and thus enabling NI) between core and management. MDAF provides service access point as depicted in the Figure 10-11.

Figure 10-11. MDAF and MDAS [115].

10.7 ONAP

Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP) is a microservice platform that aims at bringing a full network management automation in 5G for both physical and virtual network function, as it enables the design, creation, and orchestration of services on the infrastructure layer sitting on top of individual virtual network functions or SDN, or a combination of the two. It is intended as a comprehensive platform for the orchestration, management, and automation of network and edge computing services for network operators, cloud providers, and enterprises. Real-time, policy-driven orchestration and automation of physical, virtual, and cloud native network functions enables rapid automation of new services and complete lifecycle management critical for 5G and next-generation networks. The latest release (Guilin) dates of December 2020, and comes with a functional architecture with component definitions and interfaces, which provides industry alignment in addition to the open source code.

Figure 10-12. Functional view of the ONAP architecture.

Figure 10-12 provides a simplified functional view of the architecture, which highlights the role of several key components:

- Design time environment for onboarding services and resources into ONAP and designing required services.
- External API provides northbound interoperability for the ONAP Platform and Multi-VIM/Cloud provides cloud interoperability for the ONAP workloads.
- OOM provides the ability to manage cloud-native installation and deployments to Kubernetes-managed cloud environments.
- ONAP Shared Services provides shared capabilities for ONAP modules. The ONAP Optimization Framework (OOF) provides a declarative, policy-driven approach for creating and running optimization applications like Homing/Placement, and Change Management Scheduling Optimization.
- ONAP shared utilities provide utilities for the support of the ONAP components.
- Information Model and framework utilities continue to evolve to harmonize the topology, workflow, and policy models from a number of SDOs including ETSI NFV MANO, ETSI/3GPP, O-RAN, TM Forum SID, ONF Core, OASIS TOSCA, IETF, and MEF.

Especially relevant to the scope of DAEMON are two activities in ONAP.

The main one is the **ONAP Optimization Framework (OOF)** mentioned above, which has the primary goal of addressing the optimization needs of ONAP. OOF is a framework that supports creating and running a suite of optimizing applications to support: (i) a declarative, policy-driven approach to solving optimization problems, (ii) reusable components such as data and policy adapters/libraries, execution environment; (iii) general-purpose as well as custom optimizers; (iv) extensibility to multiple optimization problems.

Ultimately, the OOF provides a policy-driven and model-driven framework for creating optimization applications for a broad range of use cases, based on the core ideas that most optimization problems can be solved in a declarative manner using a high-level modeling language, and recent advances in open-source optimization platforms allow the solution process to be mostly solver-independent.

The second relevant activity is the **Control Loop Automation Management Platform (CLAMP)**, a project incubated by ONAP, aimed to provide any AI-based operation within the network. More specifically, CLAMP is a platform for designing and managing control loops. It is used to design a closed loop, configure it with specific parameters for a particular network service, then deploying and undeploying it. Once deployed, the user can also update the loop with new parameters during runtime, as well as suspending and restarting it.

CLAMP aims at supporting control loops that can be used to, e.g., (i) collect data about VNFs or VNF infrastructure, (ii) perform analyses of faults, performance, and network conditions, (iii) send message describing condition to ticketing system for human intervention, or (iv) execute many actions to remediate the network condition such as restart, rebuild, migrate, or scale up/down Virtual Machine (VM) and redirect traffic.

Gap analysis. The whole ONAP project, including the OOF and CLAMP projects, is an open-source software project aimed at implementing a MANO architecture. As such, it relies on policy models defined by the industry and by SDOs. ONAP indeed supports and offers integration for most current leading standards, like those defined by ETSI, 3GPP, or O-RAN. Therefore, it inherits the same limitations of such models, which are discussed in the rest of the document.

11 Appendix C: MLOps

MLOps is a methodology that combines Machine Learning (ML) with software development operations (DevOps) and data engineering with the goal of building, training, deploying, and maintaining ML systems in productions with high reliability and efficiency guarantees. To achieve such a goal, an MLOps workflow is required that applies to multiple tasks (e.g., classification, real-time control, or predictive maintenance) and across multiple industries (e.g., telecommunications, manufacturing, or healthcare). Figure 11-1 illustrates a generic, modular and flexible MLOps workflow that is designed to bring ML solutions to any business or industry [116].

Figure 11-1. Example of MLOps workflow.

The MLOps workflow is composed by 3 main blocks: Build, Deploy and Monitor, as follows.

Build: This module contains the core ML pipeline and spans from the data ingestion until model registering. The results from this module are trained models stored in a register, which are ready to be deployed in a production environment. There are 5 internal steps in the module:

- The **data ingestion** step triggers the full ML pipeline and it deals with 4V of data (velocity, volume, veracity, and variety) by extracting data from different sources. In this step, data can be split and versioned so that any model training can be audited.
- The **model training** step takes the ingested data and performs the traditional steps of ML from data pre-processing up to the execution of the (re-)training. Notice that the training will also include the ML algorithm selection and hyperparameter tuning. The result of this step is a trained model.
- The **model testing** step takes the trained model and evaluates its performance on a separated data set, which is obtained in step 1 above and is called the testing dataset. The performance evaluation is done based on selected metrics aligned with the specific problem context. The step outcome is a report on the trained model performance. In case of unsatisfactory performance, the previous steps are re-executed until a model with better performance is obtained.
- In the **model packing** step, the trained model is serialized into a file (e.g., using the ONNX format) or containerized (e.g., using Docker) to be used in the production environment.
- The **model registering** step stores the model in a model registry. Once the model is registered, it can be downloaded and deployed as required.

Deploy: Once the models are created, trained and stored in a register in the previous module, this module allows testing the model performance and behavior in a production or production-like (e.g., prototype or pilot) environment to ensure its robustness and scalability. This implies verifying the capability of the model for inference from data batches or data streams, and/or in making business decisions. One important component in this module is the connection of the development and production environments via Continue Integration (CI) / Continue Delivery (CD) pipelines. This module is composed by the following two steps.

- The **application testing** step aims at performing robustness and performance testing before the model is integrated into the production environment to make decision that have effects on the business operations. To achieve this, the target model is deployed in (pre-production) test environments. Testing data is used to evaluate the model and the results are reviewed by a quality assurance expert. Note that the training data is sample data that has not been used during training and has been generated in the production environment, Once the performance of the model is aligned with the expected quality, the it is approved for deployment in production.
- In the **production release** step, the model that was tested and approved in the previous step is deployed in the production environment to make business decisions or generate operation values.

Monitor: This module is used to monitor, analyze and govern the performance of the ML application (i.e., the combination of the model and its DevOps application). The performance of the ML model is monitored via pre-defined metrics and the application via telemetry data. The model itself is analyzed via an explainability framework. Finally, the governance of the model is performed using alerts and actions based on the model's performance. More concretely, this translates into the following internal steps to the module.

- The **monitor step** captures information that is critical to check data integrity, model drift, and application performance over a period of time. This is fundamental to keep track of the production system's performance, health, and longevity.
- The **analyze step** is used to measure the model performance in real time in order to detect model drifting, mitigate its negative impact on the business decisions, and improve model's performance. Notice that, over the time, model drifting is expected on deployed ML models due to unforeseeable trends that could not be observed the data that was used for training the model. When model drift is detected, any of these actions can be performed: 1) alerting the quality assurance expert to take corrective actions as needed, 2) switching or updating the model, or 3) building a new model by triggering the build module in compliance with the latest data or requirements.
- The **govern step** drives the optimal performance for the business (or, more generally, the purpose of the ML system). Once the monitor and analyze steps are completed, certain alerts and actions can be triggered to govern the system. In this step, model auditing and reporting are expected to provide end-to-end traceability and explainability for production models.